

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE
2024 THIRD SPACE SYMPOSIUM**

**EXPERIENCES OF HIGHER EDUCATION
THIRD SPACE PRACTITIONERS**

EDITORS: COLIN SIMPSON, SHARON ALTENA, ELIZABETH BLACK AND PENNY WHEELER

Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium

Editors: Colin Simpson; Sharon Altena; Elizabeth Black; and Penny Wheeler

<https://qut.pressbooks.pub/sandpitsaltena>

Please cite this publication as:

Simpson, C., Altena, S., Black, E., & Wheeler, P. (Eds.). (2025). *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17677327>

For an individual contribution, please cite as, for example:

Addanki, K., Cook, H., Cosgrove, K., Ngo, L., & Tyrell, S. (2025). Building connections: Enhancing LinkedIn presence for Third Space women. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 2–3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844331>

© 2025. This work is licensed via [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Table of Contents

Foreword	vii
<i>Celia Whitchurch</i>	
Introduction	x
<i>Penny Wheeler and Colin Simpson</i>	
Acknowledgements	xiv
CONNECTING.....	1
Building connections: enhancing LinkedIn presence for third space women	2
<i>Kranthi Addanki, Helmy Cook, Karine Cosgrove, Leanne Ngo, and Simone Tyrell</i>	
What's Beyond Twitter / X?	4
<i>Meredith Hinze, Sharon Altena, and Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng</i>	
The advantages of networks and alliances for the third space	7
<i>Silke Kirberg</i>	
IDENTITY.....	9
Theorising the third space.....	10
<i>Stephen Abblitt</i>	
I'm in higher education's third space: who is here with me?	12
<i>Zoë Allman</i>	
Collaborative autoethnography on third space identity.....	14
<i>Puvaneswari P Arumugam and Mahen Jayawardena</i>	
On the (in)visibility of librarians in third space literature	15
<i>Heidi Butters-Stabb</i>	
The seven-year itch: Are directors' and learning designers' perceptions of the role of learning designers a marriage made in heaven?	17
<i>Ruth Greenaway, Dom McGrath, and Christine Slade</i>	
Hard-pressed, but not crushed: A disposition of the heart in the space in-between	19
<i>Rebecca Kan and Eliza Yeo Hui</i>	

(De)constructing the professional identities of third space practitioners through zine making.....	27
<i>Kate Molloy</i>	
Standing out in the third space	29
<i>Donna Murray</i>	
Knowing, doing and showing.....	32
<i>Sue Sharpe, Jenny Boreland, and Tanya Henry</i>	
Make your pitch: let's solve the question of third space titles	34
<i>Colin Simpson</i>	
What does the third space look like?	36
<i>Wendy Taleo</i>	
Empowering professional identity ... through third space collaboration....	39
<i>Claire Toogood and Katy Hale</i>	
Framework for academic developers	40
<i>Kate Tregloan and Naima Iftikhar</i>	
PRACTICE.....	41
Reclaiming the resources we make	42
<i>Dana Bui</i>	
Reflecting on educational design practice	48
<i>Josephine Hook, Julie Luu, Prudence Perry, Frances Broomhead, Aster Cosmos, Yogita Ahuja, Brendan Boniface, Cathy Sell, Carmen Sapsed, and Andrew Junor</i>	
Capturing third space skills and competencies.....	61
<i>Keith Heggart, Kate Mitchell, and Colin Simpson</i>	
What can learning design do?.....	63
<i>Jeremy Stothers</i>	
Partners in crime.....	65
<i>Diana Saragi Turnip, Jon Xiating Cai, and Zara Khan</i>	
Journeys into third space working	66
<i>Charlotte Verney, Kelly Vere, and Tara Webster-Deakin</i>	

RECOGNITION	68
Establishing your credibility	69
<i>Sharon Altena, Meredith Hinze, and Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng</i>	
Sharing the oxygen mask	74
<i>Cristy Bartlett and Kate Derrington</i>	
Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of Third Space professionals	75
<i>Dustin Hosseini</i>	
Learning Designers: To define or not to define	76
<i>Dan Laurence and Meredith Hinze</i>	
"Inside the third space" podcast series	78
<i>Diana Saragi Turnip, Meredith Macaulay, Ellie McDougall, Morgan Harris, Nasrin Danish, Swapneel Thite, Jon Xiating Cai, Zara Khan, Agnee Amarnath, Camile Moray, and Neil Lawrence</i>	
RELATIONSHIPS.....	81
Beyond the binary: Third space allyship and equity in the academy	82
<i>Aster Cosmos and Miriam Reynoldson</i>	
Co-creating in the third space with friends	89
<i>Jane Kiddell and Steph Quirk</i>	
How sense-making drives successful partnerships	90
<i>Tran Nguyen and Lisa Soviero</i>	
I am not a chicken farmer	92
<i>Mark Parry</i>	
Explore a new framework to evolve third space relationships.....	98
<i>Natalia Veles and Colin Simpson</i>	
RESEARCH.....	107
Research for all in the future university	108
<i>Olivia Inwood</i>	
Cover to cover: A thesis radio journey.....	109
<i>Colin Simpson</i>	

TECHNOLOGY	115
To trial or not to trial?	116
<i>Colleen Hodgins and Naomi Millgate</i>	
Uniting expertise	118
<i>Minh Huynh, Fran Van Den Berg, Osu Lilje, Liana Pozza, and Floris Van Ogtrop</i>	
WORKPLACE	119
Uncontracted: Reimagining work and identity in higher education’s third space.....	120
<i>Joanne Caldwell</i>	
Navigating the ebbs and flows of change	124
<i>Katie Freund, Karlene Dickens, and Fang Li</i>	
Third space careers visualised.....	125
<i>Emily McIntosh and Diane Nutt</i>	
(Re)imagining the future of faculty PD	126
<i>Alexandra Mihai and Colin Simpson</i>	
From third space to shared space	128
<i>Miriam Reynoldson</i>	
Speculative future university 2050.....	136
<i>Carmen Vallis and Wendy Taleo</i>	
APPENDICES.....	139
List of Slowposium sessions	140
In-person program.....	145
List of contributors.....	147

Foreword

Celia Whitchurch

The Third Space Symposium and associated Slowposium in November 2024 have been an imaginative application of the concept of third space, and these published Proceedings are very welcome.

The concept of *third space* was first applied to higher education in 2008, arising out of a project (Whitchurch, 2008) for the UK Leadership Foundation for Higher Education (now merged into AdvanceHE). It has since been recognised worldwide as academics have become increasingly dependent on a range of teaching and learning professionals to develop their teaching, in particular online programmes. They also require sophisticated support, for example, in writing grant applications and impact statements in complex grant acquisition processes. Furthermore, the use of AI creates a pressing challenge in contemporary higher education environments, requiring knowledgeable experts who can assist in dealing with its implications.

At the same time, professional staff have been gaining doctorates as their activity becomes increasingly project-orientated. There is a growing sense of working in partnership with academics, with evidence that early career researchers now consider third space roles as a career option (Kerridge et al., 2023). However, individuals can feel frustrated if they sense that their contribution does not have parity with that of academic colleagues. As a result, there are issues of visibility, recognition and inclusion, as well as of contracts and career structures. The Symposium and Slowposium therefore offered a valuable and timely resource, particularly as they included representations other than the written word. Key themes from the resulting papers include the practical applications of third space working, recognition by and partnership with academic colleagues, the appropriateness of institutional structures and titles, overcoming liminal positioning, capturing and validating content and outputs, and career journeys in third space.

Over 100 publications have taken up the theme of third space in higher education since 2008. These are encapsulated in two recent literature reviews (Thorpe & Partridge, 2024; Veles et al., 2023). Ideas about the building of collaborative and institutional capital in third space have emerged (Veles, 2022; Whitchurch, 2026 forthcoming), as well as the use of Mode 3 knowledge and social capital (Whitchurch, 2023, 2024). Four special issues of journals – *Workplace: A Journal for Academic Labor* (2023); the *London Review of Education* (2024); the *Journal of the Association for Learning Development in Higher Education* (2025); and *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education* (2026 forthcoming) – have appeared in recent years, and a third space blog (<https://www.thirdspaceperspectives.com>(JISC) list allows for continued discussion. Although the third space movement has gained significant momentum, the concept has also been challenged as representing “no space” (Hall, 2022, p.27), while others have suggested that “we are all third space now” (Whitchurch, 2013, p. 140). Moreover, there can be tensions with maintaining a distinctive professional identity, for example for librarians, who have their own qualifications and membership body.

Looking to the future, questions remain about the creation and recognition of third space environments and those working in them. An initial step could be to devise a third space person specification for recruitment and professional development purposes, including generic qualities as well as role-specific requirements. Other possible mechanisms might include, for example:

- the creation of a third career track with associated contracts, job specifications, and promotion criteria to take account of, for example, innovation in teaching and learning and the digital environment;
- recognition of applied, user-based Mode 3 knowledge that emphasises situated knowledge, local understandings, and specific contexts, for example via commendation in annual review processes and recognition in promotion criteria;
- the incorporation of crossover points and/or secondments for people who might wish to move in and out of third space activity, for example linked to the term of a project;
- a time allowance for those who are appropriately qualified to undertake research and teaching if they so wish, whatever type of contract they may have;
- encouragement in the form of study leave and/or financial support for individuals to pursue doctorates if they do not have them;
- the establishment of national policy statements, possibly using the UK Technicians Commitment (Vere et al., 2024) as a model, to ensure visibility, recognition, career development, and sustainability for this group of staff.

(Whitchurch 2025).

However, bottom-up pressure may be necessary to make progress in this respect. In practice it may, at least to some extent, be up to individuals to persuade their line managers, for example as part of the annual review process, of the advantages of these types of initiatives, including constructive working relationships and higher levels of satisfaction and retention. The thriving third space community will also, it is to be hoped, be able to share ideas about practical steps that can be taken, using what are now well-developed online discussion fora.

Colin, Penny, Elizabeth, Sharon and everyone involved in the Symposium are to be congratulated on this publication and its contribution to the various debates around the concept of third space in higher education, and I hope that it will trigger further debate, particularly about career development and futures.

References

- Hall, J. (2022). Understanding and debating the third space: Achieving strategy. In E. McIntosh & D. Nutt (Eds.), *The impact of the integrated practitioner in higher education: Studies in third space professionalism* (pp. 26–32). Routledge.
- Kerridge, S., Poli, S., & Yang-Yoshihara, M. (2023). *The Emerald handbook of research management and administration around the world*. Emerald Publishing.
- Thorpe, C., & Partridge, H. (2024). The third space in higher education: A scoping review. *Higher Education Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-024-00374-z>

- Veles, N. (2022). *Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration*. Taylor and Francis.
- Veles, N., Graham, C., & Ovaska, C. (2023). University professional staff roles, identities and spaces of interaction: Systematic review of literature published in 2000–2020. *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 7(2), 127–168.
- Vere, K., Verney, C., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2024). Crossing and dismantling boundaries: Recognising the value of professional staff within higher education. *London Review of Education*, 22(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.22.1.29>
- Whitchurch, C. (2008). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 377–96.
- Whitchurch, C. (2013). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of third space professionals*. Routledge.
- Whitchurch, C. (2023). Rehabilitating third space professionals in contemporary higher education institutions. *Workplace: A Journal for Academic Labor*, (33), 23–33. <https://ices.library.ubc.ca/index.php/workplace/article/view/186839>
- Whitchurch, C. (2024). From “service” to “partnership”: Harnessing social capital in support of activity in third space environments. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 6(3), 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2024.2344132>
- Whitchurch, C. (2025 in press). Achieving inclusion: The case of university staff working in third space between academic and professional spheres of activity. *Social Inclusion*, Article 9596. <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.9596>
- Whitchurch, C. (2026 forthcoming). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of third space professionals* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

About the author

Celia Whitchurch

University College, London

Dr Whitchurch is Honorary Associate Professor at UCL Institute of Education, UK.

Introduction

Penny Wheeler and Colin Simpson

The idea of the ‘third space’ was popularised by Homi K. Bhabha (1994), a scholar in postcolonial studies. In simple terms, it describes the hybrid area that emerges when two cultures or identities interact. This idea has been picked up in many areas of scholarship and was adopted in the 2000s by Celia Whitchurch to describe the complex and overlapping relationships between academic and professional staff in her seminal article “Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of Third Space Professionals in UK Higher Education” (2008).

Over time, additional terms for third space professionals have emerged including *third space practitioners* (Arumugam, 2024; Behari-Leak & le Roux, 2018; McIntosh & Nutt, 2022), a useful distinction for contexts where the term third space “professional” excludes “academic” staff, and the term represents a wide array of people working in both academic and professional/administrative roles with responsibilities in both academic and professional domains in higher education. These roles include, but are not limited to, learning/instructional designers, educational technologists, academic developers, research support staff, curriculum officers, academic skills developers and more.

The proliferation of third space roles has happened over a period when universities have needed to adapt operations and structure in response to contextual challenges such as massification; inadequate funding; interdisciplinary approaches; increased international mobility for students; and the ubiquity and growth of educational technologies and digital environments. Third space practitioners have been deeply engaged with these challenges, given their core responsibilities for devising and implementing changes for better student experience and organisational development, and have also been keen to support people with the same mission in other institutions.

At the end of 2023, observing the rapid growth in the number of sessions at the ASCILITE (Australasian Society for Computers in Learning in Tertiary Education) conference which centred the experiences and contributions of third space practitioners, members of the ASCILITE TELedvisors Network special interest group decided to hold a third space symposium. This was initially envisaged as a one-day, in-person event linked to the 2024 ASCILITE conference but the surge of interest from third space practitioners quickly saw us extend this to include an online asynchronous ‘slowposium’ in the two weeks leading up to this event. We connected with colleagues in the UK and Ireland who had held a small third space online event earlier in the year to help make this a truly international event.

Over the 16 days of the online Slowposium, more than 500 participants from Australasia, Europe, Asia, and North America read, watched, discussed, created and engaged with 52 contributions from more than 100 third space practitioners. On Sunday 1 December 2024 more than 70 participants attended our in-person symposium, enjoying 19 presentations and workshops from 30 practitioners. This strong participation highlighted both the diversity of voices in this community and the desire to share our experiences and perspectives on a vital but sometimes poorly understood part of the education sector.

Both the Slowposium and the in-person symposium program presented the practitioners' contributions organised under eight categories that represent some **Themes** for third space work: the contributions in these proceedings are summarised via these themes, below.

Connecting: *how we communicate with each other and build community in the third space.* A key task for all third space practitioners is to provide the places where the different subgroups of a university or college can exchange ideas, processes, and values. It is no wonder then, when it comes to supporting connections within our own community, that we bring our strengths as “collaboration champions”, as Veles et al. (2019) characterise us, to build a family (Harland & Staniforth, 2008) from scattered individuals. The symposia programs provided for synchronous networking as well as exploring some of the platforms where third space practitioners can find each other, whether in regional or transnational communities (Kirberg, in these proceedings) or using different educational technologies and professional platforms such as LinkedIn (Addanki, Cook, Cosgrove, Ngo & Tyrell) and the successors to Twitter (Hinze, Altena & Ng).

Identity: *who third space practitioners are: our roles, titles and values.* Embracing the label “third space” and its genealogy and implications (Abblitt, in these proceedings) was only the start of the exploration of professional identity which symposium participants undertook. While accounts of identity in third space literature can be individualised and introspective (Simpson, 2025, p. 262, on academic developers in particular), we saw in the symposium many thoroughly community-centred approaches to considering identity. Contributors reflected on close working partnerships (Arumugam & Jayawardena; Kan & Yeo, who work to “creatively creolise boundaries between the centre and the periphery”; Toogood & Hale) that support personal and professional resilience and development; they invited collective responses to third space experiences (Allman; Taleo); and they longed for change to “make our way of working the gold standard in academic life” (Murray). Roles within the third space ecosystem were examined (Greenway, McGrath & Slade) and framework designs for these roles were shared (Sharpe, Boreland & Henry, for learning designers; Tregloan & Iftikhar, for academic developers). The question of third space identity was approached head-on (Simpson, “let’s solve the question of third space titles”), and more obliquely, through the counterculture of zine-making (Molloy). We also heard the call to be more inclusive in scoping the third space identity (Butters-Stabb).

Practice: *the things we do working in the third space.* Professional identities are formed “within specific discursive formations and practices” (Hall, 1996, quoted in Caldwell, 2022, p. 141), and contributors were keen to share details of their practices: “there is an appetite for building structures of recognition, not only in terms of professional development, but in terms of shared identity formation” (Heggart, Mitchell & Simpson, in these proceedings). Participants explored “some of the gnarlier issues of working in the third space” (Verney, Vere & Webster-Deakin) and highlighted the importance of underpinning practice with theory (Stothers; Turnip, Cai & Khan). A key takeaway was the value for the practitioner of evidencing their practice (Bui; Hook et al.).

Recognition: *demonstrating our value and raising understanding of our contributions.* While formal recognition programs are useful for some third space practitioners (Brogt, 2021), contributors considered other pathways as well, taking the opportunity of the symposium to outline their achievements (Turnip, Macaulay et al.) and to discuss how to establish better visibility (Bartlett & Derrington; Hosseini) and credibility (Altena, Hinze & Ng). The ambiguity of third space practice was discussed by Simpson (in “Cover to cover”) and in detail by Kan & Yeo,

and it emerged at the centre of the debate that Laurence and Hinze conducted on defining one third space role, that of learning designer, indicating the difficulty of recognising “a maturing profession grappling with fundamental questions about identity, quality, and inclusivity”.

Relationships: *building better collaborations with the people that we work with.* Alongside “ambiguity”, “tension” was another term which made frequent appearances throughout the symposium, and contributors did not hesitate to detail the multiple strategies and mindsets they adopt when dealing with the tensions of third space practice and of the university and college workplace in general. Veles and Simpson took participants on a four-phase journey from contestation to transformation; Cosmos and Reynoldson made the case for equity through allyship. Sensemaking was the key for Nguyen’s examples of third space-to- academic relationships, and Kiddell and Quirk saw third space participation as inherently relational and collaborative, reminding us of the role of trust in our working relationships. Through a narrative of his professional history, and under what is perhaps the best title of all our contributions, “I am not a chicken farmer”, Parry argued that establishing a fruitful relationship with the subject matter expert, in whatever educational context you are working, is an essential for effective learning design: “Together we create what’s best / Respect and collaboration – our true test.”

Research: *developing better understanding of the third space and the people who work in it.* We have been aware in compiling these proceedings of the strong ethical boundaries of the research space, as it has governed what we can and could not include in this collection of contributions, given the symposium was not designed as a research project, and we did not seek ethical clearance to document participant contributions. Some of the sessions were ‘of the moment’ and not suited to publication, but, from the sessions we were able to include, there is, despite these constraints, a valuable overview of key ideas and aspects of third space practice in tertiary education in the 2020s. Furthermore, the symposium program did include some of the formal research on third space practice and practitioners currently being conducted, and we have included two contributions that reflect on the role of research and researchers in the third space, from Inwood (“Research for all”) and Simpson (“Cover to cover”).

Technology: *the tools we use and the ways we use them.* As described above, the symposium was conceived as running alongside the annual ASCILITE conference, and, as we expected, presentations focussed on technology for learning had their natural home in that conference program. In these proceedings, however, we have two discussions of technology as part of third space practice. Hodgins and Millgate probe the issue (perhaps, the ambiguity or tension) of the third spacers’ role in trialling new technologies: are we “invading others’ space”?; and Huynh, Van Den Berg, Lilje, Pozza, and Van Ogtrop provide a case that exemplifies how third space work spans technology, policy and partnerships with their session on the integral partnership of educational designers and academics in navigating AI in education.

Workplace: *the practicalities of being a third space practitioner.* The tagline for the in-person symposium day was “Working well in higher education”, and this final theme of “workplace” attracted many contributions, all of which sought in some way to reimagine the current place. Caldwell, well published in this field, asked us to rethink contractual boundaries between professional and academic domains, while McIntosh and Nutt, whose book on the integrated practitioner was also highly cited by symposium contributors, looked to chart institutional boundaries as a journey. Practitioners in the TELT team at Australian National University

(Freund, Dickens & Li) looked at workplace change, its uncertainty and stressors. Then there were the contributions that offered a complete re-think of university structures, each worth serious consideration: these are the final contributions in these proceedings, from Mihai and Simpson; Reynoldson; and Vallis and Taleo.

As organisers of this event, it wildly exceeded our expectations in terms of engagement and the insights shared by everyone who contributed and participated. It was exhausting but vital in shining a light on the essential work of everyone working in third space roles.

Maybe we will even do it again someday.

References

- Arumugam, P. P. (2024). Negotiating the assumptions and identity tensions surrounding third space academics/professionals. In K. Heggart & M. Fatayer (Eds.), *Designing learning experiences for inclusivity and diversity: Advice for learning designers*. UTS ePress. <https://oercollective.caul.edu.au/designing-learning-experiences/chapter/negotiating-the-assumptions-and-identity-tensions-surrounding-third-space-academics-professionals/>
- Behari-Leak, K. & le Roux, N. (2018). Between a rock and a hard place, third space practitioners exercise agency. *Perspectives in Education*, 36(1), 30–43. <https://journals.ufs.ac.za/index.php/pie/article/view/3582>
- Bhabha, H. K. (1994). *The location of culture*. Routledge.
- Brogt, E. (2021). Engaging with different professional recognition and development opportunities for academic developers. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 26(4), 477–480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2020.1840380>
- Caldwell, J. (2022). Professional identity and professional services staff: Understanding and impact. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 26(4), 140–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2022.2073288>
- Harland, T., & Staniforth, D. (2008). A family of strangers: The fragmented nature of academic development. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 13(6), 669–678. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562510802452392>
- McIntosh, E., & Nutt, D. (2022). *The impact of the integrated practitioner in higher education: Studies in third space professionalism*. Routledge.
- Simpson, C. (2025). *Educator advisors in Australian higher education: Their roles, purpose and contribution to learning and teaching*. The University of Sydney, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Sydney School of Education and Social Work. <https://hdl.handle.net/2123/34308>
- Veles, N., Carter, M.-A., & Boon, H. (2019). Complex collaboration champions: University third space professionals working together across borders. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 23(2–3), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2018.1428694>
- Whitchurch, C. (2008). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 377–96.

About the authors

Penny Wheeler

University of Technology Sydney

Penny is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and a student of learning design at UTS.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7856-5093>

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

Acknowledgements

Putting on the Third Space Symposium 2024 was an enormous endeavour which drew on the expertise and goodwill of many people. They volunteered their time to create an event celebrating this community and we, the organisers, are incredibly grateful. In alphabetical order, we thank:

Sharon Altena, Elizabeth Black, Gosia Drewniok, Keith Heggart, Meredith Hinze, Dan Laurence, Maeve O'Dwyer, Rowan Peter, Rebecca Sanderson, Sue Sharpe, Colin Simpson, Wendy Taleo, Antony Tibbs, and Penny Wheeler.

For their invaluable support on the day at the in-person Symposium, we thank:

Stephen Abblitt, Yogita Ahuja, Nik Alksnis, Puvaneswari P Arumugam, Craig Bellamy, Jenny Boreland, Bronwyn Disseldorp, Katie Freund, May Kocatepe, Asli McCarthy, Kate Mitchell, Bettina Schwenger and James Thompson.

Thanks to the wider TELedvisors Network community for inspiration and encouragement.

We thank ASCILITE and the ASCILITE 2024 Conference organising team – particular Roger Brown and Thomas Cochrane – for their logistical support of the event, and also the University of Melbourne as our host for the in-person day.

Thanks also to ML Huppertz and the Association for Tertiary Education Management (ATEM) for their generous sponsorship of the Symposium.

We are profoundly grateful to everyone who created contributions and shared their experiences and understanding of the third space in both the Slowposium and the Symposium and also to all the participants who took part and expanded the discussion.

Thanks also to Celia Whitchurch, de facto patron saint of the higher education third space, for your enthusiasm and encouragement of this event.

Finally, we thank you for being part of the third space family and/or for caring enough to read our contributions.

Connecting

How we communicate with each other and build community in the third space

Building connections: enhancing LinkedIn presence for third space women

Kranthi Addanki, Helmy Cook, Karine Cosgrove, Leanne Ngo, and Simone Tyrell

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844331>

As third space educators, we navigate the complex intersection of professional and academic roles, which often lacks clear career progression pathways compared to traditional academia. Women are disproportionately represented in third space roles but remain underrepresented in senior leadership positions. This can lead to feelings of isolation, particularly in the increasingly remote working environment. Simultaneously, the rapid evolution of higher education, technology, and diverse student needs demands continual professional development. Through interactive discussions and feedback, we aimed to co-create a tailored approach to using LinkedIn as a tool for career advancement in the third space, addressing challenges unique to women in leadership. Participants' insights were invaluable in refining these strategies to support leadership growth among third space professionals who are women.

Reflection

We ran an interactive 30-minute workshop going through each of four implications (Building your LinkedIn brand; Networking for success; Managing imposter syndrome; and Content strategy development) from our ASCILITE poster. We had engaging discussions with like-minded workshop attendees. The main take-away from the exercise was that there are limited resources on career guidance for women in third space professions, which provoked us to create and enhance the Leadership Identity Framework for Transformation (LIFT) framework.

References

- Ngo, L., Cook, H., Tyrell, S., Cosgrove, K., & Addanki, K. (2024). Women leading in the Third space: Leveraging LinkedIn to build professional identity. In T. Cochrane, V. Narayan, E. Bone, C. Deneen, M. Saligari, K. Tregloan, & R. Vanderburg (Eds.), *Navigating the terrain: Emerging frontiers in learning spaces, pedagogies, and technologies. Proceedings ASCILITE 2024*. Melbourne (pp. 61-62). <https://doi.org/10.14742/apubs.2024.1399>
- Ngo, L., Cook, H., Tyrell, S., Cosgrove, K., & Addanki, K. (2024). *Leadership Identity Framework for Transformation (LIFT)*. <https://sites.google.com/monash.edu/lift/home?pli=1>

*About the authors***Kranthi Addanki***James Cook University*

Dr Kranthi Addanki is a Learning Science researcher and IT Lecturer at James Cook University. Connect via [LinkedIn](#) to know more.

Helmy Cook*Monash University*

Dr Helmy Cook is Senior Lecturer (education focused) and Senior Curriculum Lead at the Monash Medical School. Connect with her on [LinkedIn](#).

Karine Cosgrove*Griffith University*

Karine Cosgrove is a Senior Learning Designer, empowering educators to develop innovative, student-centred practices. Connect with her on [LinkedIn](#).

Leanne Ngo*La Trobe University*

Dr Leanne Ngo is an Associate Professor advancing digital learning, student engagement, employability, and initiatives that empower women in technology. Connect with her on [LinkedIn](#).

Simone Tyrell*Deakin University*

Simone Tyrell is a Learning Designer, scaffolding learning experiences that are engaging, student-centred, and inclusive. Connect with her on [LinkedIn](#).

What's Beyond Twitter / X?

Meredith Hinze, Sharon Altena, and Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844894>

Working within the higher education sector, particularly within the third space, can be an isolating experience with limited opportunities for professional development (Silvey et al., 2018; Trust et al., 2017). As such, the development of a Professional Learning Network (PLN) takes on heightened importance for third space professionals. Trust et al. (2016) define a PLN as a “uniquely personalized, complex system of interactions consisting of people, resources, and digital tools that support ongoing learning and professional growth” (p. 28). We commence this article with the opportunity for you to meet us, the presenters, to hear about how we leverage our professional networks. More information about us is also available via [our website](#).

Figure 1: How we leverage our professional networks

The use of social media is one of the digital tools that can be used by third space professionals to expand their PLN beyond the walls of their institution. During the pandemic, Twitter was the “go to” platform for learning designers to ask questions, offer support, share resources and communicate with those in other institutions globally. Our interest at that time resulted in us undertaking research, scraping and analysing data from the TELedvisors Twitter feed, to better understand the social media platform and pandemic conversations during this pivotal time. We concluded that Twitter was an underutilised, non-hierarchical, open platform for learning designers to share their ideas, promote their work and to have conversations with a global community of like-minded individuals (Ng et al., 2023).

What was once a thriving, central, global gathering space has since been shattered, resulting in a fragmented social media landscape (Carrigan, 2023). Our paper “Look who’s talking: Professional conversations of learning designers on Twitter during COVID-19” (Ng et al., 2023), situates use

of the platform as an important component of a learning designer's professional learning network, and helped to set the scene for our topic discussions over the fortnight of the Slowposium.

We were interested in discussing with the community what's beyond Twitter/X? What do people use now beyond Twitter? How do we build and sustain communities of practice? How do we promote and share our work? How do we find out about professional development opportunities? How do we think about and form professional learning networks and how do we connect at a more international and global level?

During the Slowposium, participants responded to a series of provocations and polls, and engaged in very lively and active discussion, reflecting on what platforms they were using to connect with the community and why they were involved or not involved. The discussion forum noted the exodus from Twitter, mourning the loss of the critical mass the community had and the fragmentation of social media with the community using separate platforms. The result from the polls put LinkedIn out in front as platform most used to connect with others professionally, as well as platform most used for professional development, followed by Twitter/X and Bluesky. Contributions to the Padlet wall resource and in the discussion forum included a Bluesky starter pack and basic explainer resource, and tips for using LinkedIn for peer learning and building connections.

The high level of engagement in our session received formal acknowledgement at the in-person Third Space Symposium event. Reflecting a year on, while Bluesky seems like the closest thing to Twitter, it hasn't really taken off. Perhaps we've become more used to using LinkedIn to network and build community than we had a year ago? The drive for connection, support, dialogue and community, that was a common theme expressed across posts during the Slowposium, strongly remains.

References

- Carrigan, M. (2023, August 24). Where now for academics on social media, post Twitter? *The Round Table: The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*.
<https://www.commonwealthroundtable.co.uk/general/education/where-now-for-academics-on-social-media-post-twitter/>
- Ng, R., Altena, S., & Hinze, M. (2023). Look who's talking: Professional conversations of learning designers on Twitter during COVID-19. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 39(3), 91–113. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.8022>
- Silvey, V., Pejcinovic, L., & Snowball, T. (2018). Crossing divides: Professional development for third space professionals. In C. Bossu & N. Brown (Eds.), *Professional and support staff in higher education* (pp. 39–54). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-6858-4_6
- Trust, T., Carpenter, J. P., & Krutka, D. G. (2017). Moving beyond silos: Professional learning networks in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 35, 1-11.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.06.001>
- Trust, T., Krutka, D. G., & Carpenter, J. P. (2016). Together we are better: Professional learning networks for teachers. *Computers & Education*, 102(1), 15–34.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.06.007>

*About the authors***Meredith Hinze***The University of Melbourne*

Meredith Hinze is Manager, eLearning/eTeaching. Her research interests explore professional identity, leadership and the learning design profession.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2908-9021>

[LinkedIn](#)

Sharon Altena*Queensland University of Technology*

Sharon Altena is a Senior Curriculum and Learning Designer within the Learning and Teaching Unit. She undertakes research relating to belonging and the learning design profession.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4260-7006>

[LinkedIn](#)

Dr Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng*University of Wollongong*

Dr Rebecca Ng is a Research Fellow within the Faculty of Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities, ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1191-8242>

The advantages of networks and alliances for the third space

Silke Kirberg

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844911>

This session was an exploration of what kind of networks are active in supra-regional and regional contexts in the field of instructional design/eLearning, specifically on LMSs such as Moodle but also in other areas of the third space, and how we get involved and help each other. The questions for the Third Space Symposium (3SS) were based on experiences gained from collaboration in various networks in German-speaking countries, in which employees from the third space come together to work on topics related to technology-enhanced learning. In the 3SS the attendees discussed and collected their networks and explained to each other how they benefited from them, including not only well-known associations like, for example, ASCILITE, but also informal or less-known networks. The results of the discussions were that participants were inspired to become active in a network or learned how to join an alliance.

Provocation

What kind of networks are active in supra-regional and regional contexts in the field of instructional design/eLearning, or specifically on LMS such as Moodle or in other areas of the third space?

Reflection

The discussion in the 3SS led to filling a world map with the networks mentioned and structuring them into different categories.

We considered the features of professional networks that have a formal structure and a wide, supra-regional reach, such as ASCILITE or the German-registered association Moodle an Hochschulen e.V., which hold conferences and webinars and are supported by an advisory board. The German Moodle association is one example of the networks that are active in the third space which are interested in promoting one specific digital tool: the association also uses Moodle as a virtual platform for the exchange of knowledge and mutual support. There is not only this supra-regional wide organization which is financed by its members but also the regional project Moodle.NRW funded by the government of the German county North Rhein–Westphalia. Both networks support each other and are engaged in the global Moodle community.

Other networks, on the other hand, deal with specific technology-enhanced teaching methods, for example ePortfolios Australia or the several German-speaking networks focusing on E-Assessment and E-examination didactics. In the author's region, the state's Ministry of Science promotes cooperative projects between more than 30 state-run applied science universities, universities, and art and music colleges. Those activities enable different people from the third space to work together and present their results at conferences.

This selection raises the question of what specific added value regional, supra-regional and global contacts offer for knowledge exchange and how easy they are to find and access. The TELedvisors Network, a special interest group of ASCILITE, takes a particularly inviting approach, appealing to educational advisors from the technology-supported field of learning and teaching to join this community of practice. The network is international and covers a wide range of topics from professional practice, such as teaching and learning, LMS, research projects, and important exchanges on professional development.

References and readings

- [bridge]. Konsortium des Verbundprojekts (Eds.) (2019). Digitale Hochschulbrücke westliches Ruhrgebiet I Niederrhein [bridge]: Projektergebnisse und Empfehlungen. [Digital University Bridge Western Ruhr Area I Lower Rhine [bridge]: Project results and recommendations]. https://www.hs-niederrhein.de/fileadmin/dateien/eLearning/PDF_s_Website/eLearning_fuer_Lehrende/Handreichung_DH.NRW-Projekt_bridge.pdf
- Berkemeier, M., Bilo, A., Fischer, Y., Fortmann, M., Frommer, A., Graf-Schlattmann, M., Gollan, H., Hahne, N., Huth, D., Kamin, A.-M., Keller, A. M., Kirberg, S., Pahlke-Kullik, K., Stegemerten, B., Temps, T. T., Ackeren, I. v., Wilde, M., & Wrenger, B. (2017). *E-Assessment in der Hochschulpraxis: Empfehlungen zur Verankerung von E-Assessments in NRW* [E-assessment in university practice: Recommendations for embedding e-assessments in North Rhein-Westphalia]. D. M. Meister & G. Oevel (Eds.). <https://doi.org/10.17185/dupublico/44292>
- Ceylan, I., Kirberg, S., & Striewe, M. (2022). *Erprobung der Interoperabilität von E-Assessment-Werkzeugen über die Grenze von Hochschulen hinweg* [Testing the interoperability of e-assessment tools across university boundaries]. e-Prüfungs-Symposium 2022, Hamburg. https://www.hs-niederrhein.de/fileadmin/dateien/eLearning/PDF_s_Website/eLearning_fuer_Lehrende/EPS2022-Ceylan-Kirberg-Striewe.pdf
- Moodle.NRW. (n.d.). Kompetenzzentrum Moodle [Moodle Collective Knowledge Hub]. NRW & Community. Retrieved November 20, 2025 from <https://moodlenrw.de/>
- Moodle an Hochschulen e.V. (n.d.). Wissens-DB [Knowledge base]. Retrieved November 20, 2025 from <https://moodle-an-hochschulen.de/wissens-db/>
- Nutt, D., & McIntosh, E. (2025). The power of social capital: The significance of relationships in third space practice. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, 33. <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1197>

About the author

Silke Kirberg

Niederrhein University of Applied Sciences

Silke Kirberg heads up the eLearning department and is particularly active in networks relating to e-exams, Moodle (as Chair of Moodle North Rhein–Westphalia) and AI. www.hsnr.de/elearning

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7243-0670>

[LinkedIn](#)

Identity

Who third space practitioners are: our roles, titles and values

Theorising the third space

Stephen Abblitt

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844932>

The massive growth of hybrid roles crossing the traditional academic/ professional boundary in higher education has given rise to voluminous research and theory on the so-called “third space”, most notably by Whitchurch (2008, 2012). But what is the third space? What are the conceptual origins of the third space, and what does this mean for our use of the term here and now today, and for our practices and positionalities, individually and collectively, as third space professionals?

This interactive presentation challenged participants to reflect on a critical–philosophical genealogy of the concept through three key twentieth-century thinkers: Jacques Derrida, Homi Bhabha, and Edward Soja.

- Derrida’s (1982) concept of *différance* was theorised as a critical gesture for opening the gap or interval between binarized oppositions such as speech/writing, here/there, self/other, insider/outsider, or academic/professional.
- This informed Bhabha’s (2004) theorisation of the liminal or interstitial “third space” where cultural encounters occurred, and where new identities and possibilities emerged, between dominant and subordinate cultures.
- Soja’s (1996) “third space” then complemented Bhabha’s perspective, exploring how different spatial practices and discourses intersected but also fostered sites of resistance to dominant power structures.

By tracing the genealogy of the concept, the presentation hoped to better inform our understanding of third space roles, identities and positions, as well as how such thought can be harnessed to challenge and transform dominant institutional power structures that seek to marginalise those of us who work in that gap or interval between the academic and the professional.

In the ensuing workshop and discussion, participants were challenged to draw on their collective personal and professional experience working in the “third space” to explore and test how this critical–philosophical genealogy of the concept might inform our understanding of our “third space” roles and identities now and into the future, including the potential challenges or limitations in applying the concept of the “third space” to our work. This included creating/drawing their own spatial metaphors to describe the spaces we inhabit and our interstitial positionality within the university.

References

- Bhabha, H. (2004). *The location of culture* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Derrida, J. (1982). *Différance* (A. Bass, Trans.). In *Margins of philosophy* (pp. 3–27). Chicago University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226541075.001.0001>

- Soja, E. W. (1996). *Thirdspace: Journeys to Los Angeles and other real-and-imagined places*. Blackwell.
- Whitchurch, C. (2008). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 377–396.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2008.00387.x>
- Whitchurch, C. (2012). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of 'third space' professionals*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203098301>

About the author

Stephen Abblitt

Keypath

Stephen Abblitt is a learning designer, educational researcher and literary scholar. He is currently Academic Development Manager for Keypath Education (Asia-Pacific).

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6866-2225>

[Google Scholar](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

I'm in higher education's third space: who is here with me?

Zoë Allman

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844946>

At the time of the Third Space Symposium (3SS), the third space was a concept I regularly encountered in articles, calls, and at conferences. I increasingly believed I was in the third space and wanted to understand who was there with me. By exploring who else was in the third space we would better understand current perspectives of higher education, the roles and relationships of those who consider themselves third space practitioners, how we all contribute to greater understanding and knowledge of the third space, and how we can ensure that we recognise and support one another.

As an academic leader in middle-senior management, when I first came across the concept I thought I was exempt, that the third space was not an area that academics or leaders could be part of, but I increasingly realised that this isn't so. Positioning this provocation for the 3SS, I posed a series of questions, inviting feedback via the 3SS forum; those questions included:

- Who is here in higher education's third space?
- How did you enter the third space?
- What makes you feel part of the third space?
- If you previously felt exempt, what led you to recognising your place in the third space?
- Have you always been part of the third space?
- How do we welcome fellow third space inhabitants?
- Other reflections, thoughts, and comments.

The aim of this provocation was to spark discussion, ignite ideas, and collate responses.

Reflections

The topic sparked interest and engagement, leading to being short-listed for the “best fora” during the 3SS. Delegates were very open in the experiences they shared, details of the roles they undertake and how they found themselves in the third space. The idea of questioning academic leadership positioning within the third space drew interest, with reflections from others around whether they previously would have considered such roles exempt, as I had. There was a general sense of the need for greater recognition and celebration of the activity happening within the third space, and a desire for more formal recognition of this work.

Further work

Prior to the 3SS, I received ethical approval from my institution to undertake research extending explorations into this topic. Delegates at the 3SS and another event, an online conference in the

autumn of 2024, were informed of this additional research and invited to participate in a separate questionnaire. The findings from this questionnaire have been analysed and submitted as a case study to a journal: the article is currently under final review and due for publication in the summer of 2026.

References

- Allman, Z. (2024a). Am I in Higher Education's third space? Who's here with me? SEDA. <https://thesedablog.wordpress.com/2024/08/21/am-i-in-higher-educations-third-space-whos-here-with-me/>
- Allman, Z. (2024b). Am I in Higher Education's third space? Who's here with me? SEDA Autumn Conference: *New Challenges for Educational Development – National and International Perspectives*, 28 November 2024. <https://www.seda.ac.uk/seda-events/seda-autumn-conference-2024/>

About the author

Professor Zoë Allman

De Montfort University

Associate Dean Education

[LinkedIn](#)

Collaborative autoethnography on third space identity

Puvaneswari P Arumugam and Mahen Jayawardena

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844956>

In many universities, traditional academics experience a clear sense of belonging due to the alignment between their professional identity and their discipline. However, third space professionals often struggle to find their place in the university setting.

Research has highlighted the unique position of third space practitioners, who occupy a liminal space (Bhabha, 2004) within the higher education landscape. These practitioners often feel “homeless” and have a vague sense of belonging. Their roles are described as liminal, binary/overlap, or borderless. Despite their expertise in teaching and learning, they are often perceived as “lesser” than discipline-based academics and professional staff.

This presentation explored research stemming from a collaborative auto-ethnographic study. In this study, three third space practitioners reflected on their professional identities, their roles in supporting academics, the assumptions they bring to their work, and their interactions with others. The presenting team also shared the challenges they faced in getting this research off the ground owing to the volatile nature of third space academic roles.

Reflection

It was heartening to hear feedback from others during the session about how the themes we uncovered in our research resonated with many of them. Many participants shared their own challenging experiences related to these themes.

Reference

Bhabha, H. (2004). *The location of culture* (2nd ed.), Routledge.

About the authors

Puvaneswari P Arumugam

Deakin University

Dr Puva P Arumugam is a Lecturer, Learning Futures, in the Faculty of Business and Law Learning Innovations team.

Mahen Jayawardena

La Trobe University

Advisor, Learning and Teaching Development

On the (in)visibility of librarians in third space literature

Heidi Butters-Stabb

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844973>

This piece was part of the Slowposium as a blog post, hence its more conversational tone. In it, I discuss my personal experience as an academic librarian encountering the idea of “third space(s)”.

When I was introduced to the concept of “third space” work in universities, I had an immediate reaction of “That’s me!” As an academic librarian I am a member of the university’s professional staff, but I teach workshops, set assessment, create learning objects, and collaborate with academics on elements of the curriculum. As a Law Librarian I have a set of Legal Research Competencies that I work to make sure students have learned by the end of their time in our law degrees. This seems to me to fall squarely within the definition of third space – summarised by Thorpe and Partridge (2024) as where “professional and academic staff cross into the others’ domain, or are engaged in activities that encompass both academic and professional activities”.

However, very little of the existing literature discusses librarians or librarianship in relation to third space. Thorpe and Partridge’s recent scoping review (2024), which looked at peer-reviewed articles from 2000 to 2022, brought up very few articles about library staff, and beyond one reference to “librarians in academic tenured roles” (Thorpe & Partridge, 2024, What is third space work? section) there was no identification within the discussion portion of the review of librarians or library staff as relevant to the discussion at all.

Another scoping review (Veles et al., 2023), referred to in Thorpe and Partridge’s work, covers a slightly shorter period of time between 2000 and 2020. This review looked only at professional staff, and identified far more articles about librarians, but the review was focused on professional identity and included “third space” as a possible descriptor of professional staff, rather than focusing on “third space” itself. Consequently, librarians were captured in this review as “professional staff” where they hadn’t been captured in a search focused on the third space. Fair or not, this seems to confirm my sense of librarians being forgotten in discussions of the third space despite clearly fitting the definition.

I have a few theories on why this is.

Perhaps part of the invisibility comes from the assumption that the third space is only for ways of operating that are new and disruptive and something that hasn’t been done before? After all, liaison librarians have been quietly doing their jobs for a long time now – Duane Wilson’s historical overview of the position dates the current form to the 1940s (2024, p. 1) – perhaps too quietly (as discussed by McCartin and Wright-Mair, 2022).

It’s also quite possible that there are some vocabulary conflicts involved. Libraries are part of a broader sector in which “third space” has an entirely different meaning as a physical space that is

not home (first space) or school or workplace (second space) (Wood, 2020). Libraries as physical spaces available to the public have a particular (although not always recognised) status as third places where it is not necessary to spend money, unlike shopping centres or movie theatres. Because of this vocabulary conflict it's actually quite difficult to search for "third space" and "library or librarian" as the majority of results will be about the broader meaning, rather than the university-specific one.

Finally, there may be geographical differences as to whether librarians are part of the third space at all. The discussion by McCartin and Wright-Mair covers some of the debate over librarians' status as "faculty" (academic) or professional in the USA (2022), but in Australia most academic librarians are classified as professional staff. (I work at an institution where academic status was removed from librarians in 2015.) Where librarians are academic staff, the question of being third space workers wouldn't arise – but in Australia, we decidedly are part of third space.

Why does any of this matter?

As an academic librarian who sees myself and the challenges of my role reflected in the definition of third space, the general lack of third space literature that mentions librarians seems like a gap. I'd like to see more discussions of the challenges of teaching into subjects run by others; of having teaching and even assessment responsibilities that are barely even acknowledged; and of how this has been a fact of academic librarianship for a long, long time.

References

- McCartin, L. F., & Wright-Mair, R. (2022). It's not personal, it's professional: Causes of academic librarian deference behavior. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(1), 102483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2021.102483>
- Thorpe, C., & Partridge, H. (2024). The Third Space in Higher Education: A scoping review. *Higher Education Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-024-00374-z>
- Veles, N., Graham, C., & Ovaska, C. (2023). University professional staff roles, identities, and spaces of interaction: Systematic review of literature published in 2000–2020. *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 7(2), 127–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322969.2023.2193826>
- Wilson, D. (2024). Constant change or constantly the same? A historical literature review of the subject librarian position. *College & Research Libraries*, 85(7), Article 7. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.85.7.1035>
- Wood, E. (2020, September 30). The rise of third place and open access amidst the pandemic, *Intersections*, American Library Association. Retrieved November 5, 2024, from <https://www.ala.org/advocacy/diversity/odlos-blog/rise-third-place>

About the author

Heidi Butters-Stabb

La Trobe University

The seven-year itch: Are directors' and learning designers' perceptions of the role of learning designers a marriage made in heaven?

Ruth Greenaway, Dom McGrath, and Christine Slade

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844983>

Seven years ago, Slade et al. (2018) explored learning design practices within Australian universities through the views of directors of learning and teaching centres and learning designers (LDs), revealing diverse entry pathways, professional development gaps, and evolving career aspirations. Since then, in the post-pandemic higher education landscape, the role and recognition of LDs have shifted significantly. This paper revisits these themes to examine the evolving perceptions, role complexity, and workforce management of LDs. Through a synthesis of recent empirical findings and sector developments, this study highlights ongoing challenges in role clarity, retention, and institutional positioning, proposing pathways to strengthen the LD profession amid higher education's digital transformation.

Introduction

Learning designers, encompassing educational, digital, and instructional designers, play an indispensable role in contemporary Australian universities. Our 2018 research identified varied career entry points, fragmented professional development offerings, and a lack of clear career trajectories from the perspectives of both LDs and Directors. These differences contributed to challenges in recruiting, managing, and retaining LD staff. Seven years later, the rapid rise of digital and hybrid learning driven by the COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the significance and complexity of LD roles while exposing persistent tensions around role definition and institutional status.

Role conceptualisation

LDs operate at the nexus of pedagogy, technology, and learner experience design. Educational designers often engage in strategic curriculum planning and capacity building; digital designers bring multimedia and user experience expertise; instructional designers focus on systematic content development and assessment alignment. This expanded nomenclature reflects an increasingly specialised and hybridised profession, yet variability in titles and functions can obscure role boundaries and complicate workforce management.

Challenges in recruitment and retention

Despite their critical contributions, LDs frequently encounter ambiguous role descriptions and limited institutional recognition, often situated outside traditional academic pathways. This

professional ambiguity hampers career development and retention, particularly as university structures sometimes categorise LDs as support rather than academic staff. Retaining LD talent is closely linked to institutional acknowledgment of LDs' pedagogical expertise, clear career pathways, and accessible professional development. Post-pandemic, there is progress with structured qualifications and enhanced dialogue between LDs and leadership, yet substantial work remains.

Conclusion

The relationship between Directors and LDs is nuanced and evolving rather than unequivocally harmonious. Our longitudinal perspective reveals that while the pandemic underscored the value of LDs, longstanding challenges around professional identity, role clarity, and workforce sustainability require sustained institutional commitment. Recognising the diversity within LD roles and fostering collaborative leadership discourse are critical to nurturing this profession. Future policy and practice must aim for integrated recruitment, role definition, and retention strategies to fully harness LDs' potential in transforming university learning and teaching.

Reference

Slade, C., McGrath, D., & Greenaway, R. (2018, July 3–5). Professionalisation in academic development: Exploring learning designer roles in a changing higher education sector [Conference paper]. *AdvanceHE Teaching & Learning Conference 2018: Teaching in the spotlight: Learning from global communities*, Birmingham, United Kingdom. Advance HE.

About the authors

Ruth Greenaway

Southern Cross University

Professor and Director, Centre for Teaching and Learning

Dom McGrath

University of Queensland

Senior Manager, Teaching and Learning, Institute for Teaching and Learning Innovation

Christine Slade

University of Queensland

Associate Professor, Institute for Teaching and Learning Innovation

Hard-pressed, but not crushed: A disposition of the heart in the space in-between

Rebecca Kan and Eliza Yeo Hui

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845000>

Provocation

As we locate ourselves in the space between professional identities, we feature ourselves as third space practitioners who are caught in the space in-between as academic developers in a higher arts education. The promises of this space arise when we probe deeper: artists have a disposition to creatively creolise boundaries between the centre and the periphery, “dividing the familiar and the foreign, the owned and the borrowed, the near and the far” (Sztabińska, 2014, p. 45). At the same time, school administrators behold dispositions to “establish a safe school environment, creating a trusting school culture, and setting high student academic expectations” (Pregot, 2016, p. 42).

With such a combustion of strengths, this dialogic exchange seeks to understand how dispositions emerge through the in-between. We question how we may develop the professional identity of third space practitioners, in order to be renewed day by day. As Routledge (1996, p. 406) surmises, this is “a place of invention and transformational encounters, a dynamic in-between space that is imbued with the traces, relays, ambivalences, ambiguities and contradictions, with the feelings and practices of both sites, to fashion something different, unexpected.”

This article explores the first-hand accounts of how two female colleagues, Rebecca Kan and Eliza Yeo (hereafter RK and EY) exchanged views about experiences in the space in-between.

About us

RK: I am a musician and musicologist by training, and educationalist by profession. Having breathed in performance and Baroque music research for the first twenty-six years of my life, I settled back in Singapore as a lecturer at a pioneering arts academy in Singapore. In 2010, I was appointed as Vice-Dean of Teaching and Learning to jumpstart academic policies and quality assurance processes at the academy. Socialised in the calling to spearhead pedagogy, research and partnerships to enhance the quality of higher arts education, I decided to embark on my second doctorate in professional education just before COVID-19 struck. In February 2023, I was conferred an EdD for my research on the in-between space of learning. It was at the beginning of the same year that there was a major re-organisation, where I was offered two appointments at the Teaching and Learning Centre (as Associate Dean of Curriculum and Pedagogy) and Faculty of Performing Arts (as Associate Dean of Degree Studies).

EY: I majored in social sciences in university, and thereafter, found myself in the HR space in a tertiary arts institution. I began my career in talent acquisition of administrative staff and

eventually transitioned to recruiting for the faculty and schools two years ago. I also hold the portfolio of Learning & Development; where exciting collaborations and partnership with the academic side comes in, together with strategic planning to upskill and move our unique position to a university college. Prior to the learning function, I helmed Employee Engagement, which allowed me to build rapport with my colleagues in an informal and light-hearted environment. From 30 July 2024, HR was re-named as People Excellence Office to develop and execute a comprehensive People Strategy in support of our academy's goals.

With such a combustion of profiles, both of us chose to use collaborative auto-ethnography to examine our own agency and identity in the space in-between. Collaborative auto-ethnography is a methodology that facilitates two or more individuals engage in dialogue to compare and contrast their lived experiences on a common phenomenon together (Norris et al., 2012). We conducted exchange in the month of October 2024, where we had five email exchanges and two 30-minute calls on Teams to exchange our views.

Our inquiry

In *L'évolution Créatrice*, the French philosopher Henri Bergson argued for in-betweens that focused on open and creative futures – between reason and intuition, between order and chaos, between predictability and unpredictability, between inclusion and exclusion, between rationality and creativity. Bergson (1907) described the indeterminacy and uncertainty of the in-between as “the space of becoming”: not just about movement towards a “preformed version of the real”, but a potential that threatens the identities that frame it. The in-between—as a space that celebrates an otherness to unfold in an autonomous and unpredictable fashion, as opposed to what is actual in body and material—forms the inspiration for kindling futures (Kan, 2023). As Routledge (1996, p. 406) surmises, this is “a place of invention and transformational encounters, a dynamic in-between space that is imbued with the traces, relays, ambivalences, ambiguities and contradictions, with the feelings and practices of both sites, to fashion something different, unexpected.”

“**Traces**” refer to influences and encounters of the past that continue to shape the present.

“**Relays**” are the processes of transmission to navigate between different individuals, faculties, or organisational structures. “**Ambivalences**” refer to the tensions that arise between institutional goals and personal agency, or balancing multiple, sometimes opposing, roles. “**Ambiguities**” represent the uncertainty, lack of clarity, or fluidity inherent in a space that defies traditional boundaries. “**Contradictions**” refer to the inherent conflicts that arise when working in a space that must reconcile opposing principles or practices that “fashion something different, unexpected” (Routledge, 1996, p. 406). In our exchange, we capture dispositions of the heart that emerge, as we navigate between polarities to seek new perspectives and critical insights as third space practitioners.

Against this backdrop, we invite you to reflect on these questions:

1. How do you perceive the “traces” of past experiences or institutional cultures shaping the current in-between space of your professional roles?
2. How do the “relays” of communication and decision-making function in this in-between space? Do they create opportunities for bridging gaps, or do they reinforce separations?
3. How do you navigate “ambivalence” inherent in your role, where you must balance institutional priorities with institutional/personal core values?

4. How do you respond when the expectations or outcomes of your work are unclear, and does that “ambiguity” offer potential for creative problem-solving?
5. Do you see “contradictions” as a necessary aspect of the in-between space that fuels growth and change, or as obstacles to be managed?

“Traces” of the past for the present

RK: As one of two constituent colleges of Singapore’s first arts university, our institution is caught between the binaries of vocation and profession. Having been established since 1938, we breathe in an academy that is deeply rooted with a rich legacy of educating some of the most important artistic pioneers, including 13 recipients of the Cultural Medallion—Singapore’s highest accolade for art practitioners—and 15 Young Artist Awards.

This 86-year-old academy prides itself on blending technical excellence with artistic specialisations in fine art, music, dance, theatre, design, fashion, and arts management. However, the shift towards thought leadership, contemporary artistic inquiry, and critical discourse raises the stakes in integrating tradition with innovation, urging us to reinterpret our legacy by uniting teaching, practice, and research.

As academic developers, we find ourselves uniquely positioned as intermediaries who bridge the divide between craft and scholarship, appreciating the deeply rooted influences that shape our institution’s culture: our rich heritage, the emphasis on foundational skills, and an unwavering commitment to providing transformative learning experiences across all age groups, from arts pre-school to lifelong learners at our Centre for Lifelong Learning.

EY: Yes, “traces” of our rich institutional culture has brought about an overall positive work culture of gratitude and award-winning people practices within the organisation. Our predecessors shaped environment and culture in cutting-edge recruitment practices, flexible work arrangements, grievance handling, age-friendly workplace and work-life harmony. Such initiatives steered our academy to be one of Singapore’s Best Employer for five consecutive years (from 2020 to 2024). Most recently, we were recognised at the Tripartite Alliance Award 2023: Work-Life Excellence & Leadership Award. We were also awarded the National Workplace Learning Organisation of Competence (Gold Award) in 2023, an award that has recognised us as an institution with robust and well-supported workplace learning culture that develop employees into self-driven learners, and provide them the building blocks to learn, grow and develop through continuous changes in the workplace landscape.

With a new value proposition and national agenda as the first arts university in Singapore (Chan, 2023), the firm standing of the People Excellence Office have open doors to collaboration and harmonious partnership between the administrative departments and faculty, as well as external stakeholders, such as our stable pool of industry, training partners and communities of practice. This has enabled synergies to be reaped amongst our Teaching and Learning Centre, Library, Research Division and People Excellence Office to enjoy and grow from its benefits of tapping into the respective expertise, knowledge, resources, and contacts.

“Relays” of communication and decision-making to bridge gaps

EY: With the trust that has been built over the years, the people team not only had access to core people strategic work, but also the privilege and opportunity to bridge gaps between

administration and academia. With a recent change in the national Tripartite Guidelines, we took the opportunity to align the institution's flexible work arrangement practices. As there were different practices within the institution, there were unhappiness on the ground. After listening to the needs of both administrative and academic staff, and in close consultation with Management and Union, we decided to land on the Work-From-Home policy from 2-days to 1-day per week. Due to the nature of work of the various functions within the institution, some would benefit from the revised policy, while others would not.

RK: At the Teaching and Learning Centre, we have made concerted efforts to enhance communication by actively involving administrative colleagues in academic meetings, consultations, and forums. Academic colleagues may sometimes overlook the crucial contributions of administrative staff in areas such as curriculum reviews, assessments, and the overall student learning experience. These staff members often serve as key intermediaries, managing complex interactions with adjunct lecturers and students, thus playing a pivotal role.

This collaborative approach proved particularly effective when we sought to improve participation in a new student learning experience survey. Administrative staff encountered challenges soliciting student participation due to the survey's lack of mobile accessibility, while academic colleagues expressed concerns over the potential implications of the survey results on staff evaluations.

By consulting with students, academics, and administrators, we collaboratively addressed these issues. We introduced a new survey system, developed policies to safeguard the confidentiality of results, enlisted Senior Management to encourage student participation, and implemented programmes to foster evidence-informed use of data. This not only built confidence among both academic and administrative staff but also bridged institutional divides. Ultimately, it was by demonstrating genuine care and attentiveness listening to their concerns that we were able to foster a culture of shared understanding, trust and collaboration.

“Ambivalences” as we navigate the space in-between

EY: The academy's core value of “care” has made it challenging for succession planning and talent renewal, which are essential to keep the organisation healthy, forward-looking and future ready.

But here is where I always remind myself of the purpose of my existence in the organisation. The organisational direction serves as a north star and there are key institutional priorities to achieve. Balance comes from reaching the priorities without compromising on the process and method on how it is achieved.

RK: Can you share an instance where you felt torn between conflicting professional identities or goals in this in-between space? how did you address that ambivalence?

EY: As a people strategist, I am aware that by releasing a particular employee through retirement was necessary for the team and for talent renewal within the organisation. However, the tension came as I was reminded that as a people partner, I am to uphold the organisation's core value of “care” at the same time. While I empathise with this colleague's situation, the release of this staff was an essential move towards achieving the institutional priorities in the longer run. In my capacity, I did what was necessary, and at the same time, handled the colleague, managed the situation and the exit process with dignity, respect, appreciation and care, to the best of my ability.

RK: I like to think of these tensions as a “pause” moment, what I love to call in music a “fermata”. As Fels and Belliveau (2008, p. 36) describe, these indeterminate pauses create an “provides a way to focus on the learning that emerges.” For me, learning truly takes place when there is both change and challenge. While decisions around tenure and retirement extend beyond my remit at the Teaching and Learning Centre, I find it gratifying to see colleagues depart with a wealth of transferable and transformative skill-sets, developed through the professional development workshops, dialogues and conversations that were had organised during their engagement as lecturers.

EY: Being in an established institution with a positive (and almost feels-like-family) culture, some may become complacent in their roles, especially if they do not rotate to take on other portfolios. Mindsets shifts may be a challenge and some eventually fall behind in terms of skillsets and artistic/professional practice. It is sometimes challenging to manage, but with strong support from leadership, effective change management, communication this could be managed with a good heart and in good spirit. We preach and advocate lifelong learning; where we encourage and sponsor training during office hours, provide postgraduate sponsorship to close the skills and industry gap, as much as we could. We hope to instil lifelong learning and walk-the-talk as an education institution, for our faculty and administrative colleagues alike. Our hope is that colleagues will always be hungry for knowledge and learning.

“Ambiguities” that conjure dispositions of the heart

RK: Ambiguity is the essence of artistic practice and perhaps even a defining characteristic of the arts (Kan, forthcoming). As Shulman (2012, p. 80) reminds us, “to call something ambiguous is not to claim that it is trivial or vacuous. On the contrary, it carries multiple meanings...” I think it’s important to suspend judgment, allow time for perplexity or doubt, and remain open to alternative interpretations. I like to think of such liminal pockets as what Manning and Massumi (2014) coined “enabling constraints,” which enhance creativity!

EY: Communication is key; if there is ambiguity, seek clarity. Should the expectations be open, it presents an opportunity for me to propose new ideas or approaches, and potentially explore uncharted territories as well.

RK: Yes! The musician disposition in me trains me to listen. There is both a physical and emotional aspect to listening, what Chinese call attentive listening or “ting”!

Listening with your whole heart, as being attuned to feelings, are so relevant in care-centric approaches!

I am also reminded by Gillies (2012) that the secrets of Finnish who are born young to greatness lie in their approach to the music: humility over narcissism!

EY: That makes me think of the time I had to show care and kindness in a professional setting, during a difficult conversation with a colleague. Some concerns and unhappiness were raised, and I had to facilitate the conversation and trust the process to be fair, and I had to show kindness at the same time. Space was given for this colleague to raise grievances at the meeting and thereafter, through our grievance handling avenue. At times like this, I appreciate the para-counselling course that equipped me to actively listen to others, probe deeper and facilitate challenging conversations, even if there are no answers sometimes.

RK: I completely resonate with how such dispositions can better develop our academy to be better prepared to deal with complexity and ambiguity in the today's uncertain world. As Klein (2008) reminds us, if we are to develop art teachers who are integrated, then greater attention needs to be paid to developing dispositions that reflect the inner life.

“Contradictions” as inherent conflicts that fuel growth and change

RK: It's definitely necessary to search for contradictions – these inherent tensions cultivate a deeper sensitivity to what Evans-Palmer (2017) calls “affective inclinations”.

In my work, two hearts beat as one. As a musicologist and educationalist, both identities shape my experience and approach. Embracing my role as a third space practitioner at the Teaching and Learning Centre allows me to appreciate how academic development initiatives in technology-enhanced learning, innovative pedagogies, assessment standards, and a shared core curriculum can enhance teaching and learning across all faculties.

However, as I shift to my role as a Senior lecturer in the School of Music, I recognise that there are other pressing and competing demands specific to the discipline, students, staff and the creative industry that may take precedence over educational innovations. For instance, there are nuances to be considered in how specialised and unique every discipline can be with respect to the use of technologies, how personalised pedagogies can be the individual music studio, how assessment

procedures can differ in a conservatoire-style curriculum, and how a common curriculum may not always be relevant to the drive towards hyper-specialisations in music studies.

When we engage with these contradictions, we create a space that acts as a catalyst for innovation.

EY: What does it mean in concrete terms?

RK: In practical terms, it means that I can creatively adapt and introduce pedagogies peculiar to visual arts and design to the performing arts. For instance, we've initiated creative pedagogies of transition, pedagogies of creative uncertainty, and pedagogies of designerly formation across disciplines and beyond the arts. On reflection, my third space positionality has allowed for the emergence of hybrid pedagogies, opening up new avenues for inter-disciplinarity.

EY: I actually see such tensions as a necessary aspect of growth and change. Contradictions challenge and balance academic ideals and administrative realities, as we must meet in a common ground. As the academy assumes the hood of a University, teaching staff are required to have research background and preferably a PhD. Our unique position in higher arts education would require staff to be competent in their professional artistic practice, professional knowledge in arts education, pedagogical content knowledge, and research inquiry. Unless a niche interest and trajectory, it is often challenging to find a candidate who ticks all of our boxes. Nonetheless, without the academic ideals, the needles of the administrative realities will not move and hence grow and change.

Welcoming your views

This Slowposium represents our first steps at developing a more critical reflexive dialogue to probe deep into dispositions of the heart, beyond the usual mode of sharing through conference and publication. We hope to have conveyed how the in-between space has fostered gratitude, a willingness to listen, humility, open-mindedness and the courage to create, in order to be renewed day by day. However, it will be important to consider what these dispositions look like in other contexts.

We're keen to hear from your practice, and challenges that you've been encountering.

References

- Bergson, H. (1907 | 1959). *L'évolution créatrice* [Creative evolution]. Presses Universitaires de France, Paris.
- Chan, C. S. (2023). *Speech at UAS Symposium*. Available online: <https://www.moe.gov.sg/news/speeches/20230510-speech-by-minister-chan-chun-sing-at-the-university-of-the-arts-singapore-arts-symposium>
- Evans-Palmer, T. (2016). Building dispositions and self-efficacy in preservice art teachers. *National Art Education Association Studies in Art Education: A Journal of Issues and Research*, 57(3), 265–78.
- Fels, L., & Belliveau, G. A. (2008). *Exploring curriculum: Performative inquiry, role drama, and learning*. Pacific Educational Press.
- Gillies, M. (2012). Conducting material. *Times Higher Education*, (2056), 31.

- Kan, R. Y. P. (2023). Through the space in-between (with illustrations by Emily Seck). In *Artbook 2108. Tomorrow's Testament*. Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts.
- Kan, R. Y. P. (forthcoming). Chapter 15: Codetta: Pedagogies of evocative ambiguity. In C. S. G. Khoo & R. Kan (Eds.), *Signature pedagogies for professions in arts and design*. Springer.
- Klein, S. R. (2008). The use of dispositions in preservice art teacher evaluation. *Studies in Art Education*, 49(4), 375–380.
- Manning, E., & Massumi, B. (2014). *Thought in the act: Passages in the ecology of experience*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Norris, J., Sawyer, R. D., & Lund, L. (2012). *Duoethnography: Dialogic methods for social, health, and educational research*. Left Coast Press.
- Pregot, M. (2016). Identifying the administrative dispositions most preferred by urban school leaders and school leadership candidates. *Leadership and Research in Education: The Journal of the Ohio Council of Professors of Educational Administration (OCPEA)*, 3(1), 34–51.
- Routledge, P. (1996). The Third Space as critical engagement. *Antipode*, 28, 399–419.
- Shulman, L. S. (2012). The challenges and opportunities for liberal education in a faith-based university. In E. Davis (Ed.), *A higher education: Baylor and the vocation of a Christian university* (pp. 75–87). Baylor University Press.
- Sztabińska, P. (2014). Contemporary artist and the notion of center and periphery art inquiry. *Recherches sur les arts*, xvi, 45–56.

About the authors

Rebecca Kan

Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts, University of the Arts Singapore

ypkan@nafa.edu.sg

Associate Dean (Curriculum & Pedagogy), Teaching and Learning Centre

Associate Dean (Degree Studies), Faculty of Performing Arts

Eliza Yeo Hui

Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts, University of the Arts Singapore

Assistant Manager, People Excellence Office

(De)constructing the professional identities of third space practitioners through zine making

Kate Molloy

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845014>

This activity provided participants with a medium for constructing, and deconstructing, their professional identity through zine making. Participants were encouraged to reflect on their professional identity within the third space through a proposed lens of academic counterculture – a space where identities intersect, and experiences and titles blur beyond recognition. The diverse communities traditionally represented in zines provided a valuable construct for reflection on professional identity in the third space. The activity leveraged zines as a medium to promote community-building and connection – a platform to construct meaning and to connect those working, or existing, in often lonely spaces.

Provocation

Participants worked through a short, interactive microlesson to explore zines through counterculture movements, the zine-making process, and provocations for utilising zine-making to construct and reflect on professional identity in the third space. Padlets were included in the microlesson to share artefacts and reflections, with examples curated from colleagues who have previously worked through the materials. The activity was designed to be both low and high touch, depending on the level of engagement. Participants could complete it in one to two hours. The session was built upon previously tested methodologies and pedagogies from a book chapter and workshop (Molloy & Thomson, 2023, 2024).

Reflection

As a third space practitioner and emerging researcher, testing this activity in a “safe space” like the 3SS was a unique opportunity. While I regularly leverage creative methods in practice, I hope to use zine-making workshops to collect data as a creative method further along in my PhD research. It was useful to avail of this space and community to test the process early on and carefully consider how participants might perceive my third space as academic counterculture provocation. Upon reflection, the activity should be less structured and include ample opportunity for participants to identify their own themes or lenses with which to construct professional identity. A significant takeaway was that all participants chose to create a digital zine as opposed to scanning a handmade artefact when provided with both options, and it will be worthwhile to pursue the “why” in future sessions.

References

- Molloy, K., & Thomson, C. (2023). Humanising learning design with digital pragmatism. In L. Czerniewicz & C. Cronin (Eds.), *Higher education for good* (pp. 397–420). Open Book Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.11647/obp.0363.17>
- Molloy, K., & Thomson, C. (2024). Humanising learning design with digital pragmatism. OER24 Conference. Association for Learning Technology. <https://blokks.co/schedules/oer24/#/2024-03-28/qmv8976e62ga/workshop-122-humanising-learning-design-with-digital-pragmatism>

About the author

Kate Molloy

Dublin City University

Instructional Designer. PhD student, School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies

<https://kate-molloy.net/about/>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3544-3170>

Standing out in the third space

Donna Murray

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845026>

TL;DR – If you don't want to read it all, please just go to the end – I'm asking us all to share something that we feel expresses our thoughts about third-space roles.

In my role as Head of Taught Students in the Institute for Academic Development, at The University of Edinburgh, I lead a team which provides support to ~45,000 UG and PGT students. This is very much a third-space role: I have to understand how students learn; how people teach; work on strategic initiatives; represent the student voice in decision making; and work across three Colleges and 21 Schools. In other words, it's a messy, complicated role. If I leave, I'm not sure how the University would work out what is required to replace me – and I suspect that is true of many third-space roles.

I no longer have as much direct student contact as I used to have, leading this area takes my time away from that. However, I do present at our Offer Holder events, and Pre-arrival/Welcome Week events. These are designed to give information, and offer time for students (and their parents/supporters) to ask questions. My main aim though is to be a welcoming presence, and to show that asking for support is not only normal, it is something that the happiest and most successful students feel able to do. As part of this I am often talking to very large groups, who may be hearing from lots of other support services or academic leads. Sometimes I am one of 15 presentations, and I am not vain enough to expect that the audience will all just remember what I say. I have taken to finishing my presentations with quotes, which are intended to either raise a laugh or make people think. My hope is that by doing something unexpected at the end, a memory of the support offered by my team may linger.

I have a range of quotations which I use. When talking to parents and supporters, I will often finish with:

"I may not have gone where I intended to go, but I think I have ended up where I needed to be" – Douglas Adams, The Long Dark Tea-time of the Soul

– which allows me to talk about how the journey belongs to the student, and it may end up not being what parents/supporters want or expect, but that's ok.

When talking to students I may end with:

"Do, or do not. There is no try" – Yoda, The Empire Strikes Back

– which allows me to tell students that I do want them to work hard, I do not want them to make studying the only thing they do, and I do want them to remember that my team is there to help them achieve their potential.

If I take this to the arena of third-space professionals, what quote might I use to help us all to express what it means to us?

I have used a Maya Angelou quote before:

“Success is liking yourself, liking what you do, and liking how you do it.” Maya Angelou

I use this quote with the caveat that Maya Angelou is one of the most mis-attributed authors of the twentieth century. However, I feel it explores one of the issues we face. How can we be confident about the value of our roles, and our skills? Universities can be a very hierarchical environment, and those hierarchies may have been established over a long period of time so seem insurmountable. In addition, our contribution may be harder to see, academic colleagues can point to their lectures, their research, the number of students they supervise because all of these are valued in the university environment. Yet, if a student cannot find resources in the Library, or cannot use the online learning environment, or isn't confident about revising for exams, they may have no capacity for their academic work. We cannot easily identify these more intangible things (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Identification

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/mikol/>"(System) FLEXIBILITY = COMPLEXITY" (CC BY-SA 2.0) by Mikol

I provided these instructions for the Slowposium participants, asking them to add thoughts, comments, quotes, pictures, sound clips etc., either anonymously or with name and institution provided.

I would like to ask people to think about how, or in what way, they would describe third-space roles, or the impact of these roles. It may be via a quote as I do; or a (very) short description; or an image, or a sound, or a metaphor whatever you want. I will then collate these, and try to draw out common themes, and highlight things which seem unique to circumstances, and write it up as a blog for the TELedvisors network. I'd hope that might kick off a longer discussion about our roles – if we can come up with some thoughts it could function a starting point for dialogue outside our sphere?

Thank you for your input, and I look forward to seeing what our community thinks.

The Slowposium ends on 30 November so that will be our deadline, and in honour of that allow me to finish with another quote:

“I love deadlines. I like the whooshing sound they make as they fly by.”

— Douglas Adams, *The Salmon of Doubt: Hitchhiking the Galaxy One Last Time*

Reflections after the Slowposium

One of the lovely things about the Slowposium was the opportunity to interact over a longer period of time than in a standard conference. There were really interesting contributions, from which I took away two themes.

Firstly the concept of transformation – both of us as individuals, but also the positive impact we have upon others, and our work environments. Articulating this can be challenging, and often it ends up with discussions on what our “outputs” are. This can reduce our work to what can be measured.

Secondly, the theme of working together was very important. This could be working as individuals within the third space, or bringing together groups and acting as a bridge, connecting people who might otherwise be in academic silos.

Both these themes relate to the issue of identity and visibility. More than a decade after Whitchurch (2013) gave us the language of “third space” we are still discussing how to explain our work, and often to justify it. Third space professionals are generally incredibly collegial and actively seek out opportunities to work in collaboration with others from across the sector. That is a strength, but one which is not always valued in Higher Education: for me, the question is how to make our way of working the gold standard in academic life.

Reference

Whitchurch, C. (2013). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of third space professionals*. Routledge.

About the author

Donna Murray

The University of Edinburgh

Dr Murray is Head of Taught Student Development and Head of Masters provision in the Institute for Academic Development.

Staff profile <https://institute-academic-development.ed.ac.uk/about-us/staff/profiles/donna-murray>

Knowing, doing and showing

A framework for evidencing learning design practice

Sue Sharpe, Jenny Boreland, and Tanya Henry

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845035>

Some of the challenges facing third space practitioners include role clarity, professional identity, having a voice, demonstrating value, establishing legitimacy and evidencing expertise. This session focused on the challenge for third space professionals in demonstrating value and evidencing expertise, particularly practitioners in learning design and related roles, and proposed a framework to meet this challenge (Boreland, Henry, & Sharpe, 2025a).

Figure 1: *The Learning Design Evidence Framework*

The framework (Figure 1; Boreland, Henry, & Sharpe, 2025b) aims to guide collection and use of evidence demonstrating impact and efficacy, increasing visibility, justifying funding, supporting career progression and identifying development needs. It is a “fit for purpose” redesign of similar approaches used by academic staff for promotion. The framework was presented for discussion and feedback and provided participants with an opportunity to apply the framework to their own contexts and to plan future actions.

References

- Boreland, J., Henry, T., & Sharpe, S. (2025a). Knowing, doing and showing: a framework for evidencing education and learning designers’ practice in higher education, *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* (33). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1210>
- Boreland, J., Henry, T., & Sharpe, S. (2025b). *The Learning Design Evidence Framework* [Figure]. Figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.29993107.v1>

About the authors

Sue Sharpe

Deakin University

Lecturer, Artificial Intelligence and Inclusive Education. Sue leads academic development initiatives that advance inclusion, addressing emerging challenges in higher education including generative AI and assessment reform.

Jenny Boreland

Queensland University of Technology

Jenny manages learning designers, fostering excellence in educational designs to deliver impactful, positive outcomes for all learners.

Tanya Henry

The University of Queensland

Tanya provides leadership and mentorship to a team of faculty-based Learning Designers who are driving assessment transformation across UQ.

Make your pitch: let's solve the question of third space titles

Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845053>

Inconsistent titles for third space roles have plagued us for decades (Geis & Klaassen, 1972). While it may seem trivial whether we are called learning designer, education designer, instructional designer, eLearning advisor, or education technologist, the variability in these titles make it harder to communicate about these roles and ensure that educators who need help are able to find it easily from the right people.

What if everyone somehow agreed on a single term for each of our various roles? (Assuming that we maintain broad role types of learning designer, educational technologist, academic developer and the array of other third space positions)

For example: there are no more educational designers or instructional designers – only learning designers

The same for education or learning or whatever technologist. Somehow we settle on – educational technologist (for example).

The same for academic/faculty/education developer.

Would this make life easier? Why?

What would you prefer your title to be?

In this discussion activity, I encouraged participants to make a pitch for your preferred title and make a case for why we should adopt their preferred title.

Will it solve anything? Will it change anything? Who knows. At least we can have some fun with it.

Well, since I started this whole thing I guess it is only fair for me to provide the first offering.

EdAdvisor – a collective term for people working in the tertiary education third space to enable better learning and teaching by supporting educators specifically. EdAdvisors include learning designers, educational technologists, and academic developers (and all of the many, many variations of these titles).

EdAdvisor is a portmanteau of Educator and Advisor. This acknowledges the fact that EdAdvisors (or EdAd for short) are frequently educators in their own right, as well as recognising that they advise the educators they work with. *Advise* is an important part of this name, as it recognises expertise, and elevates EdAdvisors beyond “just support” staff. Providing support is still a key part of what EdAds do, but there can be an implication of a less equal relationship when it is part of the title.

Some may notice the similarity of EdAdvisor to Edvisor or TELedvisor(s). Given that I was part of the discussion where we first coined Edvisor, this is no coincidence. Now that the TELedvisors Network has been around for close to eight years, this term has some degree of “brand recognition” in the sector. I am proud to be a TELedvisor but I think EdAdvisor is clearer in communicating what these people do. Over the years, I have seen this (and edvisor) misspelled frequently and also mispronounced. It doesn’t roll off the tongue. (There are no plans to change TELedvisors branding to EdAdvisors – currently.)

The term EdAdvisor does not represent everyone in the third space, just a sub-group who share a common purpose and commonly work together. It encourages collaboration and shared understanding, and makes it easier to collectively describe us. Please consider using the term EdAdvisor in the future. Thank you.

Reflection

The identity question has vexed us in the third space for more than fifty years. I suspect that our two greatest barriers to consistency are the desire to have ownership of role titles, which is understandable but not always practical, and the tendency in the higher education sector to demand the perfect over the good. In the case of the latter, any title where a small exception might be found, even if only relevant to 1 in 1000 cases, is often automatically dismissed as unsuitable. Part of this process is going to have to involve acceptance that some people won’t get their personal preference in exchange for agreeing on titles which have the widest possible understanding and acceptance.

References

- Geis, G., & Klaassen, J. (1972). It’s a word, It’s a name, It’s ... an Educational Technologist. *Educational Technology*, 12(12), 20–22.
- Mitchell, K., Simpson, C., & Adachi, C. (2017). What’s in a name? The ambiguity and complexity of technology enhanced learning roles. In H. Partridge, K. Davis, & J. Thomas (Eds.), *Me, Us, IT! Proceedings ASCILITE2017: 34th International Conference of Innovation, Practice and Research in the use of Educational Technologies in Tertiary Education* (p. 449), ASCILITE. <http://2017conference.ascilite.org/program/whats-in-a-name-the-ambiguity-and-complexity-of-technology-enhanced-learning-roles/>

About the author

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

What does the third space look like?

Wendy Taleo

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845059>

Dynamic and bold, creating movement
 skills embedded in our skin
 technology both binding and dividing
 staring into a vortex
 side by side
 a kaleidoscope
 tilted towards each other, reflecting
 is it an implosion, illusion,
 or creating new shorelines?
 embedded in historical structures
 our work writes history
 grounded and creating space.

Poetry written by Wendy Taleo in response to the images created

The following text from the Third Space Symposium was used as a prompt for three different Artificial Intelligence (AI) image generators. I used Lunapic.com to animate images and incorporated asemic writing as an antidote to the artificial intelligence and digital content. I recorded the sound of my pen scraping across the paper as I created the asemic writing and this forms that soundtrack for the video. The asemic writing was completed while I viewed the images and is a non-verbal way to respond to the created images.

The term “third space” describes people working across and between the boundaries of traditional academic and professional roles in tertiary education.

Who works in the third space?

Third space practitioners include learning designers, educational technologists, academic developers and many other people in roles with similar titles.

Other people in the third space include workers in tertiary education who are developing the academic and language skills of students, research assistants and technicians, library staff and a wide array of other workers straddling these worlds.

While these roles have existed for more than 70 years, in many different forms, their value to their organisation and to the sector is often misunderstood, reducing these workers’ ability to effect meaningful change. Career progression, contracts and working conditions can be unstable or limited.

The skills and knowledge that Third Space practitioners in professional roles bring may be questioned, and they are often blocked from contributing to research in their fields of expertise.

The Third Space Symposium and Slowposium aims to shine a light on the valuable contributions that third space practitioners make, examine the ways that we work together and consolidate practical actions to raise our impact and working conditions in tertiary education.

Short prompt

The term “third space” describes people working across and between the boundaries of traditional academic and professional roles in tertiary education.

Create an image that represents the third space in this context. Image should be high definition, intense colour and modern design.

Create an image that represents the third space in this context. Image should be high definition, intense colour and modern design.

In addition to the images, I intersperse asemic writing and capture the soundtrack which is fast becoming unknown, the sound of the pen on paper. This is imparting somatic intelligence as “a different kind of knowing, one that is embodied, temporal, and resistant to extraction” (Semsik, A. 2025). My impression from the public comments left on the YouTube short is that people react to different parts of the video, images, poetry, sound and the asemic writing. My reflection on this exercise is that this form of expression is useful for me. I have used this piece as a conversation starter over the last year and I find myself returning to it for both inspiration and to observe if anything has moved or changed in my thinking.

Reflection, 2025

In addition to the images, I intersperse asemic writing and capture the sound track which is fast becoming unknown, the sound of the pen on paper. This is imparting somatic intelligence as “a different kind of knowing, one that is embodied, temporal, and resistant to extraction” (Semsik, A. 2025). My reflection on this exercise is that this form of expression is useful for me. I have used this piece as a conversation starter over the last year and I find myself returning to it for both inspiration and to observe if anything has moved or changed in my thinking.

References

Simsek, A. (2025). Knowing Futures: CLA, Heidegger, and Somatic Intelligence in the Age of AI. *Journal of Futures Studies*. <https://jfsdigital.org/knowing-futures-cla-heidegger-and-somatic-intelligence-in-the-age-of-ai/>

Taleo, W. (2024). What does the Third Space look like? YouTube. https://youtube.com/shorts/39Y-ZNwNhQg?si=OqtuPzDIYLTh0z_g

About the author

Wendy Taleo

Flinders University

Wendy is a convener of the TELedvisors network and an enthusiastic education designer, technologist and poet.

Empowering professional identity ... through third space collaboration

Claire Toogood and Katy Hale

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845065>

During the 3SS, we shared a pre-publication copy of our paper on “Empowering professional identity and positive outcomes through third space collaboration: A subject lecturer and EAP practitioner case study”. This was subsequently published by the *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* in their special edition on third space in HE in January 2025.

We both are, or have been, third space practitioners in various roles in UK HE institutions and related organisations. As such, we enjoyed the opportunity to share our work with an interested audience and engaged in the discussion and reflection on the Slowposium Forum both on our own paper, and in relation to the work of others. As Katy posted on the Slowposium Forum, in response to one comment we received “... when Claire and I started to collaborate, this was definitely what we were trying to do. We were trying to bridge a gap for students”. We appreciated the opportunity to be part of a community event focusing on exactly that, better experiences and outcomes for students and graduates, through an ambitious, collaborative and rich third space.

Reference

Toogood, C., & Hale, K. (2025). Empowering professional identity and positive outcomes through Third Space collaboration: A subject lecturer and EAP practitioner case study. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education, special issue* (33).
<https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1196>

About the authors

Claire Toogood

Birmingham Newman University and Harper Adams University

Association of Graduate Careers Advisory Services

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9893-087X>

[LinkedIn](#)

Katy Hale

Aston University

Teaching Fellow – Library and Learning Services

Framework for academic developers

Kate Tregloan and Naima Iftikhar

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845078>

We invited participants to join us to explore a framework that describes academic development (AD) activities across multiple third space spectra, and to map their own projects in these spaces. Participants tested and explored the framework, considering how to use it in their own projects for planning, evaluation and impact.

The University of Melbourne Built Environments Learning and Teaching (BEL+T) Group is a faculty AD group. BEL+T operates in three forms: as a design studio, as a consultancy, and as a research group. These approaches cross three spectra in our framework: modes of operation (Academic and Professional); values and goals (Staff and Institutional); and planned outcomes and impact (Research and Teaching). This interactive workshop explored these spectra through mapping of participants' experiences, followed by reflection and discussion of the commonalities and differences uncovered through this activity.

About the authors

Kate Tregloan

The University of Melbourne

Dr Tregloan is Associate Professor in Higher Education at the Centre for the Study of Higher Education.

Naima Iftikhar

Western Sydney University

Dr Iftikhar is Lecturer in Learning and Teaching and Academic Lead in Professional Learning in the Office of the PVC Learning and Teaching.

Practice

The things we do working in the third space

Reclaiming the resources we make

Dana Bui

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845098>

Abstract

As educational designers, we dedicate countless hours to creating resources, tipsheets, and digital assets with the intent of building capability in our institutions. Yet, the moment we step away from that institution, our ideas and everything we've created are left behind. Frustrated by this disconnect, I developed a process for converting, revising, updating and building on these resources into a space that is mine. This paper unpacks the motivations and methods behind the creation of my blog, [The Educational Designer](#). It details a refusal to let institutional norms define my professional voice, which led to a liberated approach to evolving my practice on my own terms. I invite others to use this work as a starting point to reimagine their experience, skills, and identity as distinctly individual and valuable.

Reclaiming the
resources we make

Dana Bui | Educational Designer

Third space challenges

The position occupied by educational designers, often referred to as the third space, encompasses peripheral yet vital roles in educational development. This space is frequently characterised by several challenges that directly inform our motivations and actions. Among these are:

The challenges of third spaces

- Lack of recognition
- Instability
- Feeling like a cog in a wheel
- Lack of agency
- Lack of voice

Lack of professional recognition

Educational designers regularly support academics in the ideation and implementation of new initiatives, contributing to the elevation of educational standards. However, their contributions remain largely unacknowledged in subsequent awards, publications or presentations by academic staff.

Workforce instability

Despite repeatedly being described in leadership discussions as “essential”, designers are often offered short-term contracts and limited tenure, with roles adjunct to the lifecycle of projects or initiatives and their perceived completion.

Putting out fires

Tenured staff often experience persistent workload demand, reacting to institutional changes such as the shift to remote teaching, alterations in assessment practices, or the adoption of generative AI tools. This often occurs without recognition of our achievements or time to pause, reflect, and evaluate, before the next initiative has been dictated.

Limited agency and voice

Institutional change invariably occurs with little or superficial consultation, and educational designers are often engaged as facilitators of the new initiative, policy or technology, regardless of their professional perspectives. Advocacy for quality education may be stifled by authoritative leadership and rushed initiatives, with voices frequently overlooked.

Reflection and Motivations

In 2023, with ten years of experience as an educational designer, I recognised a need to assert greater agency over my professional outputs. In consideration of the issues above, my goals emerged:

Reflecting on 10 years of educational design

- I needed to:
- showcase my skills
 - retain my own IP
 - establish my own voice

Showcasing capabilities

I sought to establish a public platform that would provide tangible evidence of my skills and expertise. This needed to be separated from my workplace to establish my individual identity.

What is your voice?

Your voice is the freedom to be able to express yourself in a way that is uniquely you, with all your diverse perspectives, representing all your skills, experience and knowledge.

Retaining intellectual property

While institutions retain legal ownership of the published resources we have produced, the underlying concepts and ideas remain ours. Redeveloping these ideas into new formats allowed me to retain ownership over my ideas.

Establishing an independent professional voice

Institutional writing conventions, such as the “Monash tone of voice”, restrict authentic expression. I required a platform where nuance, critique, and personal identity could be freely expressed, distinct from institutional constraints. I needed a way to be able to say, “I’m living in an episode of Utopia, and I’m a little bit dead inside”. This is not the Monash tone of voice.

So, what did I do?

Showcase my skills Retain my own IP Establish my own voice

“The Educational Designer”

Defining professional voice

Professional voice in this context extends beyond the functional content of communications. It represents the synthesis of experience, knowledge, identity, and communicative autonomy. Although institutions may support diverse perspectives, formal etiquette and tone requirements limit such freedom. My process focused on articulating my educational philosophy in a manner representative of my distinct identity.

Strategies for redeveloping resources

In the interest of bringing others along on the journey, I am sharing the various strategies that I have used to redevelop my work. This section presents practical strategies for reclaiming your work, extending its reach, and expressing your unique professional voice more fully.

1. Use Generative AI to revise resources

Expanding on ideas

If you have “quick tips” resources, give these ideas to AI to see how it expands on the topic.

Prompt: You are an education expert writing a blog post on [topic]. Elaborate on these ideas, explain why they are important, and give examples. Here are the ideas: [1], [2], [3].

Rewriting text

Generative AI makes deliberate attempts to create a homogenous voice, which is in opposition to my intention to establish my unique voice. If the original writing is already well-formed, this helps retain the ideas and change the phrasing.

Prompt: Rewrite the following text, changing the sentence structure, word choice, and overall flow while preserving the core meaning and key information. Aim for a version that is noticeably different from the original in terms of phrasing and organisation but conveys the same essential ideas. Here is the text [text].

New ideas

If you’re working on something new, write your ideas down first, then review the literature, and then prompt AI. This helps to have more confidence in your own work. This means that AI can help make the process more comprehensive, rather than outsourcing the critical components to AI.

Prompts:

I’m working on a blog post on [topic]. Can you find any gaps in research or unique angles?

I’m working on a blog post on [topic]. Can you suggest some potential questions people may want answered on this topic?

I have an idea for a blog post on [topic] but haven’t formed it well. Ask me questions to help me form my ideas more clearly. Here is my idea: [idea].

2. Find old, outdated, or no longer used resources

Outdated or archived resources can be revisited and updated in light of contemporary educational innovations (I’m looking at you, Generative AI). This can give you an opportunity to review the concept, ensuring it is in line with the current literature. This strategy can be difficult without a

How did I do it?

- Developed strategies.
- Added some shiny new ideas.

What strategies did I use to redevelop the resources?

1. Use AI to rewrite my resources
2. Find old, outdated, or no longer used resources
3. Change the format
4. Change the examples
5. Use voice to text
6. Track everything
7. Write in my own time

great filing system, but go back through old projects and initiatives and find whatever resources you created that were of an advisory or informative nature. Don't forget the shared/group folders and your personal folders (obviously, only searching for the resources you developed yourself).

3. *Change the format*

When redeveloping something currently in use, change the format to ensure it's sufficiently different from the original. Here are some formats I commonly use:

Commonly asked questions from educators with a response, reasoning and advice.

- Example: Student norms: Why can't they just do it the way I want them to?

Strategies for a [common topic] I'm asked for support with.

- Example: How to improve group work processes for equitable, engaging, and productive student collaboration

Two/three strategies for [topic].

- Example: Two long-term strategies to create inclusive learning environments

[Verbing] [topic] with steps and advice.

- Example: Step-by-step: Building impactful branching scenarios

Simplifying [topic] by using less institutional jargon

- Example: Demystifying learning outcomes: What they are and how to write them

4. *Change the examples*

Rather than limit examples to your primary disciplinary context, give AI your discipline-specific example and ask AI to create an equivalent example in another discipline. AI will provide a broad example, and you'll need to add specificity. Get in touch with other third spacers, ask them what they might use in their disciplines. This broadens the scope and applicability of the redeveloped resources and serves as a way of expanding your knowledge, experience, and connection base.

5. *Use voice to text*

 Voice typing When there is significant commonality in advice given during consultations, I capture this via voice-to-text tools during routine activities, providing both new ideas for blog posts and a feedback database. You can use voice typing on Google Docs, or use the "mic" button on your keyboard when you're on your phone. Have a cloud-based notebook or document system on the go, and take a few minutes after each meeting to verbalise the advice you've just given. If you can remember in the moment, turn it on during Zoom meetings when you're speaking to capture the advice you give. Just make sure you're only capturing your words, not the words of others.

6. *Track everything*

Use a systematic, procedural approach and capture the redevelopment in a spreadsheet to prevent redundancy across posts and resources. Capturing this in a spreadsheet ensures a more

comprehensive coverage, including links to the existing content, new content, and notes on what parts have been captured.

7. *Write in your own time*

Perhaps most importantly, this work must be conducted outside of work hours. This ensures there is no conflict of interest and the IP remains your own. This strategy pairs well with voice typing and your phone's virtual assistant (Siri, etc). Often the best ideas come while driving, walking or doing chores. Verbalising the idea means they don't get lost and you don't have to stop and write anything down because you can speak it to capture it (caveat: obviously, pay attention while driving).

Outcomes and significance

This approach gave me several outcomes addressing the challenges outlined above. The content published on my blog remains my IP, offering personal recognition for years of development of knowledge, skills and experience as an educational designer. The independent authorship gives me agency, enabling freedom in topic selection and promoting exploration over reactive, institution-driven content production. The blog facilitates my authentic voice, identity, and self-expression, which allows the integration of wit, personality, and critique in my writing. This, in turn, enables me to showcase my distinct professional identity.

What did this give me?

- Personal recognition
- Agency
- Voice

Reflection

The purpose of sharing this process was to encourage fellow educational designers to assert ownership of their skills, knowledge, and identity. As part of my presentation, I included a call to action for their third space professionals to reclaim their resources and share their journey. A similar journey is that of my fellow colleague, EDI advocate and educational designer, Aster Cosmos, whose blog represents their own passions, skills, knowledge and experience, exemplified in [one of their posts about the Third Space Symposium](#). “You were so right about using time between things to do material building for your brand. Ranting into my phone in speech-to-text mode while I'm driving home is an excellent way to make blog posts!”

Initially, I expressed limited interest in actively promoting the blog, citing constraints of time and energy. However, in recent months, I have found renewed motivation to engage with strategies related to search engine optimisation (SEO) and digital dissemination. I have learnt that visibility in search engine results actually requires verification with platforms like Google search to ensure a website's presence is recognised and accessible to a broader audience. So I'm currently in the process of tweaking my blog posts in line with SEO strategies, but it's a slow process.

A call to action

In the presentation, I also wanted others to feel the same sense of empowerment I've felt from writing in my own voice and owning my own words. I wanted to see other people reclaiming their

professional identities and resources. I still want this, so if you're reading this and it strikes a chord: Start the journey, keep in touch, and send me a link to your blog, because I'd love to subscribe.

About the author

Dana Bui

Monash University

Educational Designer

<https://gravatar.com/theeducationaldesigner>

Why am I talking about it here and now?

Reflecting on educational design practice

Josephine Hook, Julie Luu, Prudence Perry, Frances Broomhead, Aster Cosmos, Yogita Ahuja, Brendan Boniface, Cathy Sell, Carmen Sapsed, and Andrew Junor

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845108>

We are a group of ten educational designers at Monash University, drawn from a much larger group of approximately 70 educational designers across all ten faculties and the central learning and teaching office at Monash. We all work in different ways, either on our own or in a team, with different priorities and access to resources, and at different stages of our careers.

We gathered some brief reflections on our practice and experience, with a focus on our professional development, as we believe this might be useful advice for others working in the field. This self-reflective work helps us to gather evidence of our impact, making our third space work more visible, and disentangling the work and ourselves from organisational structures.

After the Slowposium presentation, participants joined the discussion and shared with others their thoughts on the concepts and ideas presented under the sections detailed below, following the instructions to explore the reflections from participants in each section of this site “and use them as a prompt to think about PD opportunities which might resonate with you.”

About our reflections

The reflections are organised into the following sections:

- What do you do, and how did you get here?
- What are the goals of your work, and how do you measure ‘success’?
- What are some of the blockers to success?
- What PD have you found most valuable?
- What further advice do you have for educational designers seeking to progress their careers?

Each of these sections is divided according to the three different levels of educational designer, termed *education developers* in the Canadian literature, classified by Dawson et al. (2010). The North Island College Centre for Teaching and Learning Innovation (Canada) (North Island College, n. d.) built on this work to create ‘competency charts’ which outline the skills, qualities, knowledge and abilities of educational designers at various stages of growth and professional learning.

The three levels are:

1. novice/entry-level (1-5 years)
2. intermediate/associate director (5-7 years)
3. senior/director (7+ years)

The Educational Developers Caucus (Canada) has published a series of Education Developers guides (see Society for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education [Canada], n.d.). These guides prompt us with a range of suggestions to develop our own portfolios of practice, build rapport and trust in our practice, and reflect on our practice.

What do you do, and how did you get here?

Novice 1-5 years

I currently work in two roles, as a casual educational designer, and as a part-time digital learning support officer (providing learning design and LMS administration). I previously worked in teaching, research, and academic support and found that the tasks I was doing were slowly evolving into ed design, as that was what was needed by the teams I worked in, and I had a higher digital literacy than others which made me the best choice at the time.

I am an Educational Designer in a Faculty at Monash University. I worked in learning design and instructional design in various corporate roles for approximately five years before moving in to HE. When I was ready to return to the workforce after my second child, I decided to look for part-time work, so I got a casual role with FAST here at Monash. I was initially placed with the DVCE but came over to the Faculty to assist in their move to 'Flex' unit offerings, and I have never left! I was lucky enough to secure a fixed-term contract position at first and then an ongoing contract. I have now been in the faculty as an ed designer for 4.5 years.

I work as a faculty educational designer, with a focus on assessment design and innovation. I transitioned into educational design after working as a learning skills adviser and teaching associate, with previous experience as a researcher and educator in history. These previous roles involved a lot of teaching and student-facing support, so I developed practical knowledge of student learning across a range of contexts, assessment approaches, etc. Over time I became increasingly interested in the curriculum design and development aspect of my work, in which I collaborated with academics or co-developed curriculum resources to improve student learning experiences and outcomes. This interest led me to educational design.

Intermediate 5-7 years

I work across three domains – educational design, education governance and management, and strategic initiatives. Started off as a STEM Educator while pursuing PhD. After 10 years of teaching experience, I furthered my passion for Higher Education by proactively getting involved in education projects and initiatives across the university including accelerated projects during the COVID era. After a couple of years of intensive experience in Ed Design in one faculty, I transitioned to a different faculty as an Ed Designer driving education transformation (course redesign and accreditation, curriculum revamp, T&R staff development). I now lead a team of four learning and education designers, along with project-based collaboration with T&R staff and teaching fellows.

Working directly with teachers to advise them around student engagement, meaningful assessment, etc. anything in the pedagogy but also EduTech space together with broad strategic educational initiatives at faculty level. I originally started as a teacher (tutor, then lecturer) in my faculty and did that for many years, eventually leading a number of big units myself and engaging in some initial scholarship in the education space. The teaching work dried up however (or rather was not offered on a contract type that was sustainable for me) and I transitioned into an educational designer role in the same faculty.

I support academics in creating high quality educational experiences and outcomes for students. I view it as a jack-of-all-trades type role. I arrived by happy accident really. I had a STEM research background, but followed the education pathway, primarily because I was passionate about education. I enjoyed teaching and I was quite good at it, but I could not keep up with having young children and the out of hours demands. One day I applied for an Educational Designer role in an area where I had both teaching and some discipline expertise and essentially learned on the job and haven't looked back!

Senior 7+ years

I'm a senior educational designer in a faculty, where I manage a small team of educational designers to advise and support our educators in their education practice. I started as a high school teacher, then as a research student I was given an UG teaching load. I worked as a head tutor and lecturer teaching into a variety of units in my department. From there I went into a student-facing academic support role where I saw the myriad challenges students face in their studies. When my current role as an educational designer was advertised, I jumped at the chance to effect curriculum transformation at a more strategic level.

Lead and support educational initiatives and projects across the faculty and university, including the design, delivery, and administration of all units, including the learning management system. Most of my education was completed through distance learning, and later, online education. As a trained teacher, I became deeply interested in designing learning experiences for people. With the rise of online learning, I saw it as an opportunity to future-proof my career in an area I was passionate about. This led me to pursue a Masters of Education (Online Learning and Design) and transition my career into higher education, where I have had the opportunity to grow my skills and expertise.

I inspire positive changes in academic teaching practices through consultation, facilitation of professional development, and supporting teaching excellence. I was an English teacher, student trainer and lecturer overseas before applying for and becoming an Ed Designer.

I am an educational designer who supports educators in all aspects of T+L from course conception and governance, through to development, delivery and evaluation, classroom instruction, EDI/UDL, staff wellbeing, curriculum development, accreditation, assessment innovation, staff training, research (scholarship of T+L) and online lessons and LMS design. I

studied and practised science for many years (since 2010), working as a researcher in laboratory and field contexts. I regularly supplemented my income with tertiary science teaching, in class, computer, laboratory and field settings, coursework and research settings. I really loved teaching, ed design and research, but as ed design was the more attainable and stable of the teaching and research work I had been trained to do (and was doing), I accepted an ed design offer when it was made to me (rather out of the blue, four years ago; my current manager, who at the time I had never met, emailed me one night saying I had come highly recommended for my ed design skills). While I desperately miss science teaching and research, I really enjoy the science education research and educator training I do as part of my ed design role, and much of the foundational scientific content is the same in the science discipline I am now proud to be in. At the end of the day, I have kids and a mortgage so, while I adore the role and am committed to the sector, I would be only telling a half-truth if I suggested that the job security within a Go8 university setting wasn't the lead factor in my being here!

What are your goals and how do you measure success?

Novice 1-5 years

The goals of my work have changed frequently over different roles, but it is always with the greater aim to support quality teaching and learning. I personally measure success in my role by enabling measurable success in others (i.e. seeing what they are able to do with the skills or systems I assist them to develop), and by how the output I produce is utilised by others.

My two specific work goals for this year are –

1. Play a key role in the strategic planning and implementation of innovative and evidenced-based educational practices, specifically the exploration of relevant education technologies where it makes sense to do so, within the faculty, university and wider higher education community. This will be measured through completion and delivery of a number of specific projects.
2. Advising and leading educators in the development of engaging and holistic learning experiences that consider the asynchronous and synchronous spaces as inherently linked, providing research-backed guidance on how to develop engaging and effective learning activities that tell a clear narrative for students. This will be measured through completion of some specific projects – supporting the University LMS upgrade, delivery of ed tech workshops, and general unit design.

More broadly, my own goals for my work revolve around being a trusted T&L advisor, increasing my knowledge & contribution to SoTL, continuing to improve my presentation skills, and working on new & exciting education interventions across the university.

I aim to foster effective and engaging curriculum design and teaching practices among the academics I work with, to enable improved student learning experiences and outcomes. I partially measure success in relation to practical pedagogical/curriculum improvements at the unit and level, e.g. better student engagement, academic performance, progression of skills and approaches across study levels in a program, more authentic and impactful assessment approaches, etc.

I also measure success in terms of my influence on the pedagogical capacity of the academic community I work with, e.g. providing advice or resources that build the educational knowledge and skills of academics in my faculty. This includes identifying and disseminating authentic peer learning examples (e.g. assessment designs), so academic colleagues can learn from one another's approaches.

Intermediate 5-7 years

- 1) Student success
- 2) Staff enablement
- 3) Efficient continuous improvement and quality assurance processes for delivering high quality education
- 4) Undertaking education research and evaluation for publishing.

My goal is to iteratively improve our offerings one step at a time, upskill and mentor our teachers to help them be better educators and change organisational and local processes to incorporate sound pedagogical practices.

I do a lot of observational work and reflection on what I see in the activities and materials of a subject, together with quantitative data analysing student performance around particular concepts, having teachers I work with share back their key findings which I compare against my expectations, as well as the usual mix of surveys and focus groups.

Very broadly – to support my school in delivering the best educational opportunities for our students and enable them to go forth and be well equipped for their future lives. More specifically though, the two primary goals would be

- 1) to assist in finding critical areas for improvement and determining the best way to address these (i.e. 1:1 work with academics, or creating professional development opportunities) and
- 2) fostering a supporting culture that looks to promote best practice and innovative approaches.

I find measuring success is generally difficult as there are many factors that will influence outcomes. But I generally look at (in no particular order) SETU feedback from students (general but also comments about specific aspects of a unit I've worked on), staff feedback (formal/informal), staff attendance at events, various observable trends (e.g. % various assessment types). Some aspects of success are harder to measure: for example, when supporting new academics, one measure of success is when they don't need to ask me anymore.

Senior 7+ years

My role has evolved over nine years from working intensively with individual academics who wanted to try something new in their education practice – with a focus on LMS design, and assessment – which were really tangible ways into unit design more broadly. We had centrally set targets for 'enhancement' at the time, so I measured the number of units where my team had an

impact, no matter how small. Over time, though, working with successive DDEs and changing education priorities, opportunities arose for the work of my team to become more strategic. I looked at how we could effect education transformation at the course level. We did this by providing curriculum maps and reviews to course leaders, who were encouraged to lead a conversation with their teaching teams on the narrative of their programs, how skills and knowledge development should/could be scaffolded through a program via learning activities and programmatic assessment. This work is now aligned to the formal course review process, so it has become embedded in faculty practices, and leads to course level renewal. So I started small, and looked for opportunities for our work to become more integrated into existing processes. We have nurtured relationships and trust with our academic colleagues over time so that we are seen to add value to course and unit renewal. Not that we're all the way there yet – progress has been slow and we continue to seek ways to tell the stories of our impact so our academic colleagues welcome us into the conversation.

My goals are to manage the day-to-day delivery of education, support the staff who do this work and engage in projects that forward the education goals of my faculty and the wider university. I measure success by my ability to manage this workload whilst still making positive impactful contributions to the strategic education goals of the institution.

Inspiring positive changes in teaching practices to create better learning experiences and outcomes for students.

Evidence of success is mostly anecdotal, but can be found in:

- 1) academic colleague's unsolicited and solicited comments
- 2) students' comments and ratings of purpose-built surveys (e.g. regarding learning materials, multimedia, interactive activities I built or supported in building)
- 3) academics' implementation of teaching practices and awards/ recognition of those practices
- 4) professional development requested by departments in the faculty, and
- 5) collaborative project grants/ publication output.

I aim to empower people, students and educators, with the competence and confidence and love for learning and scientific research methods. I aim to enable close, progressive, open and dynamic communities which foster care for people globally and for the environment, and I strive to remove or reduce barriers to educational engagement. I measure my success through successful class, unit and course delivery in a range of metrics, including student satisfaction, student performance, and student retention. I also measure success through community health metrics such as community closeness, diversity, and my feelings around staff happiness. For example, if staff are all present and engaged and coming to me with joy and excitement and passion, I feel I have succeeded. If there is a positive learning culture in the student body, I consider myself successful. I also value positive ad hoc commentary from my peers and colleagues, and well as performance reviews.

What are some of the 'blockers' to success?

Novice 1-5 years

It can be difficult to schedule time to evaluate measurable success in a meaningful way. I think that by the nature of the work we do at university, we are always pushing to move forward to the next semester, or the next project, and don't often have the opportunity to pause and reflect.

I think one of the biggest challenges is the amount of "invisible work" that goes into our role. It's work that is often hard to quantify, can be very time-consuming, and the lines can be blurred in regard to whose responsibility the work is. Some of this comes down to pushing back on certain tasks, which I will admit I'm not very good at doing, but I think some of it also comes down to a lack of workforce planning, i.e. not enough people to do the work, and team structures not fit to accommodate the work properly.

Another big challenge for me, personally, is a lack of confidence in certain scenarios. Because of the many people around who hold PhDs and the like, I often have a little bit of imposter syndrome. I think this also comes down to the vast number of things that we need to advise on: I am very confident in some areas and not so confident in others. I think there's a tendency to feel like we need to be experts on everything, which is an impossible thing to be!

In my role, there are some factors that can limit my impact at times.

It is generally easiest to make successful contributions at the unit level. Unit level work can be limited by the time/resourcing available to my academic colleagues and myself, so is generally targeted / staged. Given these limitations, success can sometimes be modest or gradual. When possible I work to create impact at higher levels (e.g. program level, Area of Study/School/Faculty level), where I would say that the key barrier again can be academic colleagues' scarcity of time or attention. Building ongoing relationships/trust over time can address this challenge, particularly by demonstrating sensitivity to the specific contexts of different academic collaborators/ disciplines.

Another challenge relates to the place of my role / team within its organisational context, e.g. the relative standing of professional and academic staff, occasional overlaps/ confusion/ communication gaps between my team and other teams within and outside of the faculty. These are fairly standard organisational issues and are not generally a major problem. In terms of barriers to success, I would say that the necessity to ensure buy-in/alignment from multiple organisational stakeholders can sometimes undermine my team's ability to show independent initiative and ambition — but conversely, this also means we are generally well-attuned to the practical needs of our clients/leadership, and don't over-invest in or duplicate project work.

Intermediate 5-7 years

- 1) Lack of stability/constant changes in business processes
- 2) T&R staff workload and time limitations

- 3) Support/encouragement for professional staff to pursue Ed focussed research as a part of their workload
- 4) No means to share ideas for strategic initiatives

- not having the budget or buy-in from leadership to get important work done
- overly bureaucratic processes to make major changes end up tripling the time to see any real changes
- teaching staff I work with not having the time to invest in upskilling or doing things differently
- the psychological welfare of staff

Primarily due to confounding factors – if you help design a really great assessment and rubric it can be objectively great but implemented poorly, for example. Likewise, if you contribute to a unit requiring an IUP, if it ends up a “purple” unit, the success must be attributed to many moving parts that have been effectively implemented (not just my role), so it’s hard to determine how effective my contributions were.

Additionally, academic buy-in is required for everything and becomes a condition for success. If there is not academic buy-in, it doesn’t get off the ground. I feel that academic workload and attitudes contribute to this – no doubt they have heavy workloads, especially at peak times, but I think the distance between my (professional) role and their (academic) role sometimes means they are unwilling to take on my suggestions. My perception at times is that given I am no longer at the coalface I am certainly viewed by some academics as “admin”, here to create more work for them for no good reason.

Senior 7+ years

The key frustration for me early on was that despite University and Faculty mandates for education transformation, and all the work I’d done to provide a scalable pedagogic model – which was supported by a complex mix of learning theory, blended learning methodology and instructional design principles, ‘just-in-time’ support resources, workshops – uptake across the faculty was at best uneven, with pockets of resistance to any innovation whatsoever. The work was exhausting and at times demoralising. It took me some years of trial and error, and reflection, to realise that my initial change management strategy – building relationships, working with early adopters, and showcasing exemplars of good practice – needed to be recast as a learning design, with our educators as active learning participants in their own learning. Bringing educators together in dialogic and disciplinary learning communities helps to reinforce their identity as educators and experts in their fields; acknowledge the passion, fear and pride in teaching; create a safe space for creative risk-taking; and scaffold their own development.

Probably just the amount of work that we need to do due to all the change that is occurring around us, everything is urgent, everything needs to be completely redone, nothing lasts for even 12 months.

Organisational culture and a lack of reward/ promotion structure that recognise and celebrate teaching as much as does research. We often get to work with teaching-focussed academics, or T&R academics who are passionate about teaching, or academics who are “required” to work with us. However, there is a great portion who either don’t prioritise teaching or simply don’t have the time to dedicate to teaching.

Sometimes, I do not quite have the knowledge base to help educators with problems they encounter. For example, I could probably use some upskilling in universal design for learning principles, and some more digital learning environment- themed issues, such as managing H5Ps or having seamless platform interfacing. These are issues that stress educators out, and that I am sometimes having to really reach to support them. I also find that some administrative and organisation structures and infrastructure can be very limiting, particularly communications. I could use some more active inclusion in terms of being in the third space. I often fall off email lists, and people are sometimes unclear about what I am expecting from them or what they can expect from me.

What PD have you found the most valuable?

Novice 1-5 years

In terms of informal PD, I have found participating in communities of practice to be the most valuable because of the knowledge and perspectives shared.

In terms of formal PD, I have recently undertaken a postgraduate degree in digital teaching and learning, and that was invaluable for the opportunity to explore technologies and theories that I wouldn’t otherwise have been able to dedicate the time to.

The most valuable PD for me has been formal qualifications which I have had to fund myself. I’ve been wanting to do my Masters of Education since I’ve joined in this role but have found the cost to be a major barrier. I have recently commenced a Grad Cert in Education through a CSP, and in the short time that I have done it have found it to be hugely beneficial to my role as an ed designer.

Conferences are also great, which I’ve been lucky enough to have funded by the faculty. Writing papers and presenting have been so valuable, not just in developing my knowledge in SoTL but also in developing my writing and presentation skills and building my professional network.

I tend to value the sharing of practice examples and approaches from higher education T&L colleagues, via conferences, seminars, peer learning / discussion, etc. Because my role requires me to participate in curriculum design problem-solving and innovation with academics, learning about authentic approaches that others have applied can be particularly useful.

More general, non-specific PD can be useful for better understanding general principles or key concepts, but I tend to find such PD less immediately useful (e.g. general coverage of T&L concepts, introductory ed tech training, etc.) It’s often not that difficult to find online resources

that cover the basics — and the most impactful PD is more specific to my role’s current context / problems.

Intermediate 5-7 years

It’s mostly been 70/20/10 approach in terms of PD, with the majority of it coming from experience on job. Other than that I have found attending TELevisors network and other educational forums quite helpful in finding a community of belonging and source of motivation to undertake self-guided initiatives to collaborate.

I found KaosPilot to be a really helpful training which distilled together a considerably number of pedagogies and learning theories into a cohesive whole and adopts a very clear framework around the design of not just learning but any experience-based event.

I did the QM rubric course a few years ago, which at the time I found valuable in terms of having a framework to audit courses for quality: <https://www.qualitymatters.org/qa-resources/rubric-standards/higher-ed-rubric>

I have an interest in education research so I found it useful to do a course on Education Research through my faculty, which helped me to interpret literature more effectively and boost my critical thinking skills.

Attending various disciplinary education conferences also helps to stay on top of who is doing what – especially in terms of innovation. Similarly, I have appreciated the post-COVID explosion of various webinar series as they are more accessible than in-person events.

Senior 7+ years

In an effort to make my work more visible, I have concentrated my PD efforts on conference presentations and publications, and journal articles, in collaboration with ed design and academic colleagues – although the time available for this work does get pushed out by more pressing BAU deadlines. The one thing I have found most valuable for myself professionally is to apply for HEA fellowship. The process of writing a narrative of professional practice required me to reflect on my practice and my influence for the first time, and served to align my work with educational theory and research. This has filtered back into my work where I am feeling less like an imposter and more like an expert in my field.

Attending conferences, it’s this window of time where you don’t have to be answering questions and emails constantly, and you just get to think and reflect on your work and what impactful initiatives you can engage with (even if they are not related to the conference).

I find courses on LinkedIn Learning, Coursera and other online learning platforms helpful. They are great tasters and can offer a wide range of topics from which you can choose. I am currently working towards the Google User Experience Design Certificate.

I really enjoy going to L+T conferences, particularly small or discipline-specific ones. I get key skills/workshops, bonus incidental content (like that other talk in the session that isn't the one I came along for but was completely great and relevant), and the networking is invaluable.

Do you have some further advice to share with colleagues?

Novice 1-5 years

Collaborate with each other as much as possible. We all have such varied backgrounds and wisdom, and it's so much fun to share and learn from each other.

Be flexible, be open to learning new things, collaborate with others as much as you can, build good quality relationships, continue to study (if you can), identify a few areas of interest/ specialisation, attend conferences & engage with professional networks.

It's hard to think of catch-all career advice, because ED roles cover a range of niches, with people from different professional backgrounds. The most valuable skill that cuts across all contexts may be the ability to narrate stories of significant impact related to ED work. It can be challenging to delineate the impact of one's individual ED contributions (or an ED team's contributions) from the work of academic colleagues, other organisational teams, etc. So my advice might focus on reflectively documenting and narrating impactful work, from goal-setting to review of impact. The goals of ED work are often set by academics based on the challenges they face in their teaching context — but EDs (consciously or not) can play a valuable role in helping academics to define the educational problems, and the goals and methods to address them (e.g. by drawing upon concepts from SOTL and relevant practice examples).

Intermediate 5-7 years

Be proactive. Join the TELedvisors Network and other CoPs and get active on LinkedIn. Find friendtots (experienced people working in the same area as you who can be your well-wishers, director of honesty and mentor). If you think of an idea or come across an opportunity, talk to your manager and try to provide a rationale for how it aligns with the Faculty/School/Division's vision.

Take all the opportunities you have to show off your work and how great you are as this becomes necessary evidence to others that you know what you're talking about.

If your role allows, carve out projects that are genuinely of interest to you to keep the motivation going.

Senior 7+ years

Find a mentor, probably from outside your regular team/faculty. Find a learning community where you can test out ideas. Begin any project with an exploration of data and scholarly literature. Reflect on your practice and investigate where you can influence others' practice. Manage up where necessary to ensure you have a seat at the table!

Always try to design things that make people's life easier: no-one likes more complexity or additional work. This will make you shine!

1. Collaboration is key.
2. Learn new skills. An ed designer needs to solve problems, sometimes from multiple angles. Having a diverse skillset will be very useful.

Absolutely! Be communicative and proactive. This role does not just exist or just “happen”. It is crafted and curated and guided constantly, and has to be actively integrated into the T+L community, either through formal processes and procedures, but also in terms of more organic staff interactions and social structures. The deference of leadership to your authority in ed design is critical for educators to find you relevant and valuable. If all of these things aren't working ideally, speak up! Be clear about what you expect from the role, and where you can take it. It is an active role, always. Make it go, make it grow.

References

- Dawson, D., Britnell, J., & Hitchcock, A. (2010). Developing competency models of faculty developers: Using World Café to foster dialogue. In L. Nilson & J. Miller (Eds.), *To improve the academy: Resources for faculty, instructional, and organizational development*, 28 (pp. 3-24). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- North Island College. (n.d.). *Educational Development – Teach Anywhere*. Center for Teaching and Learning Innovation. Retrieved December 8, 2025, from <https://teachanywhere.opened.ca/home/key-info-links/about-centre-staff/eddev/>
- Society for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education [Canada]. (n.d.). Educational development resources. *STLHE*. Retrieved December 8, 2025, from <https://stlhe.ca/resources-2/educational-development-resources/>

*About the authors***Josephine Hook***Monash University*

Senior Educational Designer | SFHEA

Julie Luu*Monash University*

Educational Designer

Prudence Perry

Monash University

Educational Designer

Frances Broomhead

Monash University

Educational Designer

Aster Cosmos

Monash University

Educational Designer | Accessibility

Advocate | Equity & Diversity Champion

Dr Yogita Ahuja

Monash University

Lead Educational Designer

Brendan Boniface

Monash University

Educational Designer

Dr Cathy Sell

Monash University

Educational designer and translator

Carmen Sapsed

Monash University

Educational Designer | FHEA

Dr Andrew Junor

Monash University

Educational Designer (Assessment
Specialist)

Capturing third space skills and competencies

Keith Heggart, Kate Mitchell, and Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845187>

As co-facilitators of this session, our intention was to create a structured opportunity for third space practitioners to articulate, for themselves, the breadth and depth of their professional practice. We came together from slightly different institutional contexts but with a shared commitment to building a sector-wide understanding of third-space work that is not defined by formal position descriptions, but by lived professional practice. The session was designed not as research, but as a collegial act of professional sense-making and community-building.

We opened by situating the idea that third-space roles sit at the intersection of academic, professional and strategic domains, which means the expertise required is often hybrid, relational, and emergent. Because this hybridity is not always well recognised or documented, competencies tend to remain tacit and undervalued. Our aim, therefore, was not to define a competency framework, but to surface the work in people's own terms, allowing practitioners to speak for themselves rather than being spoken for by role classifications.

The use of a shared Padlet board enabled rapid, ground-up mapping of the practices attendees considered central to their roles. However, our reflections as facilitators centred less on the content shared and more on the experience of the process. What was most striking for us was the affective dimension: participants appeared energised not because they were “listing skills,” but because they were being invited to name and legitimise aspects of their practice that are usually invisible in institutional discourse. The act of identifying these practices publicly felt unusual precisely because so much expertise is routinely assumed rather than acknowledged.

For us as hosts, this was a reminder of how infrequently third-space workers are given a forum to collectively narrate their contribution. The session confirmed something we had anticipated in planning: that there is an appetite for building structures of recognition, not only in terms of professional development, but in terms of shared identity formation. The energy in the space suggested that naming practice is not simply descriptive — it is political, in the sense that it challenges reductive framings of third-space work as “support” rather than as professional judgement and intellectual labour.

The interactive format also led us to reflect on the methodological value of bottom-up mapping as a community-building practice. Where formal frameworks tend to start with categories and map people into them, this approach inverts the logic — the community defines what counts, and only later (if desired) can this be codified. As facilitators, we were conscious that our role was not to validate or evaluate individual contributions, but to create the conditions in which they could be voiced and held in common.

Ultimately, the session highlighted for us that recognition for third-space practitioners cannot come solely from institutional structures — it must also emerge from within the community itself.

This activity was a small step toward building that shared language and visibility. Our next challenge, as a collective, is to consider how these practitioner-led understandings might evolve into sustainable forms of peer recognition, professional development pathways, and sector advocacy.

About the authors

Keith Heggart

University of Technology Sydney

Senior Lecturer and Director of the Centre for Research on Education in a Digital Society (CREDS)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2331-1234>

Kate Mitchell

The University of Melbourne

Senior Learning Designer (ePortfolio)

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

What can learning design do?

A case for pedagogy before technology

Jeremy Stothers

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845193>

Learning designers are often asked to apply technology to learning. But, if we first apply learning theory, then the student experience can be a lot richer.

Is it a designer's job to edit lesson content?

Use the QR code below or go to youtube.com/watch?v=IYh5sNRnIIY to watch the video (Stothers, 2024), then consider the provocation.

Notes and resources:

- Learning theory: [Constructivism](#)
- "How to make it succeed: Give relevant problems that call on pre-existing knowledge while providing generous help."
Adapted from [Map It: The hands-on guide to strategic training design](#)
- This execution shares much in common with active learning as per the [Carl Weiman Science Education Initiative](#). See examples in action:
 - Recommended video: [Inspiring and resolving a lesson](#)
 - [Menu of videos](#) associated with the initiation.

Resources

Constructivism – <https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/constructivism>

Map it: The hands-on guide to strategic training design – <https://blog.cathy-moore.com/book-map-it/>

Carl Weiman Science Education Initiative – <https://cwsei.ubc.ca/>

Inspiring and resolving a lesson – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zATnGROyHF&t=34s>

Menu of videos – <https://cwsei.ubc.ca/resources/instructor/demos>

Reference

Stothers, J. (2024). *Learning Design: A case for theory (before technology)*
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IYh5sNRnIY>

About the author

Jeremy Stothers

Monash University

Learning Designer

Partners in crime

Nexus ed developers as co-leads

Diana Saragi Turnip, Jon Xiating Cai, and Zara Khan

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845199>

This presentation explored the integration of Nexus educational developers as co-leads in educational projects within the Faculty of Medicine & Health at the University of New South Wales. It looked at their role in enhancing collaboration, fostering innovation, and driving impactful outcomes in medicine and health education.

Our aim was for participants to gain insights into the value of Nexus educational developers as co-leads and practical strategies for fostering innovation in their own projects within their own educational contexts in the faculty.

About the authors

Diana Saragi Turnip

University of New South Wales

Educational Developer, Medicine and Health

Jon Xiating Cai

University of New South Wales

Senior Educational Developer, Medicine and Health

Zara Khan

University of New South Wales

Educational Developer, Pro-Vice Chancellor Education and Student Experience

Journeys into third space working

Charlotte Verney, Kelly Vere, and Tara Webster-Deakin

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845209>

In our recent article (Vere et al., 2024), we explored third space working in universities drawing on our three doctoral research projects. We reflected on individual, institutional and sector-wide experiences of third space working and how boundaries between academic and professional staff can be crossed and even dismantled to enable more productive relationships and working.

Part One: Journeys into third space working: personal experiences of boundary-crossing

An asynchronous interaction with Padlet materials in Week One of the Slowposium

To begin with, we shared our three distinct, yet connected, experiences of third space professionals working in HE in England through three mini case studies and/or vlogs, accessible to participants in a Padlet, illustrated below.

Material for Journeys into third space, available online at <https://uonarts.padlet.org/afztw/materials-for-journeys-into-third-space-webster-deakin-verne-wwj8sp8bd9a3qfq9>

We posed three questions to the Slowposium participants as follows:

1. What boundaries do you cross in your current role or have you crossed during your career?
2. What boundaries do you feel unable to cross, and why?

3. How can we create spaces in HE in which we can cross or dismantle boundaries?

Part Two: How can we facilitate third space working within our organisations?

A live online session in Week Two of the Slowposium

Drawing again on Vere et al. (2024), we hosted a live online discussion/webinar focusing on the questions provoked by the article.

During the discussion/webinar, we linked to challenges and opportunities shared by participants in Week One and engaged live participants in unpicking some of the gnarlier issues of working in the third space.

Reference

Vere, K., Verney, C., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2024). Crossing and dismantling boundaries: recognising the value of professional staff within higher education. *London Review of Education*, 22.1.29. <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.22.1.29>

About the authors

Charlotte Verney

University of Bristol

Head of Assessment

Kelly Vere

University of Nottingham

Director of Technical Strategy

Tara Webster-Deakin

University of Nottingham

Assistant Professor, Widening Participation and Outreach Manager, Faculty of Arts

Recognition

Demonstrating our value and raising awareness of our contributions

Establishing your credibility

Sharon Altena, Meredith Hinze, and Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845215>

Learning designers are highly qualified learning and teaching professionals (Altena et al., 2019; Altena et al., 2025) who have struggled over the past 40 years to establish their legitimacy and credibility within universities (Szekeres, 2011). The COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent rapid pivot to online learning have assisted to some degree in the valuing and legitimatising of learning designers within universities (Petherbridge et al., 2022; Xie & Rice, 2021). At the same time, there is increasing awareness that design and teaching in universities has become increasingly complex due to the heterogeneous nature of students, changing student demands, and technological impacts on learning and teaching, particularly generative AI.

The design of learning in higher education is no longer the sole remit of the lone academic, but is a shared endeavour with specialist curriculum designers, learning designers, academic developers, learning technologists, librarians and student success coaches working in partnership with university teachers (Bawa & Watson, 2017). The positioning of learning designers as “support staff” or “techies” within institutions is unhelpful for convincing academic staff to see learning designers as equal partners (Altena et al., 2019; Prusko & Kilgore, 2023).

So, the question remains, how can learning designers and other third space workers establish their credibility within institutions?

To explore this question, an in-person workshop was held at the Third Space Symposium in Melbourne. This workshop explored the concept of credibility, which was defined as “the quality of being believable and worthy of trust” (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.; Collins Dictionary, n.d.; Merriam-Webster Dictionary, n.d). At its core, credibility was viewed as being about human connection and understood to be multifaceted and context specific. Credibility was conceptualised as having seven dimensions as shown in Figure 1. Importantly, it was acknowledged that credibility is not something that you can bestow upon yourself, but rather it is a gift given to us by others, which is earned through our actions and interactions with others.

Figure 1: *The seven dimensions of credibility*

Drawing upon leadership theory and positive psychology, the workshop took a proactive, strengths-based approach where upward spiral conversations were encouraged, and the tall poppy syndrome and imposter syndrome were discouraged. The message to participants was:

*“We can’t get others to believe us
if we don’t believe ourselves.” (Jolles, 2018)*

Three learning designers shared their 30 practical strategies they use for building their credibility and profiles within and outside of their institutions. Some examples included:

Sharon

Meredith

Lye Ee (Rebecca)

Make effective use of your email signature to show your title, qualifications, awards received and publications.

Build your professional profile and promote your work on social media (see "What's Beyond Twitter / X?" in these proceedings).

Prior to meeting with an academic, send a short, friendly email introduction that includes examples of your previous work.

Participants were subsequently encouraged to share and discuss their own strategies for building their credibility with others in the room. In the second part of the workshop, participants had the opportunity to use the My Credibility Map and Action Plan as shown in Figure 2, to identify who and why they need or want to develop credibility with, and to then prepare an action plan with dates about the proactive steps they could take towards building or further strengthening their credibility.

Figure 2: My credibility and action plan canvas

My Credibility Map and Action Plan

NEED	Who I need credibility with 	Why? 	What? 	When?
	Who I want credibility with 	Why? 	What? 	When?

Workshop participants were then encouraged to complete a 1-week, 4-month and 12-month commitment card (Figure 3) and seal each commitment card in an envelope to be taken with them back to their workplace. Participants were invited to add their name to an email list indicating that they would like reminder emails sent inviting them to open their commitment envelopes over the course of the next year. Throughout 2024–2025 those who registered have received reminder emails from the facilitators one week, four months and 12 months after the workshop to prompt them to open their envelope and to check-in and act if they have not committed to their identified action.

Figure 3: Example of a My Credibility commitment card

Reflection

Our aim in preparing this workshop for the Third Space Symposium was to give back to the community who had so generously assisted us by being willing to complete a survey or be interviewed by us for our research into the profession.

In preparing for this workshop, we found that it provided us with the unexpected benefit of reflecting on how each of us in our roles have developed our credibility within our institutions and to examine the similarities and differences in our approaches.

Through our workshop we gave our third space colleagues the gift of time to stop ... think ... and reflect on their own credibility and why it is important for them. Purposefully designing the workshop to involve participants in individual, quiet time for reflection activities and collaborative discussions provided a beautiful ebb and flow to the workshop for both the introverts and extraverts in the group. The buzz in the room, the rich conversations, sharing of ideas and connections that were made was more than we had dared to dream and was inspiring for us as the workshop facilitators. It highlighted the value in bringing third space professionals from different institutions together in the one physical space to share their experiences, expertise and the challenges we face individually as we try to establish ourselves as part of a recognised profession in our institutions.

References

- Altena, S., Ng, L. E., & Hinze, M. (2025). Who are learning designers in post-pandemic Australasian universities? *Higher Education Research & Development*, 44(7), 1589–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2025.2482797>
- Altena, S., Ng, R., Hinze, M., Poulsen, S., & Parrish, D. (2019, December 2–5). “Many hats one heart”: A scoping review on the professional identity of learning designers. In Y. W. Chew, K. M. Chan, & A. Alphonso (Eds.), *Personalised learning. Diverse goals. One heart. Proceedings ASCILITE 2019, Singapore*. <https://doi.org/10.14742/apubs.2019.284>
- Bawa, P., & Watson, S. (2017). The chameleon characteristics: A phenomenological study of instructional designer, faculty, and administrator perceptions of collaborative instructional design environments. *The Qualitative Report*, 22(9), 2334–2355. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2017.2915>
- Cambridge Dictionary. (n.d.). Credibility. In *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved 4 November, 2024, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/credibility?q=Credibility>
- Collins Dictionary. (n.d.). Credibility. In *Collins Dictionary*. Retrieved 4 November 2024, from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/credibility>
- Jolles, R. (2018). *Why people don't believe you ... : Building credibility from the inside out*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Merriam-Webster Dictionary. (n.d.). Credibility. In *Merriam-Webster Dictionary*. Retrieved 4 November 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/credibility>
- Petherbridge, D., Bartlett, M., White, J., & Chapman, D. (2022). The disruption to the practice of instructional design during COVID-19. *The Journal of Applied Instructional Design*, 11(2), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.51869/112/dpmbjwdc>
- Prusko, P. T., & Kilgore, W. (2023). It took a pandemic to help us contextualise the value of learning designers in higher education. In T. Jaffer, S. Govender, & L. Czerniewicz (Eds.), *Learning Design Voices* (pp. 29–38). <https://doi.org/10.59668/279.12263>
- Szekeres, J. (2011). Professional staff carve out a new space. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 33(6), 679–691. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2011.621193>
- Xie, J., & Rice, M. F. (2021). Instructional designers' roles in emergency remote teaching during COVID-19. *Distance Education*, 42(1), 70–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587919.2020.1869526>

*About the authors***Sharon Altena***Queensland University of Technology*

Sharon Altena is a Senior Curriculum and Learning Designer within the Learning and Teaching Unit. She undertakes research relating to belonging and the learning design profession.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4260-7006>

[LinkedIn](#)

Meredith Hinze*The University of Melbourne*

Meredith Hinze is Manager, eLearning/eTeaching. Her research interests explore professional identity, leadership and the learning design profession.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2908-9021>

[LinkedIn](#)

Dr Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng*University of Wollongong*

Dr Lye Ed (Rebecca) Ng is a Research Fellow within the Faculty of Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities, ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1191-8242>

Sharing the oxygen mask

Collaboration so we can all breathe more easily

Cristy Bartlett and Kate Derrington

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845223>

This contribution examined how third space practitioners can leverage individual expertise and collaboration to improve profile and impact. In this recorded session, we shared and discussed vignettes of practice, then demonstrated how to build greater visibility and recognition of the value of the third space. By using collaborative practice with other third space practitioners, we can create a stronger shared identity which gives us all a seat on the plane.

In this recording we provided an overview of a session that we presented recently at a UniSQ professional development day. Here we examined the third space in higher education to establish a shared understanding of the term and our current practice. We finished this presentation with vignettes of practice, that demonstrate how we have built greater visibility and recognition of the value of the third space. After watching the video, participants were invited to contribute to a Padlet.

About the authors

Cristy Bartlett

University of Southern Queensland

Manager (Student learning advising)

Kate Derrington

University of Southern Queensland

Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of Third Space professionals

Reflections on lived experience

Dustin Hosseini

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845233>

The discussions for this session had this article as a starting point:

Hosseini, D. D. (2025). Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of third space professionals: reflections on lived experience. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education, Special edition* (33). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1234>

The paper surfaces a recurring challenge encompassing the recognition and visibility of third space professionals in higher education as educators who experience silencing stemming from pernicious ignorance. Accordingly, Dustin uses Dotson's notion of pernicious ignorance (2011, p. 238) to analyse a reflective vignette to illustrate a challenge that undermines third space practitioners.

His aim is to equip readers with theory that they can use to counter negative workplace behaviours, whether observed, experienced or both, while strengthening their positions as third space professionals.

Reference

Dotson, K. (2011). Tracking epistemic violence, tracking practices of silencing. *Hypatia*, 2, 236–257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01177.x>

About the author

Dustin Hosseini

Strathclyde Institute of Education

PhD candidate at the Strathclyde Institute of Education. During the 3SS, Dustin was an Associate Tutor, School of Education, University of Glasgow.

<https://www.dustinhosseini.com/>

Learning Designers: To define or not to define

Dan Laurence and Meredith Hinze

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845238>

While the profession of ‘Learning Designer’ has many pseudonyms and various emergent and liminal qualities, it is not as new as many might like to contend. Learning Design is a heterogeneous profession that famously takes in often multi-skilled communicators, teachers, artists, technicians, psychologists, therapists and taxidermists. Previous studies have explored competency standards to better clarify and professionalise the role ([Hinze, M., Altena, S. & Ng, R. 2022](#)). With various degrees, qualifications and standards being put forward from both institutions, unions and professional bodies intersecting with increasingly corporatised and systematised university cultures seeking to hold the third space to account, it is timely to ask: Should Learning Designers be defined?

This Third Space Slowposium activity pulled apart the pros and cons of this thorny question and sought to have Learning Designers themselves input their opinions into the topic in a structured way using a Kialo board to facilitate a democratic voice from all participants. Participants added pro and con claims below each other’s points, creating an interactive discussion map. Kialo was a useful way of visually structuring debate and allowing participants to see how ideas were connected, supported, or challenged.

We structured the debate in Kialo to canvass the topic of establishing professional competency standards for Learning Design and probe the tensions between professionalisation and flexibility. We saw strong support for standards to establish credibility, career pathways, and quality assurance alongside significant concerns about potentially limiting diversity, innovation, and accessibility within the field. The interdisciplinary nature of learning design work requires flexible, inclusive standards that acknowledge overlapping competencies.

There is a need for further research, discussion and exploration of competency standards in the public domain. From our reflections on the session, we would suggest several middle-ground approaches and critical success factors. These include the need for multiple levels creating different standards for different contexts, building in systematic review and updating processes from the start, and evaluating competency based on evidence from experience and portfolios rather than only formal credentials.

The debate reveals a maturing profession grappling with fundamental questions about identity, quality, and inclusivity. The strongest approach would likely combine the legitimate benefits of professional standards with safeguards against their potential negative consequences.

Reference

Hinze, M., Altena, S. & Ng, R. (2022, December 4–7). Reconnecting with ourselves? Developing standards and competencies for Learning Designers [Panel]. *39th International Conference on Innovation, Practice and Research in the Use of Educational Technologies in Tertiary Education, ASCILITE 2022, Sydney, NSW, Australia*.
<https://doi.org/10.14742/apubs.2022.211>

About the authors

Dan Laurence

Victoria University

Learning Designer / Design Lead

[LinkedIn](#)

Meredith Hinze

The University of Melbourne

Meredith Hinze is Manager, eLearning/eTeaching. Her research interests explore professional identity, leadership and the learning design profession.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2908-9021>

[LinkedIn](#)

"Inside the third space" podcast series

Insights from education design and development professionals

Diana Saragi Turnip, Meredith Macaulay, Ellie McDougall, Morgan Harris, Nasrin Danish, Swapneel Thite, Jon Xiating Cai, Zara Khan, Agnee Amarnath, Camile Moray, and Neil Lawrence

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845249>

The podcast series *Inside the Third Space* seeks to formalise and highlight the achievements of third space professionals, recognising their essential role in driving educational innovation and transformation across the higher education sector. While the series originates from the University of New South Wales, its insights are relevant to a broader community, acknowledging that third space professionals everywhere face similar challenges and opportunities.

The podcast series includes four episodes, each focusing on a different role within education design, development, and program teams, yielding valuable insights into the experiences, challenges, and transformative potential of third space professionals. A discussion forum is available for listeners to connect, share thoughts, and learn from each other's journeys.

Through this initiative, we invite engagement from the broader higher education community, creating an opportunity for dialogue, collaboration, and shared learning. By connecting with others in the field, we aim to inspire and empower professionals to navigate and leverage the "third space" in their own contexts, driving innovation and enhancing the overall educational experience across institutions.

For inquiries or to share your thoughts beyond the 3SS, feel free to reach us at insidethethirdspace@gmail.com

Inside the Third Space podcast

You can listen to the podcast right here in the Slowposium, or you can find it on [Spotify](#), [YouTube](#), [Apple Podcasts](#) or you can add [the RSS feed](#) to your favourite podcast platform.

Episode descriptions

Episode 1 – Lucy Jellema

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/2P7kKeYSROXBQRU922oYNY?utm_source=generator

Host Morgan Harris delves into the concept of the third space with Lucy Jellema, an Educational Developer for equity at UNSW Sydney. Lucy shares her journey, her role in supporting students from low socio-economic backgrounds, and insights into mental health among third-space professionals.

Episode 2 – Fiona Nicolson

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/62G7NN4BGjS2iHDqSfmsVK?utm_source=generator

Host Zara Khan explores the third space with Fiona Nicolson, manager of the Medicine and Health Education Development Unit at UNSW. Fiona shares her journey, insights into academic-professional collaboration, and the challenges and successes within this unique educational space.

Episode 3 – Natalie Gelche

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/1wGdEp8xpB8YfRrRBPkMeW?utm_source=generator

Host Nasrin Danish discusses the third space with Natalie Gelche, a Senior Educational Developer at UNSW. Natalie shares her journey from HR to the third space, navigating life as a non-academic in an academic world, and the significance of embracing AI in education.

Episode 4 – Samadhi Driscoll

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/0EaeOn9QSCOVPUqICy2AWh?utm_source=generator

Host Agneetha Amarnath dives into discussing the unique role of third-space professionals in higher education with guest Samadhi Driscoll, Nexus Program Lead at UNSW Sydney. Samadhi reveals how her background in education and psychology shapes her innovative approach to fostering collaboration and bridging academic and professional perspectives to create lasting impact.

About the authors

Diana Saragi Turnip

University of New South Wales

Educational Developer, Medicine and Health

Meredith Macaulay

University of New South Wales

Meredith was an Educational Developer in the Faculty of Arts, Design and Architecture, as part of the Nexus Program. With a Master's in TESOL, she has over twenty years of experience as an English language teacher, TESOL teacher trainer and materials and curriculum designer.

Ellie McDougall

University of New South Wales

Ellie is an Educational Developer (Nexus) in the Faculty of Engineering with a background in science education.

Morgan Harris

University of New South Wales

Morgan is an educational developer (Nexus) from the Faculty of Engineering.

Nasrin Danish

University of New South Wales

Nasrin is an educational developer (Nexus) from the Faculty of Engineering.

Swapneel Thite

University of New South Wales

Swapneel holds a PhD in Engineering Education: within Nexus, he is an educational developer who currently leads the White Hat AI Hacking of Assessments project.

Jon Xiating Cai

University of New South Wales

Senior Educational Developer, Medicine and Health

Zara Khan

University of New South Wales

Educational Developer, Pro-Vice Chancellor Education and Student Experience

Agnee Amarnath

University of New South Wales

Agnee is an Educational Developer with the Faculty of Science.

Camile Moray

University of New South Wales

Camile is the Educational Development Manager (Nexus) for the Faculty of Science.

Neil Lawrence

University of New South Wales

Neil is an educational developer (Nexus) from the Faculty of Science

Relationships

Building better collaborations with the people that we work with

Beyond the binary: Third space allyship and equity in the academy

Aster Cosmos and Miriam Reynoldson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845271>

Higher education professionals work hard to promote diversity of thought and create safe spaces for learners to contribute, but how many of us feel our workplaces do the same for ourselves and our colleagues? We argue that third space professionals possess unique strengths and opportunities to foster a more inclusive higher education work environment.

In this presentation, we made visible those third space attributes which allow us to be effective and active allies, offered practical strategies for everyday allyship, and shared some of the progress, pitfalls and possibilities of a longer-term project to establish a faculty allyship network.

Acknowledgement of Country

We stand today on the unceded lands of the Wurundjeri People of the Kulin Nations. We acknowledge their continuing connection the Land, Water and Sky Country and the fire of Knowledge they continue to hold and preserve as they have over thousands of generations. We pay our respects to their Elders, past and present and to any First Nations Peoples who are here with us today.

In working in the education space and speaking directly on matters of allyship and equity, it is critical that we recognise the ways in which Indigenous ways of Knowing have been often viewed as lesser as well as their active exclusion from Western learning institutions.

We recognise the important role of Indigenous Knowledge and ways of Knowing in all sites of learning and teaching and the importance of disassembling the ongoing structural barriers in place to seek true justice for Indigenous Australians.

Why this session?

We hope you will:

- ▣ Recognise the depths of your ability to influence change
- ▣ Explore some ways of taking action
- ▣ Reflect on your own space and what allyship is needed there

Some ground rules

- Be respectful towards one another
- Accommodate yourself however you need to support your participation
- Laugh at our jokes, we are funny 😄

Intention	Participants grow to appreciate their potential as active allies into the future
Desired Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the depths of your ability to influence change • Become familiar with with some ways of taking action • Reflect on your own space and what allyship is needed there
Agenda	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is allyship? 2. Why are third spacers uniquely positioned for allyship? 3. Taking action: everyday steps 4. Taking action: Organising
Role	Participate in the prompts and reflect on points raised for your own practice
Rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be respectful towards one another • Accommodate yourself however you need to support your participation • Laugh at our jokes, we are funny 😄
Time	20 minutes

What is allyship?

An **ongoing** way of **changing the world**, one person, one place, one practice at a time.

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

7 ally archetypes

- THE SPONSOR**
Endorses those at risk of being overlooked
- THE CHAMPION**
Recognises people for their expertise
- THE AMPLIFIER**
Ensures all voices are heard
- THE ADVOCATE**
Helps create opportunities for others
- THE SCHOLAR**
Learns about the experiences and challenges of others
- THE CONFIDANT**
Hears and affirms the experiences of others
- THE UPSTANDER**
Intervenes when witnessing wrong being done

From Karen Catlin's *Better Allies: Everyday Action to Create Inclusive, Engaging Workplaces*

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Why is allyship needed?

The fifty million diversity wheels of the internet...

All essentially communicate the plurality of human experience but our societies decide that just a few "kinds" of human are "normal".

... etc.

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

The power of intersections

“ the self can only come into being when it is in dialogic relation with others ”

Lipari, 2014, p. 130

Third spacers...

- work at the intersections
- experience exclusion
- struggle to balance plural identities
- have to fight for recognition

- have privileged access to the spaces of others
- are fluent in multiple discourses
- are building spaces to honour and support each other.

Taking action

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Taking action
Everyday allyship

How did some of what you shared match with these?

- SPONSOR
- CHAMPION
- AMPLIFY
- ADVOCATE
- LEARN
- LISTEN
- STAND UP

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Taking action Organising

- Aster has been part of two allyship groups built at the same time
- Establishing psychological safety
- Creating self-sustaining collectives

Allies need allies!

You can't be an organising committee of one.

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Close

All the pieces of treasure you've heard from us and others in the session are in the chest to the right.

Now you have to pick just one to take with you as you leave.

"What one thing will you do differently when you return to the real world?"

(for you D&D players, I promise it's not a mimic)

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

About the authors

Aster Cosmos

Monash University

Educational Designer | Accessibility Advocate | Equity & Diversity Champion

Miriam Reynoldson

RMIT University Social Equity Research Centre

Miriam is a digital learning specialist, teacher and PhD candidate. Her research explores the value of learning in digital ubiquity.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6022-7739>

[LinkedIn](#)

Co-creating in the third space with friends

A short interactive experience

Jane Kiddell and Steph Quirk

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845287>

Boundary crossing, blended professionals working in the third space are “not constrained by structures and systems but rather cultivate strong relationships, interests and knowledge bases...” (McIntosh & Nutt, 2022). Rewarding third space participation is inherently relational and collaborative, beyond individual experiences: the activities in our three Slowposium live events invited participants to consider what impacts friendships and work alliances have on identity, collaboration and shared understandings of success in the third space.

In a liminal, interactive space, Steph and Jane, who are friends, colleagues and co-designers, invited participants to share and explore the themes of third space work where there are existing relationships between work roles.

- Are the boundaries less “boundy” when trust and commitment are already in place?
- Can existing relationships improve the outcomes of the work that occurs in the third space because values and goals are already formed?

In Mural, 3SS participants explored, in a welcoming, reflexive and conversational space, how relationships and friends impact co-design, success and outcomes in the third space. Together we considered the power of existing relationships and collegial networks in the success or otherwise of our work, celebrating the diversity of skills, qualifications and lived experience of third space practitioners.

Reference

McIntosh, E., & Nutt, D. (2022, May 18). Blended professionals: How to make the most of ‘third space’ experts. *Times Higher Education Campus Learn, Share, Connect*.
<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/blended-professionals-how-make-most-third-space-experts>

About the authors

Jane Kiddell

Deakin University

Lecturer, Learning Futures

Steph Quirk

Deakin University

Senior Digital Learning Developer, Learning Futures

How sense-making drives successful partnerships

Two case studies

Tran Nguyen and Lisa Soviero

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845298>

Partnerships in online learning are becoming increasingly common in higher education. Third space professionals (Whitchurch, 2012), such as learning designers, often play a critical role in these partnerships by setting standards, developing processes and building relationships. They often act as brokers and border-crossers (Keppell, 2007), working across various stakeholder groups to help enhance course quality and student learning (Abblitt, 2024), as well as to influence change and innovation at the interpersonal, professional, institutional, and societal levels (D’Souza et al., 2022). Key to success in these partnerships is sense-making, which helps foster empathy, collaboration, innovation, and resilience by focusing on people rather than process alone.

We share two case studies of third space professional experiences with sensemaking to drive successful partnership outcomes.

- The first case relates to high-level onboarding and maintenance of partnerships, involving a range of stakeholders from client services to faculty.
- The second relates to nurturing effective course co-design relationships between academics and learning designers.

We hope participants in the session gained insights into the role of “third space” professionals in sensemaking and relationship building in fulfilling educational partnerships, so that less time can be spent on resolving challenges and more on collaborating to create an excellent student experience.

References

- Abblitt, S. (2024). Locating academic quality for online learning in higher education: Perspectives from learning design. In D. Gilmore & C. Nguyen (Eds.), *Partnering with online program managers for distance education: Approaches to policy, quality, and leadership* (pp. 139–166). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003387138-10>
- D'Souza, I., Luu, J., & Cui, T. (2022). Educational designer social influence: Changing teaching and learning practice. In S. Wilson, N. Arthars, D. Wardak, P. Yeoman, E. Kalman, and D. Y. T. Liu (Eds.), *Reconnecting relationships through technology. Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Innovation, Practice and Research in the Use of Educational Technologies in Tertiary Education, ASCILITE 2022*. <https://doi.org/10.14742/apubs.2022.56>
- Keppell, M. J. (2007). Instructional designers on the borderline: Brokering across communities of practice. In M. J. Keppell (Ed.), *Instructional design: Case studies in communities of practice* (4th ed; pp. 68–89). IGI Global.
- Whitchurch, C. (2012). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of 'third space' professionals*. Routledge.

About the authors

Tran Nguyen

Keypath

Account Director

Lisa Soviero

Keypath

Learning Design Manager

I am not a chicken farmer

Mark Parry

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845306>

As with most provocations in academic contexts, this video is designed to challenge established ideas and spark critical debate. It's been developed to inform, entertain and push you out of your comfort zone, encourage you to think differently, reconsider your assumptions, and explore new perspectives.

How might we better understand academics and ourselves? On a warm day in the mid 1990s, I visited a chicken farm near Gosford. I was researching and writing an agriculture module and was there to consult with the farmer about his birds and the hidden layers of the farm infrastructure. I brought along a camera and audio recorder.

This presentation poetically explores co-designing with university academics and other subject matter experts (SMEs) by reflecting on that large part of the “educational technology iceberg” that's usually hidden and underwater. Those faint pencil-mark discussions, negotiations, and planning sessions are eventually erased and removed, rendered invisible when the final, sparkling learning resource is delivered. A central cog in the machine exists somewhere in the middle, a professional staff member with a job to do. Those specific and often complicated professional interactions about aligning content to assessments, the critical review of existing assets, and the sequencing of content and activities with pedagogy that are crucial to the role are usually rendered invisible as the course is delivered to learners.

I've been a multimedia producer, instructional designer, academic developer, learning designer, and learning technologist. I am not a chicken farmer. Drawn from professional experiences of more than 30 years as an educational developer working across various educational sectors, including university and higher education, this spoken word presentation explores a central yet often overlooked role of learning technologists in higher education and beyond.

My presentation

(11 mins)

Mark Parry
Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences (FASS)
University of Technology, Sydney (UTS)

Video transcript for **I am not a chicken farmer: A learning designer's reflections on co-designing with academics** [<https://youtu.be/OV8vfgIwK9M?si=6uRjOnMyvN2wDZjZ>]

Hello, my name is Mark Parry. This presentation will take just over ten minutes. It reflects on the hidden aspects of co-designing with academics and Subject Matter Experts (SMEs), much like the submerged part of an educational technology iceberg. The erasures of planning, alignment of content with assessments, and the behind-the-scenes work of learning designers often go unnoticed when the final resource is delivered.

Visibility

Learning design, when done well, is invisible. My career began in 1990 in education, teaching science to high school students. As a teacher, I was central and visible, but when I transitioned to educational resource development in the 90s, my role became more behind-the-scenes. One of my first SMEs was a chicken farmer. Although my role shifted, I was still central to the production process, collaborating with talented technical and creative teams. These projects earned industry awards, though many are now outdated relics of the past.

Despite the invisibility of learning design in the final resource, the actual job role was respected and visible within the teams I worked with. As one screen designer put it, “We all make you look good.” This was a collaborative truth that resonated. I made sure not to take team members for granted.

Collaboration

Educational resources are team efforts, with screen designers, illustrators, coders, audio engineers, and SMEs all playing vital roles. My job appeals to my curiosity and love of learning. Over the years, I've learned from SMEs across various fields: chefs, hairdressers, lawyers, chicken farmers,

firefighters, accountants, anthropologists, scientists, film makers, school principals, board members, doctors—each providing expertise we transformed into educational materials.

However, collaboration isn't always smooth. Some SMEs and educational leaders welcome co-design, while others resist it, viewing learning designers as intruders or threats. I've experienced a range of interactions, both cooperative and adversarial. It all comes down to how the role of learning design is perceived.

Change

I've evolved from a classroom teacher to a learning designer working across educational sectors, from teaching kindergarten to postgraduates to corporate. I've worked as a part-time casual, contract casual, permanent full time, freelance external contractor, and volunteer. I've worked for about ten Australian universities, as an academic and as professional staff and also as a freelancer. Sometimes concurrently. I like being between worlds. I've contributed to dozens of higher educational research projects, especially media-based dissemination of findings, but I'm not a researcher. I describe myself as a practitioner. Apart from higher education, I've also worked in schools, colleges, government agencies, peak bodies, non-profits, corporate, and community organisations. Change is a constant. I love variety. I like being the teacher at the front of the room, but ...

I also like the behind-the-scenes nature of being a learning designer. This is a visual motif of what it's like being behind-the-scenes.

In the post-pandemic era, the role of learning designers has gained further recognition, especially in higher education and corporate training. However, I've often observed that learning design is often misunderstood, especially in systems where the role is reduced to a technical support function or ignored entirely. On top of this, polite, yet controlling behaviour, professional silos and gatekeeping are all problems.

As a recognised job role, learning design is better known now than in 1995, but there's still a way to go.

The shadow side of systems

In my own story as a learning designer, my fundamental aims have always been about trust, collaboration, and co-design to produce high quality learning resources. I like to make my SME look good. But there have been obstacles in my path: mostly SMEs, supervisors, and other leaders who don't seem to get it. Now, either they don't know any better, which is a problem, or – for other reasons – make terrible, short-sighted decisions. Which is also a problem. In well-designed systems, learning designers are acknowledged and supported. But in dysfunctional systems, we're often rendered invisible, treated as IT support or administrative staff. This misunderstanding leads to a lack of collaboration and respect, where SMEs (and leaders) may resist pedagogical and technical advice or avoid engaging with learning design altogether. Worse still, some of these leaders have had limited professional experience in learning, teaching and education.

A bit of an aside about gatekeeping, which is, in everyday language when someone controls or limits access to information, resources, or opportunities that others need. It's like when one person

holds the keys to a door and decides who gets to come in or stay out. This can make things harder for others who want to contribute or move forward.

For example, in a workplace, it might be someone who decides who gets to attend certain meetings or have access to important documents, even though others could benefit from them. It's a way of keeping control over something that could be shared more freely.

As a learning designer I've faced marginalization, where I wasn't included in curriculum meetings or invited to contribute at a strategic level, even though my educational technology expertise was crucial.

To summarise these experiences, I wrote down more than a few of my colourful workplace stories and anecdotes. The presentation was starting to feel like a rambling outline for a twelve-episode Netflix drama. And it sounded a bit irritable. So instead of sharing these horror stories with you here today, I removed them from my presentation and copied them into ChatGPT with instructions to analyse. This revealed themes of marginalisation, misunderstanding, lack of collaboration, disrespect for expertise, unsustainable workloads, and power imbalances. The AI also provided recommendations: raising awareness of the role, clarifying responsibilities, creating structured collaboration, advocating for representation, and fostering professional development.

I've worked with lots of SMEs, both good and bad. I once got into a power struggle in a staff tearoom with an English teacher, all because poetry was in her teaching domain and supposedly not in mine. So, here is a poem.

The co-design path

(with apologies to Robert Frost)

In learning's craft, it's crystal clear,
No one builds it alone, my dear.
A team of pros, with wisdom wide,
Each plays their part with steady pride.

The SME, a guiding light,
Sharpens each lesson to fit just right.
From firefighters to surgeons skilled,
Their expertise our content fills.

To slice an onion, thin and sweet?
A chef's advice makes it complete.
But chickens, friends, I cannot charm—
I am not a chicken farmer!

For firefighting tactics bold,
Or legal cases tightly told,
A lawyer shares what they best know,
While scientists make learning grow.

Reputation risk? A school's top task—
Public relations experts we must ask.

In every field, I seek their hand,
To co-design and make it grand.

Beyond their knowledge, something more:
Trust and teamwork at the core.
Together we create what's best,
Respect and collaboration—our true test.

Conclusion

So, what am I working on right now, in terms of learning design? Well, I have a few casual roles happening, collaborating with some very pleasant SMEs. This suits me well. My recent role in facilitating online Live Sessions for the University of Technology, Sydney (UTS) in the Graduate Certificate in Learning Design (and its micro-credential equivalent) has been very constructivist and profoundly and professionally satisfying and enjoyable. My career is closer to its end than its beginning. Over the past 30 years as an educational resource developer, I've navigated diverse sectors and witnessed the evolving role of learning design. Even those less-than-optimal experiences have taught me some valuable lessons and provided me with some stories to tell. (I'm happy to share these, but not right now.) Whether called Instructional Designer, Educational Technologist, or Learning Experience Designer, the role remains crucial yet misunderstood. Systems that trust respect and recognise learning designers lead to better outcomes for everyone.

To close, I'll quote Dr. Norman Swan: "Work becomes oppressive when it feels relentless, unrecognized, badly managed, and the system doesn't allow you to do your best." My hope is that this presentation sparks further reflection and action to elevate the role of learning design.

Best wishes and farewell—see you in the evaluation phase.

Provocation

As with most provocations in academic contexts, this video is designed to challenge established ideas and spark critical debate. It's been developed to inform, entertain and push you out of your comfort zone, encourage you to think differently, reconsider your assumptions, and explore new perspectives.

3SS participants considered the video via the following prompts and a positive and constructive discussion ensued.

Discussion prompts

- Reflect on your own experiences in learning design, and as a "third space practitioner". Have you ever felt your role was invisible? How did you handle that?
- Think about systems or teams where learning designers are undervalued. What small changes could shift the perception?
- Share challenges and obstacles you've faced in co-designing with SMEs and how you overcame them.
- Share examples from your experience of positive collaborations with SMEs or other team members. What factors contributed to that success?

Reflection

November 2025

I'd like to offer a brief personal and professional reflection a year after the 3SS. Over the past 30 or so years, I've had an enjoyable career as a "producer of learning materials" or learning designer. (What's in a label? That which we call a "Learning Designer" by any other name would perform a similar set of tasks: the essence or value of something isn't necessarily altered by what we choose to call it.) Regarding the 3SS, I appreciated the opportunity to participate and share my thoughts, perspectives and learnings in the unexpected liminal "third space" of the 100% online "Slowposium". I'm advised that the 3SS was not intended as a research activity, yet I'm pleased the organising committee are able to document and disseminate the ideas presented by the contributors. Due to established protocols in the field, any participant comments or quotes in response to my presentation – also called "participant data" – cannot be used in the proceedings. This I understand and respect.

Central to my presentation (that is, apart from my professional identity and the Australian poultry production industry) is a fundamental idea around professional and collegial acknowledgement and the value of dialogue for professional growth, shared understanding, respect, trust and collaboration. My experience with 3SS was valuable. As a learning designer, I had a voice in this space. I felt acknowledged, seen and heard, especially when interacting with comments and responses in the online discussion forum that was associated with my presentation, reaching its full value with each forum post and reply, either from myself or from other participants who were enabled to speak and be heard. Messages sent and received.

My presentation yielded several responses and comments from others who attended the 3SS. (I'm unable to quantify this; it's enough to acknowledge a professional and collegial resonance with the ideas.) Further sharing my video presentation on additional social platforms – after the event, outside the 3SS Moodle site – attracted similar interest and discourse. (Again, these are outside the scope of the proceedings.)

In this collegial exchange and interchange, collective wisdom is realised. I look forward to reading the 3SS proceedings and continuing the conversation.

About the author

Mark Parry

University of Technology Sydney; Western Sydney University

Educational developer; learning designer; lecturer for UTS Graduate Certificate in Learning Design

<https://parryville.com.au/>

Explore a new framework to evolve third space relationships

Natalia Veles and Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845319>

Higher education research demonstrates the increasing relevance of the university third space metaphor to describe how people work together while crossing, disrupting, and transcending the boundaries of their respective roles and identities, thereby challenging the confines of organisational structure. Third-space working is characterised by diverse thinking, co-creating new practices, and challenging outdated systems and processes. It is often a space of professional tensions that working across boundaries inevitably produces.

Whether you navigate a professional/academic identity, work across the central organisational command centre or in a faculty, or experience tension at the intersection of teaching and research activities – you may be experiencing the “third space effect”.

This one-hour interactive session in the Slowposium aimed to challenge participants’ perceptions and inspire their third-space imaginations by presenting a four-phase framework for the evolution of professional interaction within changing boundary practices and identities. These phases combine work by Whitchurch (2012) and Veles (2023) which describe a practical pathway for re-imagining third space relationships, from Contestation to Reconciliation to Reconstruction and finally to Transformation.

In the second part of the session, participants applied this framework to real-world third-space scenarios, looking for new and desired futures. Participants were invited to engage in collective critical reflection about how the combination of third-space working, boundary learning and the collaborative capital of relationships and recognition of people’s contributions can be applied to and can shape contemporary and emerging university practices.

The session was conducted via Zoom and the recording of the session is available on YouTube [https://youtu.be/v8RE6_jX7bM]

Presentation

Four phases of interaction: how university staff work and learn in third spaces

Natalia Veles, PhD
James Cook University, Queensland, Australia

Colin Simpson, SFHEA
ASCILITE TEledvisors Network & University of Sydney

Overview of the presentation

1. Introductions (5)
2. Acknowledgement of the foundational work on university third space and third space professionalism (Whitchurch, 2008, 2012, 2018, 2023) and more recent developments (5)
3. The dynamics of third space - original framework (Whitchurch, 2010) and advancing from three to four phases (Veles, 2023) (10)
4. A case study from Veles's (2023) published research (10)
5. Interactive activity applying the principles (15)
6. Reporting back (10)
7. Conclusion (5)

2

the "emergence of broadly based, extended projects across the university, which are no longer containable within firm boundaries, and have created new portfolios of activity."

Whitchurch (2015, 2022)

SRHE

Carina Basso
Natalie Brown, Editors

The Impact of the Integrated Practitioner in Higher Education
Studies in Blended Professionalism

Edited by Emily McInerney and Diane Watt

OPTIMISING THE THIRD SPACE IN HIGHER EDUCATION
CASE STUDIES OF INTERDISCIPLINARY AND CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

Natalia Veles

The Learning Development Project

Revisiting and advancing the university third space scholarship

UCLPRESS LONDON REVIEW OF EDUCATION

Third space roles and identities in educational settings

3

The dynamics of third space - advancing the framework of interactions from three to four phases

The image shows two book covers. On the left is 'Reconstructing Identities in Higher Education: THE RISE OF THIRD SPACE PROFESSIONALS' by Celia Whitchurch, published by SRHE. On the right is 'OPTIMISING THE THIRD SPACE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: CASE STUDIES OF INTERCULTURAL AND CROSS-BOUNDARY COLLABORATION' by Natalia Veles, published by Knowledge Research in Higher Education. A large pink arrow points from the left book to the right book.

Explored university activities (Whitchurch's research - 2010 and 2013 publications)

The diagram consists of seven pink rectangular boxes arranged in two rows. The top row contains four boxes: 'Programme development', 'Widening participation', 'Community and business partnership', and 'Professional and academic practice'. The bottom row contains three boxes: 'Learning support', 'Institutional planning', and 'Communications and public relations'.

The framework of interactions - three distinct processes or phases (Whitchurch's research)

- ❖ *Contestation*
- ❖ *Reconciliation*
- ❖ *Reconstruction*

The image shows a photograph of three objects on a white surface: a white rectangular block, a white ring, and a light blue ring. To the right of the photograph is a list of three items, each preceded by a diamond symbol (❖).

Framework of interactions - CONTESTATION

- ❖ **Operational issues:** navigating operational challenges and processes associated with different ways and paces of working among academic and entrepreneurial approaches.
- ❖ **Contractual nature:** the clear, goal-oriented nature of privately funded work versus the more open-ended nature of academic projects.
- ❖ **Political issues:** the negotiations and political dynamics involved in public/private collaborations.
- ❖ **Perceptions of work:** various activities crossing public/private spaces are seen as “trade” or “dirty” work by some.
- ❖ **‘Resistance and struggle’** (Whitchurch, 2013, p. 26): common academic frustrations, such as management requirements and resource constraints; proliferation of the sense of ‘otherness’ and lack of understanding of one another and their respective work.

7

Framework of interactions - RECONCILIATION

- ❖ **Potential of collaboration:** Encourages joint efforts between parties for mutual benefit.
- ❖ **Perceived added value:** Promotes initiatives that wouldn’t occur otherwise.
- ❖ **Ideological and material outcomes:** Aims to raise aspirations and improve opportunities.
- ❖ **Negotiation of differences:** Facilitates new identities and collaboration.
- ❖ **Dynamic in-between space:** Allows for innovative and unexpected activities.
- ❖ **Cultural translation:** Creates a safer space for new activities and relationships.
- ❖ **Critical exchange:** Restructures binary choices to open new alternatives.

8

Framework of interactions - RECONSTRUCTION

- ❖ **Interaction and respect among academic colleagues.**
- ❖ **Freedom to produce appropriate solutions.**
- ❖ **Creation of the new “rules and resources” and setting up new structures of authority.**
- ❖ **This pluralistic environment is defined by terms like ‘partnership’, ‘capital building’, ‘networking’, and ‘creativity’.**
- ❖ **Individuals contribute to forming new plural spaces and developing new identities.**
- ❖ **Investment in both strong and weak ties with key individuals and networks is crucial.**
- ❖ **Institutional and professional growth opportunities mitigate the frustrations of the Contestation process.**

9

Framework of interactions - SUMMARY

- ◊ The processes of Contestation, Reconciliation, and Reconstruction are interconnected.
- ◊ They can occur simultaneously, representing different stages in the development of activities and identities.
- ◊ Individuals may align with one process or display characteristics of multiple processes based on circumstances.
- ◊ These processes help describe the complex and multi-dimensional nature of working in third space environments highlighting both ideological commitment and disenchantment among individuals.

10

University staff in collaborative third space environments - "Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration" (Veles, 2023)

The alignment of the five third space projects and the core activity domains of teaching and learning, research and engagement

(developed from Whitchurch's [2008] university third space typology)

TUA = Tropical University, Australia
TUS = Tropical University, Singapore

11

Case study example

The university project of entrepreneurial collaboration among three key actors:

- ◊ a scientist (the Academic)
- ◊ a technical solutions manager (the Innovator)
- ◊ a Research Business Manager (the Business Manager).

Veles, N. (2024). Critical thirding and third space collaboration: University professional staff and new type of knowledge production. *London Review of Education*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.22.1.24>

Veles, N. (2022). *Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003259527>

12

Extended framework of the dynamics of third space - TRANSFORMATION

- ◊ Learning at the boundaries must occur.
- ◊ Dialogical interaction and collaborative capital creation are involved.
- ◊ Three levels of transformation: can occur on institutional, interpersonal, intrapersonal, or on all three, levels.
- ◊ The integration of individual worldviews, perspectives, and personal and professional discoveries.
- ◊ Lasting transformation of processes and practices

13

Extended framework of the dynamics of third space - Four Phases (Whitchurch's and Veles's research)

- ❖ Contestation
- ❖ Reconciliation
- ❖ Reconstruction
- ❖ Transformation

14

Activity: Applying the principles in the workplace

Your university has decided to embark upon a major curriculum renewal project. This will involve an ongoing collaboration between academics in the history school and a group of academic developers, learning designers and educational technologists (collectively EdAdvisors).

The academics are sceptical of this project and question whether the EdAdvisors adequately understand what they are teaching and how they teach to make a useful contribution. They feel that if the EdAdvisors are to be helpful, they need to think and act much more like academics. This is the first time they have not had complete control of their curriculum process.

The EdAdvisors have reviewed the past courses and teaching feedback for the subjects involved and have some ideas for what might be changed, from a pedagogical and technological standpoint.

In breakout groups, what actions, based on what we have learned, might be used to move from contestation to reconciliation?

- By learning & teaching leaders?
- By academics
- By EdAdvisors

16

Third space interactions - further provocations

“Third Space is...open, symbolic, playful, and generative. It can also be contested space if power differentials force confrontations between conceptual systems” and yet, “the possibilities of Third Space challenge us to reconsider our professional priorities and concepts.” (Elmborg, 2011, p. 345).

- How can individuals mobilise third-space learning and work to achieve genuine transformations?
- How will technology continue to shape third-space thinking and working across third-space environments?
- How could we, third space professionals, apply the knowledge of the phases of interaction productively and across various collaborative projects and activities?

17

Connect with us:

Natalia Veles:

email: natalia.veles@jcu.edu.au

linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/dr-natalia-veles-283316ab/>

Colin Simpson:

email: colin.simpson@sydney.edu.au

bluesky: @gamerlearner.bsky.social

blog: Screenface.net

18

Selected references

- Akkerman, S. F., & Bakker, A. (2011a). Boundary crossing and boundary objects. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(2), 132-169. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654311404435>
- Akkerman, S. F., & Bakker, A. (2011b). Learning at the boundary: An introduction. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2011.04.002>
- Akkerman, S.F., & Bruining, T. (2016). Multilevel boundary crossing in a professional development school partnership. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 25(2), 240-284. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2016.1147448>
- Bhabha, H. K. (1994). *The location of culture*. Routledge.
- Soja, E. (1996). *Thirdspace: Journeys to Los Angeles and other real-and-imagined places*. Blackwell.
- Veles, N. (2023). *Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003259527>
- Whitchurch, C. (2013). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of "Third Space" professionals*. Taylor and Francis.
- Whitchurch, C. (2010). Some implications of "public/private" space for professional identities in higher education, *Higher Education*, 60(6), 627-40.
- Whitchurch, C. & Law, P. (2010). *Optimising the potential of third space professionals in UK higher education*. Leadership Foundation for Higher Education.

The university third space is:

the “emergence of broadly based, extended projects across the university, which are no longer containable within firm boundaries, and have created new portfolios of activity.”

Whitchurch (2015, 2022)

20

The university third space further interpreted as:

“a relatively new approach that has intriguing implications for how work changes where clear professional boundaries dissolve”

Verbaan and Cox (2014)

21

References

- Veles, N. (2023). *Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003259527>
- Whitchurch, C. (2012). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of “third space” professionals*. Taylor and Francis.

About the authors

Natalia Veles

James Cook University

Academic Head, Career Development. RPCDP (Registered Professional Career Development Practitioner)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6010-2653>

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

.

Research

Developing a better understanding of the third space and the people that work in it

Research for all in the future university

Olivia Inwood

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845331>

In my presentation, I presented the utopian idea of the future university as a place where everyone can conduct research, and the small interventions I am currently making to encourage this idea. The concept of the third space encourages us to break down silos and think beyond job titles and realise how existing in ‘the blurred space’ or having a blurred work identity can actually allow for new perspectives and collaborations to foster.

My dream for the university is that everyone has a chance to do research or to simply have the opportunity to be reflective about their work: to think, read and write. Both academic (teaching-focused) and professional staff are often denied time to do this, particularly if their research might not translate to immediate monetary outputs. If we rethink the relations between the academic and professional staff worlds, and view research as a collaborative effort, we might find more opportunity for us all to engage in research in some way.

In my university, I’ve helped establish a community of practice (CoP) that was firstly focused on academic literacy resources; however, because we opened up this CoP to anyone in the university, creating a welcoming space, it unintentionally became a haven for third space staff, people who previously felt like they weren’t allowed to take part in ‘academic’ conversations despite having a lot of skills and knowledge to contribute. This has helped develop new collaborations, for example, between academic literacy and wellbeing staff, and enabled members to work with reflexivity and contribute to new spaces such as the University’s Teaching and Learning Showcase. Our CoP highlights how the development of inclusive and non-hierarchical spaces for staff in the university and the acknowledgement of blurred work identities can lead to exciting new collaborations and potential research endeavours.

About the author

Dr Olivia Inwood

Western Sydney University

Dr Olivia Inwood was previously an Academic Literacy Coordinator and is now a Learning Programs Manager at Western Sydney University Library.

[LinkedIn](#)

WSU [Researcher page](#)

Cover to cover: A thesis radio journey

Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845343>

I have been researching third space practitioners and the factors that impact their efficacy in Australian higher education since 2016 for my PhD. As this journey comes to an end, “listen” as I take you between the covers of my thesis and explore key ideas and findings, interspersed with some of my favourite musical cover versions. This one-hour show was initially “broadcast” as part of ALTC radio at the 2024 ALT conference in the UK. I used cover versions because scholarship is largely about building on what has come before and adding your own spin.

Engage

[Music plays] You are listening to ALTC Radio. I'm Colin Simpson, and the program is Cover to Cover. We just heard from Messerschups with their version of Wicked Game originally recorded by Chris Isaak a little while ago.

In the next hour, I'm going to share some of my favourite cover versions and also take you between the covers of my work in progress doctoral thesis. (It's getting close. It's getting close). I kind of like the analogy of the cover version to describe academic research. It's all about building on work that's come before but putting your own spin on things to hopefully create something new. I should probably tell you a little bit about myself before we get under the covers, so to speak.

I have worked in the tertiary education third space since 2003, both in vocational education and training and also higher education. Third space workers in tertiary education occupy roles which are neither academic nor entirely professional. They kind of transcend or cross or sit in between those barriers. And so, we're talking about things like learning design, educational technology, academic development, that kind of stuff. So, I've worked at the Canberra Institute of Technology, Australian National University, Monash University, Swinburne University, and I'm currently a senior learning designer at the University of Sydney.

I am also one of the leaders of the ASCILITE TELevisors Network, and we're a community of practitioners for people working in the tertiary education third space, we have been operating since 2017. We do webinars, have a fairly active discussion board and do what we can to support people in these kinds of roles.

Anyway, enough about me. Let's have another song. [Music plays] And that was the lovely Mary Jo Starr AKA Kaarin Fairfax, with her interpretation of the Hunters and Collectors classic 'Throw your arms around me'. You will not find that on Spotify. That was on a very small release called Used and Recovered by. It was a 3RRR Community Radio compilation.

Given the number of times that I've already mentioned the third space, you may not be surprised to hear that this is the subject of my PhD research. I've been doing this part-time at the University

of Sydney since 2016. Firstly, under Peter Goodyear and now under Lina Markauskaite. I first had the urge to do this after I started working in higher education in 2015 and realised that things were quite different for third space professional staff in higher ed than I'd sort of been experiencing in the vocational education sector. I was finding it a lot harder to get things done, and I kind of wanted to know why. So, as I explored the literature and went down a range of rabbit holes, I realised that a lot of what I was reading didn't really mesh with my own experiences.

There's some very good literature about the third space, but a lot of it just was incomplete. My first challenge was I wanted to talk about three roles collectively, so learning designers, educational technologists, and academic developers. And this was just not a term that existed in parallel to this. Some colleagues and I created the TELedvisors network, the community of practice that I mentioned before, and we coined the term edvisor, which I've kind of revised to EdAdvisor because people kept getting edvisor wrong, which is a portmanteau of educator and advisor. And I've landed on these four research questions.

1. Who are EdAdvisor in Australian higher education and what do they do?
2. How do our EdAdvisor contribute to better learning and teaching?
3. What are the enablers and inhibitors of EdAdvisor practices?
4. What actions can be taken to enhance EdAdvisor efficacy?

I'm not entirely sold on the wording of these questions, but it's pretty close. I think that will get me there.

Let's have another track. [Music plays] Right there we had The Slits, their interpretation of 'I heard it through the grapevine'.

So, let's continue with my little story about my doctoral research. I'm taking an abductive approach epistemologically, if you want to put it that way. Because this lets me be informed by theory but means that I'm not necessarily beholden to it.

I'm still able to see where the findings take me in terms of my theoretical frameworks. There are two you've probably guessed Third Space Theory is definitely one of those. There's different flavours of Third Space Theory. But obviously I'm looking at third space as it applies to higher education, which was largely popularised by Celia Whitchurch in the late two thousands, drawing on sociolinguistic theory from Homi Bhabha.

Whitchurch's work focuses on boundaries between academic and professional or administrative staff, and she puts people into one of four categories: bounded professionals, cross boundary professionals, unbounded professionals or blended professionals. The second theoretical lens that I'm using is practice theory and if there are, you know, a handful of flavours of Third Space Theory, there are a million versions of practice theory. I would kind of sum it up though, as "I do, therefore, I am". Now practice theory broadly is concerned with what we do and what that tells us about ourselves. The application that I'm most interested in is work done by Stephen Kemmis in, I guess, the 2010s who sort of breaks practice down into "doings", which is, well, the things that you're doing, "sayings", which is largely the understanding of why you might be doing something and "relatings", which are the interactions between the people involved in doings. Kemmis adds this idea of practice architectures, which are really important in the third space EdAdvisor world because that essentially involves creating the conditions for someone else's practice to occur.

So, using all of these elements, I'm basically exploring what it is that EdAdvisors are doing and the different areas of higher education that impact that.

Let's have another track. [Music plays]

Iggy pop there with his take on Johnny O'Keefe's. Australian rock and roll classic, Real wild child (Wild One).

So, when I'm talking about EdAdvisors. I am talking about people in three roles. Let me give you a very potted rundown on what I think are the distinguishing features of these. So academic developers are more likely to be people in academic positions, generally women obviously, you know, your mileage may vary. Some of the primary activities that academic developers are involved in are building capability, quality management of teaching – so, teaching evaluations, providing feedback peer review of teaching – and designing teaching and learning, which is kind of something that they do share with learning designers.

And this is probably more the curriculum side of design rather than the designing learning activities and resources. They'd also be involved in nurturing learning and teaching culture and research. This is probably one of the more distinguishing characteristics of academic developers largely because they get to hold academic roles.

The academic status of the academic developer is really important. It allows academics to feel that they're working with someone who actually understands their practices, their challenges, what they're going through, and most academic developers have reported that this just makes life a lot easier.

Moving on to educational technologists, you may also know them as learning technologists. People in this role are more likely to be male, which is against the norm for particularly people in professional staff positions in higher education. On a side note, I recognise that I'm talking to people at ALTC and the definition that I'm using for learning technologists or educational technologists seems to veer away a little bit from the ALT definition, which I would suggest actually kind of brings learning design into the equation far more than in the Australian experience. Educational technologists are largely there to facilitate educational technologies, so implementing, evaluating, procuring, working with vendors, all of that kind of stuff, making sure that academics and other people know how to use it appropriately. So, there is definitely a need for pedagogical knowledge, but it is largely seen as a technological role. ETs will also be involved in building learning activities and resources, putting things up into the learning management system, making multimedia assets, videos.

There is a tech support component. Even ed techs kind of get a little bit resentful about only being seen as the tech guy, but I think that that is actually a fairly common complaint among all EdAdvisors. And there is also a capability building component to the education technology role.

Finally, we've got learning designers. More likely to be women, definitely more likely to hold professional positions. As the name suggests, definitely involved in designing, teaching and learning. Probably more to do with designing learning activities, learning resources than curriculum. Definitely there to build capability, build learning and teaching resources.

And they do have or claim a role in facilitating education technology as well. This is probably because the learning designer role is much more of an all-rounder kind of role than either the AD or the ed tech kind of roles. Which means that sometimes they can feel that they're a little bit shut

out of things at the very pedagogical end of the spectrum or the very technological end of the spectrum.

And so, they're kind of the middle child of the EdAdvisor family.

Let's have another song. [Music plays] Welcome back. That was the Vividels, covering the classic Go-Betweens track Was there anything I could do?

Now I previously mentioned that my or the Australian view of Educational/Learning technologist varies a little from the UK definition which is probably important given that we are actually here at ALTC. The clarity of third space roles is widely regarded as one of our biggest challenges, both in terms of consistency of titles and also the role definitions. But why does this matter?

I think there are actually four major implications for having poorly defined and poorly understood roles. It means that it is harder for academics to find the right help, the help that they actually need, and if they find it, it makes it harder to trust the expertise of the person that they're working with. If they don't understand what the person is capable of or what their responsibilities are, then why should they trust them? Poorly defined roles also make it harder to hire good people. If I'm looking at, you know, LinkedIn or a job ad site or whatever, and I type in a particular search term, and for whatever reason the University of Warwick has listed someone as a technology specialist, LMS, I'm not going to find that role. Finally, leaders may not know how to appropriately use people working in these EdAdvisor third space roles.

Now these issues with clarity over, you know, role titles and role definitions are nothing new in my review of literature. I found an article from 1972 by Geis and Klaassen, where they were basically discussing whether educational technologists or instructional designer should be the term that is being used. And they did a review of all of the titles being used in their institutions. So yeah. This is, this is not a particularly new issue. I worked on a paper with some colleagues Kate Mitchell and Chie Adachi in 2017, where we looked at 37 job ads and we found 27 distinct titles for basically these three EdAdvisor roles that I've been exploring.

So, is this a solvable problem? Probably not. But I think it's definitely still worth exploring. And one of the things, one of the themes that's really emerged in the research that I've done is that the ambiguity is not always a bad thing. A lot of people noted that it creates a little bit more flexibility. There's a little bit more fluidity. You've got opportunities to do activities that might not necessarily be associated with your role because people don't always necessarily know what you should be doing. So yeah, there's, there's a balance that needs to be found. So, I think that's an interesting finding.

Let's have another song. [Music plays] Johnny Cash there from American Three with his take on Tom Petty's "I won't back down". I like this song because it embodies the main quality I have had to draw on as I've progressed through my PhD. Spite.

Now one factor, which has had a massive impact on the ability of third space practitioners to enable better learning and teaching is the divide between academic and professional staff in higher education. In my own research, my survey sample was 77% professional staff and 23% academic staff. The first thing worth noting is that when I asked survey respondents what factors they felt served as barriers to their work, 69% of the professional staff, but only 35% of academic staff, selected the academic professional divide, and that was statistically significant.

There were a few other statistics of note. I asked a series of questions about the extent to which people felt that their work was understood and valued by different stakeholders, academics, leaders, and people in other EdAdvisor roles. For the question about whether academics value their work, 71% of with a professional classification broadly agreed, but 57% of people with an academic classification broadly agreed. Also statistically significant. There are a couple of major themes that emerged from the interviews. One, which is probably no major surprise, is that there is a social status hierarchy between academic and professional staff and that having an academic role means that there is a sense of shared understanding with academics, which often makes life a little bit easier. Interestingly, the academic professional question was largely not seen as a barrier to relationships between people in EdAdvisor roles. We're all quite capable of happily getting along.

Let's have another track. [Music plays] Sharon Jones and the Dap Kings there with a song you may recognise from the soundtrack to The Big Lebowski. "Just dropped in (to see what condition my condition was in)". That was originally performed by Kenny Rogers and the First Edition, you're listening to ALTC Radio. I'm Colin Simpson playing covers and banging on about my doctoral research into third space professionals in Australian higher education.

One aspect of higher education, which plays an important part in the efficacy of EdAdvisors, or third space practitioners is the relationship between central areas of the university and the faculties or disciplinary areas, if you want to call them that. This plays an important part. In shaping the ability of these third space practitioners slash EdAdvisors to support better learning and teaching. In my sample, 62% of respondents worked in a central division. 29% reported working in a faculty unit, and 9% selected other. Now, there was no significant difference in the questions that I asked about if people feel that their work is understood or valued by different stakeholders, depending on whether they were central or faculty based, and there was no significant difference on the questions about their ability to contribute to decision-making on educational practices or educational technologies.

However, there are a lot of big feelings, generally speaking. About the relationship between central and faculties. Probably the key theme was that there were competing priorities and a power imbalance. The faculty people had a local focus. It was discipline based, and it was very much about learning and teaching, whereas people in the central area were perceived as being more focused on the big picture and having a whole of institution focus. And this is, you know, within responses from the interviewees as well as the common themes within the literature. And so these relationships can be quite fraught because there's a sense that central people will barge into faculty areas to try and impose one size fits all solutions and they're not interested in local initiatives.

And on both sides, there was basically a sense that there's a lack of understanding either of local needs or big picture needs. So there's definitely some challenges for us to work out in the relationships between central and faculty.

Let's have another song coming to the end of the show here on ALTC Radio. [Music plays] That was a version of a Robert Palmer song, Johnny and Mary by Norwegian DJ Todd Terje featuring Brian Ferry on vocals.

In between songs I've been discussing some of the factors which affect the work of third space practitioners in higher education. One final factor that has not received a lot of attention in the literature is the impact of organisational structures on EdAdvisors.

This includes whether units are centralised or decentralised, so there might be a single central unit, and members of that unit are embedded in faculty teams, or it might simply be all faculty teams with no central unit. Organisational restructures and instability was another big part of this theme. New structures can mean that you are working alongside new people or no longer working with your old colleagues.

New leaders inevitably bring new plans and projects, which can mean that something that you've worked on for months or years is simply abandoned. And of course, there's the very real risk of job losses, none of which is conducive to getting things done. Working with other stakeholders in the institution was also often regarded as a challenge, particularly when working with university IT departments to whom educational technologies are often just a small part of their overall portfolio

Time now for one more song, and this one is an original. [Music plays] And that one was "Everything is now" by a Melbourne artist, Jess Ribeiro. Thought I would slip an original track in among the covers to symbolise the original contribution that this research is meant to bring to the field. Something along those lines. This brings us to the end of my show here on ALTC Radio.

I'd like to thank Dom Pate for indulging me. I hope you've enjoyed the tunes and found my work of some interest. If you are a third space practitioner or have an interest in this area, I'd like to encourage you to consider getting involved in an event that I'm organising later in the year. The Third Space Symposium. This is an event in two parts. We're going to have a one day in person event on Sunday, the 1st of December. Now that will be at the University of Melbourne in Australia, so maybe that's a little bit of a stretch, but preceding that we are having a two week online asynchronous, "slowposium". Where we will be exploring all facets of third space experience, work challenges, and opportunities.

So you can find out some more information about that at thirdspacesymposium.com. That's all one word. And if you'd like to know more about my research on the third space or the TELedvisors Network or anything really, please look for me on socials. I'm Colin Simpson on LinkedIn and gamerlearner in other places.

About the author

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convener of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

Technology

The tools we use and the ways we use them

To trial or not to trial?

A Space Invaders' dilemma

Colleen Hodgins and Naomi Millgate

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845348>

In the vast galaxy of academic tech, third space practitioners are on a mission. Should we launch trials of new and emerging technologies in teaching and learning? Or are we invading others' space? What? Who? How? Where? When? Why? These are the questions fuelling our interactive journey.

Together, we explored sustainable strategies for trialling tech in the educational cosmos. Using tools like ThingLink and Padlet, participants mapped their experiences, shared ideas, and uncovered best practices for working with academics and other stakeholders.

We collected vital data, ensuring third space invaders can land in the academic realm for the greater good.

Ready to join the mission? (With thanks to ChatGPT for the space invader supporting words).

Provocation

Should we launch trials of new and emerging technologies in teaching and learning? Or are we invading others' space? What? Who? How? Where? When? Why?

Go to <https://www.thinglink.com/scene/1908399447096689317> to play (accessible version available)

 3rd Space invaders
Colleen · A year ago · 43 views

About the authors

Colleen Hodgins

CQUniversity

Senior Educational Developer

Naomi Millgate

CQUniversity

Senior Educational Developer, VET Futures

Uniting expertise

The integral partnership of educational designers and academics in navigating AI in education

Minh Huynh, Fran Van Den Berg, Osu Lilje, Liana Pozza, and Floris Van Ogtrop

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845357>

As an educational designer in the central Educational Innovation team, I [Minh] have collaborated with academic colleagues from the School of Life and Environmental Sciences. Our work has often crossed organisational boundaries and roles, but supporting AI in education presented a unique challenge. This new area required us to navigate changing AI and assessment policies at a central level while providing practical support to teachers and students.

This presentation explored the challenges and opportunities we encountered in integrating AI into education from a third space perspective. We discussed how we worked together within and across teams, between central and faculty units, and with academics, leaders, and others to foster a collaborative environment. Our goal was to share insights on enabling strong partnerships.

To facilitate a meaningful exchange of ideas, we shared a [video](#) highlighting our experiences and a discussion board for attendees to share their stories and ideas. This interactive space allowed participants to revisit and reflect on the discussions. We aimed to gather diverse perspectives on the use of AI in education and shared how we implemented an AI tool called [Cogniti](#) at the University of Sydney. Cogniti supports learning through various applications, including assessment feedback, role play, case studies, and as a Socratic tutor. Our innovations include a Cogniti AI assistant that [expands on marker feedback](#) and a student-facing AI assistant providing [feedback on scientific report](#) drafts

About the authors

Minh Huynh

The University of Sydney

Fran Van Den Berg

The University of Sydney

Osu Lilje

The University of Sydney

Liana Pozza

The University of Sydney

Floris Van Ogtrop

The University of Sydney

Associate professor

Workplace

The practicalities of being a third space practitioner

Uncontracted: Reimagining work and identity in higher education's third space

Joanne Caldwell

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845373>

Scan this code for a link to the podcast on Spotify.

Provocation

Given the ongoing shifts in professional identity and practice within higher education, the symposium provided an opportunity to critically consider the archaic structure of employment contracts in the sector. I proposed that there is scope to re-examine the traditional bifurcation between academic and professional services roles. Rather than maintaining distinct contracts for these groups, institutions might instead adopt a unified employment model in which roles are defined by job descriptions specifying tasks and responsibilities, thereby negating the need for categorical differentiation. While such a model presents clear challenges in the United Kingdom, particularly in relation to Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) reporting, Research Excellence Framework (REF) submissions, and other statutory requirements that currently necessitate definitional distinctions, the session focused deliberately on exploring possibilities rather than practicalities.

The discussion was grounded in a 2024 podcast (Caldwell, 2024a) that examined the notion of identity among professional services staff and its relationship to my own research in this area (Caldwell, 2021, 2022a, 2022b, 2024b). During the session, participants were invited to reflect on the perceived value of work undertaken by professional services and academic staff, and to consider the potential of a third space employment model.

Context: The Third Space Professional

The concept of the third space has been a topic of scholarly discussion for several decades. Bhabha (2004, p. 2) conceptualised it as “the overlap and displacement of domains of difference,” describing it as an in-between space that moves beyond singular or binary notions of identity. This third space provides “the terrain for elaborating strategies of selfhood” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 2), enabling the emergence of hybrid identities that challenge established norms. Within this liminal context, “new signs of identity, and innovative sites of collaboration and contestation” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 2) are made possible. Bhabha further contends that the third space disrupts cultural conventions by existing as “neither the one nor the other” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 37). However, for this form of hybridity to be legitimised, difference and otherness must first be acknowledged. This theoretical framing offers a useful lens for examining the shifting boundaries between academic and administrative roles within higher education.

In recent years, the limited body of literature addressing the identities of professional services staff has increasingly centred on the emergence of the third space professional. The notion of the third

space professional in higher education was developed through Whitchurch's extensive research, which identified a new category of hybrid staff who operate across the traditional academic and administrative divide (2004, 2006, 2008a, 2008b, 2009a, 2012, 2018).

The career trajectories of professional services staff are no longer characterised by linear progression. Instead, individuals now move fluidly across departments, undertake secondments, and pursue opportunities across institutions and the broader sector (Whitchurch, 2009b; Veles & Carter, 2016). Such transitions, while offering new opportunities, may also lead to a loss of professional identity and a sense of displacement, as individuals perceive themselves as not fully belonging to the academic or professional services domains (Whitchurch, 2009a; Veles & Carter, 2016; Akerman, 2020).

Over the past fifteen years, scholarly attention has shifted from examining the functions of professional services staff as a support mechanism for academics and institutions to exploring their evolving professional identities. Increasingly, professional services staff are recognised as a distinct and integral workforce, whose roles are becoming more fluid and blended rather than strictly delineated (Vere et al., 2024).

Rethinking contractual boundaries: The potential for institutional employment models

Participant responses revealed significant variation shaped by individual experience and institutional context. Many identified the perceived divide between academic and professional services staff as stemming not only from contractual distinctions but also from disparities in the visibility of their work. Reference was made to the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF) and REF as mechanisms that privilege visible, quantifiable outputs, as well as to HESA reporting practices, which capture data exclusively for academic staff. Participants argued that these structures render the work of professional services staff largely invisible, reinforcing their lack of recognition and sustaining expectations that they will continually assume additional responsibilities and initiatives.

Participants highlighted the persistent hierarchies and disparities within higher education employment structures. One noted that teaching-only contracts are frequently perceived as less prestigious than research-focused appointments, reflecting the ongoing prioritisation of visible research outputs. In contrast, many professional services and third space staff occupy highly specialised, senior, or research-active roles, contributing substantively to policy formulation, strategic initiatives, and the broader institutional direction. Participants emphasised the importance of recognising and making visible these contributions, observing that "contracts that recognise those who are developing skills across multiple areas could be beneficial."

A particularly salient theme concerned the absence of recognition of research and data generation undertaken by professional services staff. Categorising staff solely according to contractual type risks narrowing the perceived scope of expertise within the sector. Unlike academic staff, professional services staff typically lack workload models that explicitly allocate time for research, constraining their capacity to engage in scholarly activities. As one participant noted, "The idea of research time for third space professionals is such a crucial idea... I can provide some grant funding to third space professionals for research, but time is the limiting factor." Consequently, the

absence of dedicated research time often necessitates that professional services staff undertake research outside of contracted hours, a practice that can adversely impact their work–life balance. Participants argued that stronger collaboration between academic and professional services colleagues, alongside better integration of professional services-generated data within institutional research ecosystems, could yield valuable insights to inform policy and enhance both staff and student experiences. These findings align with Verney and Curtis (2025), who advocate institutional mechanisms to support professional services staff and dismantle cultural barriers.

Although developing a unified higher education contract presents significant structural and regulatory challenges, the discussion underscored that expanding opportunities for staff to work across traditional boundaries is both timely and necessary. Empowering professional services staff to engage in research and collaborative practice not only enhances their professional development but also enriches the collective knowledge base that underpins universities' educational mission.

Final reflections

Participating in the Third Space Symposium and engaging with its online content was a novel and enriching experience. Given the international scope of the symposium, it was initially uncertain whether a discussion focused on higher education contracts, particularly within a UK context, would resonate with all participants. Although the number of responses was limited, the insights provided were valuable in exploring perspectives on the notion of a third space and the concept of an institutional contract of work. The feedback also revealed the frustrations experienced by professional services staff regarding how they are perceived within the academy, alongside their strong desire for recognition of the breadth and depth of their contributions. Within the UK, stringent reporting requirements necessitate clear distinctions between professional groups in higher education. However, considering the sector's ongoing evolution, there is potential for future reconsideration of employment contract structures. I intend to pursue further research in this area to contribute to that discussion.

References

- Akerman, K. (2020). Invisible imposter: identity in institutions. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(4), 1–5.
- Bhabha, H. (2004). *The location of culture* (2nd ed.), Routledge.
- Caldwell, J. (2021). Perceptions of identity in higher education: Professional services and academic staff. EdD Thesis. Manchester Metropolitan University. <https://e-space.mmu.ac.uk/629210/>
- Caldwell, J. (2022a). Professional identity and professional services staff: understanding and impact. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 26(4), 1–8.
- Caldwell, J. (2022b). “People don’t understand what our role is, it is definitely seen as an inferior job to an academic”: Perceptions on relationships between professional services and academic staff in the UK. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 37(1), 24–35.
- Caldwell, J. (2024a). “Non-Academic”: Labelled by what you’re not. In *Knowledge Exchange: Deep-Dive*. <https://open.spotify.com/episode/30MtITFUxNBwdKrhLooHPK>

- Caldwell, J. (2024b). Nomenclature in higher education: “non-academic” as a construct. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 46(5), 507–522.
- Veles, N., & Carter, M.-A. (2016). Imagining a future: changing the landscape for third space professionals in Australian higher education institutions. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 38(5), 519–533.
- Vere, K., Verney, C., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2024). Crossing and dismantling boundaries: recognising the value of professional staff within higher education. *London Review of Education*, 22.1.9.
- Verney, C., & Curtis, H. J. (2025). Enabling an inclusive research culture for higher education professional services researchers. *Exchanges: The Warwick Research Journal*, 12(3), 50–71.
- Whitchurch, C. (2004). Administrative managers – a critical link. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 58(4), 280–298.
- Whitchurch, C. (2006). Who do they think they are? The changing identities of professional administrators and managers in UK higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 28(2), 159–171.
- Whitchurch, C. (2008a). Beyond administration and management: Reconstructing the identities of professional staff in UK higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 30(4), 375–386.
- Whitchurch, C. (2008b). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 377–396.
- Whitchurch, C. (2009a). Progressing professional careers in UK higher education. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 13(1), 3–10.
- Whitchurch, C. (2009b). The rise of the blended professional in higher education: a comparison between the United Kingdom, Australia and the United States. *Higher Education*, 58(3), 407–418.
- Whitchurch, C. (2012). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of ‘third space’ professionals*. Routledge.
- Whitchurch, C. (2018). Being a higher education professional today: Working in a third space. In C. Bossu & N. Brown (Eds.), *Professional and support staff in higher education* (pp. 11–21). Springer Nature.

About the author

Joanne Caldwell

Salford Business School

Dr Joanne Caldwell FAHEP FHEA is Joint Editor of *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education* and works as School Business Manager at Salford Business School, University of Salford. Her doctoral research explored the relationships of professional services staff with academic colleagues.

Navigating the ebbs and flows of change

Katie Freund, Karlene Dickens, and Fang Li

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845387>

Third space professionals are often responsible for promoting change in higher education, such as driving strategic education goals, redesigning curricula, or implementing new technologies. While being facilitators of change, third space professionals are also vulnerable to changes such as restructures and shifting strategic priorities, with little autonomy or agency due to the liminal position of these roles.

The fishbowl discussion for this Symposium session invited participants to speak on the panel or contribute online from across third space roles and institutions to provide a diverse range of perspectives. Topics included:

- how to maintain wellbeing, relationships, and community amid uncertainty in higher education
- the soft skills and emotional labour required to facilitate change with our key stakeholders, and
- strategies we can enact to manage the inward and outward stressors in this complex environment.

About the authors

Katie Freund

Australian National University

Dr Katharina Freund is the Technology-Enhanced Learning and Teaching (TELT) Manager for the ANU Medical School.

Karlene Dickens

Australian National University

Karlene Dickens is a Learning Designer in TELT.

Fang Li

Australian National University

Fang Li is a Learning Technologist in TELT.

Third space careers visualised

Emily McIntosh and Diane Nutt

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845397>

This 30-minute presentation recording is based on research involving qualitative questionnaires and semi-structured interviews with those identifying as third space professionals (TSPs) in the United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand.

Third Space Slowposium: Third Space Careers visualised

Introductions

Dr Emily McIntosh PFHEA NTF
Director of Student Success, University of the West of Scotland, UK

Dr Diane Nutt PFHEA
Higher Education Consultant, based in York, UK

McIntosh, E. and Nutt, D. (eds.) (2022) *The Integrated Practitioner in Higher Education: studies in third space professionalism*, Routledge

Blog: [Third Space Perspectives - Exploring Integrated Practice](#)

Watch on YouTube

This presentation showcases a variety of interesting visuals from the study, alongside some of the findings from the interviews, and explores the themes that came out in discussions that related to how participants visualised their career pathways in the third space in higher education. The presentation analyses these findings thematically, demonstrating some key insights into how TSPs describe and then navigate their career pathways in the academy.

About the research: To encourage reflection in the survey and interviews, participants were asked to select and submit up to two images that best described their work in the third space (to the survey), and to visualise their career journey. The images and visualisation were discussed in the participant interviews.

About the authors

<https://www.thirdspaceperspectives.com/>

Emily McIntosh

Harper Adams University

Dr McIntosh is Chief Student Officer (CSO), a Principal Fellow (PFHEA) and a National Teaching Fellow.

Diane Nutt

Freelance

Diane is a Higher Education consultant and a Principal Fellow (PFHEA).

(Re)imagining the future of faculty PD

Alexandra Mihai and Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845413>

How can we (re)imagine the future of faculty professional development where meaningful work takes place across functional boundaries? How can we intentionally build the common ground necessary for effective and comprehensive faculty development?

Alexandra's research into Centres for Teaching and Learning in the US and Europe has revealed a variety of patterns for the relation between CTLs and educational technology teams (with their various names and identities). This workshop drew on this research and kicked off with a short presentation outlining the most relevant models encountered. Participants then worked in small groups on exploring various scenarios aimed at developing strategies for enhancing internal coherence as well as the impact on the teaching quality and student experience at the respective institution.

The subsequent plenary discussion aimed to bring together the strategies linked to the different models and enable participants to better understand what is necessary to make the work of these teams – merged, separate or collaborating – effective given the specific institutional context.

This workshop was targeted towards professionals working in staff development, both on the technology and pedagogy side (in or outside CTLs), as well as representatives of university management in charge of faculty professional development and/ or educational technology implementation.

(We conducted this workshop in one synchronous session (90 minutes), but an alternative could be a blended session, starting with asynchronous work and discussions and culminating with the synchronous part.)

Suggested reading

Beckley, T. (2022). How do higher education teaching and learning centers contribute to an institutional culture of assessment? [Doctor of Education, West Virginia University]. *Graduate Theses, Dissertations, and Problem Reports*. 11234. <https://doi.org/10.33915/etd.11234>

Belt, E. S., Menendez, B., & Cestone, C. M. (2024). Center for teaching and learning websites as online faculty development: A framework. *To Improve the Academy: A Journal of Educational Development*, 43(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.3998/tia.3311>

Czerniewicz, L. (2021). *Changing centres of teaching and learning: An analytical review* [Report]. OpenUCT (University of Cape Town). <https://open.uct.ac.za/handle/11427/33848>

- Drysdale, J. (2018). *The organizational structures of instructional design teams in higher education: A multiple case study* [Doctoral dissertation, Abilene Christian University].
<https://digitalcommons.acu.edu/etd/115/>
- Drysdale, J. (2021). The story is in the structure: A multi-case study of instructional design teams. *Online Learning*, 25(3), 57–80.
- Hayward, D., Baumgarthuber, C., Wright, M. C., & Kim, J. J. (2024). Developing theories of change to advance center for teaching and learning work. *To Improve the Academy: A Journal of Educational Development*, 43(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.3998/tia.3442>
- Holt, D., Palmer, S., & Challis, D. (2011). Changing perspectives: Teaching and learning centres' strategic contributions to academic development in Australian higher education. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 16(1), 5–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2011.546211>
- Lotti, A., Serbati, A., Doria, B., Picasso, F., & Felisatti, E. (2022). Teaching and learning centre: Analysis of key elements. *Formazione & Insegnamento*, 20(2), Article 2.
https://doi.org/10.7346/-fei-XX-02-22_06
- Neisler, O. J. (Ed.). (2023). *The Palgrave handbook of academic professional development centers*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80967-6>
- Palmer, S., Holt, D., & Challis, D. (2010). Australian teaching and learning centres through the eyes of their directors: Characteristics, capacities and constraints. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 32(2), 159–172.
- Wright, M. C. (2023). *Centers for teaching and learning: The new landscape in higher education*. Johns Hopkins University Press.

About the authors

Alexandra Mihai

Maastricht University

Assistant Professor- Innovation in Higher Education

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>

From third space to shared space

A speculative renovation of university role architecture

Miriam Reynoldson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845419>

The “third space” refers not to a spatial environment with physical boundaries, but to an imagined location for university work that resists traditional categorisation. Celia Whitchurch (2008) proposed “space” as a metaphor to help us situate practices that otherwise don’t belong within the (also metaphorical) bounds of academic or professional work.

This simple thought experiment took the space metaphor and used it as a basis for speculatively renovating the architecture of work roles in the university. It drew on theoretical work in social science and architecture, and from emerging speculative approaches to inquiry. Speculative methods enable us to contemplate “conditions which may not yet currently exist, to provoke new ways of thinking and to bring particular ideas or issues into focus” (Ross, 2017, p. 215).

Speculative fiction has previously been used to great effect in third space research. Costello et al. (2022) use it to generate profiles of imaginary learning design “superheroes”.

This event took place in two ways: first, as a collaborative mural that participants could add to throughout the asynchronous slowposium, and second as a live presentation during the symposium itself.

Part 1: The Slowposium mural

An online mural hosted on Miro was open for participant contributions over the two weeks of the slowposium. Participants were invited to visualise the “third space” as a material environment, somehow existing in between or alongside the “first” and “second spaces of academic and professional work. They were asked to imagine:

What if there were no boundary between academic or professional work? What if, instead of seeking definition for a liminal third space, we could inhabit a single shared space?

Step 1: Illustrate the third space based on their experience of it.

Participants depicted their own metaphor of the space in relation to the supposed “first” and “second” spaces. Where are the boundaries and/or intersections? Where would your own work take place? Can you see into or enter other spaces? Why did you picture the space this way?

For example:

Figure 1. Towers and tunnels

Source: © M. Reynoldson, used with permission

Academic work (the medieval tower in Figure 1) is prestigious but archaic, seeming out of touch with the modern world. Professional work (the skyscraper) provides the contemporary business sensibilities that enable academia to turn a profit.

The third space is an underground tunnel between the spaces, where covert collaborations happen. Without these collaborations, neither academic nor professional work could succeed – but they deliberately take place out of view.

Step 2: Renovate the space.

Participants chose one of the illustrations depicted in the first step, and considered: how could this space be altered (now or in the past) to enable any type of university work to happen across spaces?

Participants speculatively altered the dimensions of this space, removing the limits to enable free movement throughout. This took forms like:

- breaking down boundaries
- removal of partition walls
- addition of windows and doors
- construction of a bridge
- a complete demolition making way for a new shared space.

For example:

Figure 2. Tower renovation plan

Source: © M. Reynoldson, used with permission

Remove the secret tunnel and install ramps, stairways, elevators, slides and ladders between the two spaces, enabling various forms of practical and playful movement between them (Figure 2).

Step 3: Reflect on the feeling of this new shared space.

Participants considered: how might inhabiting it make us feel? What kind of atmosphere might it evoke? What are the potential issues and consequences of the changes – for example:

Who benefits?

What new problems are created?

What would roles look like?

What would work look like?

What might be gained or lost?

Part 2: The symposium presentation

During the symposium itself, I spoke a little more about the ideas behind this speculative project:

You don't go to a third space to do your work. You go to an academic space or a professional space, and you try to fit. But you're always a few toes out of line. You're not home. You do what you can, and then you move into the other space, and it's the same. You're needed, but maybe you're not quite recognised. You're still not home.

As Lakoff and Johnson (1981) famously argued, the metaphors we use shape our understandings of the world around us and the options for action we believe are available to us. For this reason, metaphor can help us speculate on possibilities for change. It is also a way of temporarily disconnecting us from the admin and technicalities of the empirical world.

I wanted to reflect on that metaphor of “space” using the concept of social topologies (Law & Singleton, 2005; Mol & Law, 1994) to suggest a few ways of conceptualising this social construct of work-as-space. These are each potential ways of reimagining the space we currently picture as made up of distances, regions and boundaries. In brief:

- when we think of social space as networked, instead of distance and borders separating us, we’re concerned with who we are connected to and who are aren’t
- when we think of social space as fluid, we think of shifting relationships, borders melting and moving, every part of the space being moved by every other
- when we think of fire space, we think of dynamics that can change instantly, without seeming to move at all.

Fire spaces, flickering rapidly between states of presence and absence, are particularly resonant for those of us operating in digitally mediated university spaces (Gravett et al., 2023). Metaphors like these enable us to visualise social configurations and relationships in their complexity, ambiguity and continuous evolution.

These metaphors are useful insofar as they help us think about social dynamics as a “where”. One of the most obvious examples of networked space is the organisational chart, which maps out where everyone sits in a company, indicating the power structures, the connections between teams, the dotted lines that tell you someone serves two masters. But this is exactly the kind of model that creates binaries and discomfort for those whose work doesn’t fit in (or under) a box. Networked space with its nodes and links is too tidy, too theoretically comfortable, to really describe the shiftingness of the atmosphere we’re trying to describe.

I also wanted to draw on the notion of “affective atmospheres” to contemplate the experience of inhabiting metaphorical spaces. Atmospheres emerge through the assembling of bodies in a space, but cannot be reduced to the simple addition of the former to the latter (Anderson, 2009; Bille et al, 2015). Architectural theory understands atmosphere as a quality linked to how built environments are designed and experienced by those who inhabit them (Sumartojo & Pink, 2018). A medieval church, a marbled hotel lobby, a cramped bedsit each evoke particular feelings in us when we enter them.

I offered a few illustrations of my own as suggestions for how a third space might manifest in fluid, networked and fire topologies.

Figure 3. *Third space bubbles in a beaker separating academic from professional fluids*

Source: © M. Reynoldson, used with permission

In the beaker (Figure 3), I imagined academic and professional spaces as something like oil and water: theoretically incompatible, but when they are thrown together, capsules of fluid are formed that might be substantively one, yet enveloped in the other and floating between the two, eventually—inevitably—to be subsumed by the element that dominates.

Figure 4. *A third space elevator moving between professional and academic floors*

Source: © M. Reynoldson, used with permission

In the building (Figure 4), I pictured the third space as the shaft of a lift that moves between allocated floors. It's not a habitable environment—rather, it's a utility space, a transport zone, designed specifically for people that need to be somewhere else.

Figure 5. A dialogue box appears inviting us to enter a third space in our browser

Source: © M. Reynoldson, used with permission

When I think of fire space, the first thing that comes to mind is the computer screen (Figure 5). I think of tabs, dialog boxes: things that jump into existence on our monitors, and just as instantly disappear as we choose “ok” or “cancel”. I think of the kind of code-switching work that people must do invisibly when navigating multiple cultures, constantly watching for cues that tell them which version of themselves to be today.

What I really wanted to ask was this: what kind of materials are we actually trying to play with when we think about the architecture of third space? Spaces, their materials, their shapes, and their inhabitants, create affective atmospheres which are shared and which affect who and how we are within them. How do such imaginaries make us feel about the spaces we inhabit and move between? What new imaginaries might we create – and how might we shape them in ways that support our work, each other, and ourselves?

References

- Anderson, B. (2009). Affective atmospheres. *Emotion, Space and Society*, 2(2), 77-81.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2009.08.005>
- Bille, M., Bjerregaard, P., & Sørensen, T. F. (2015). Staging atmospheres: Materiality, culture, and the texture of the in-between. *Emotion, Space and Society*, 15(1), 31-38.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2014.11.002>

- Costello, E., Welsh, S., Girme, P., Concannon, F., Farrelly, T., & Thompson, C. (2022). Who cares about learning design? Near future superheroes and villains of an educational ethics of care. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 48(3), 460-475. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2022.2074452>
- Gravett, K., Ajlawi, R., & O'Shea, S. (2023). Topologies of belonging in the digital university. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 33(2), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2023.2256342>
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1981). *Metaphors we live by*. University of Chicago Press.
- Law, J., & Singleton, V. (2005). Object lessons. *Organization*, 12(3), 331-355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350508405051270>
- Mol, A., & Law, J. (1994). Regions, networks and fluids: Anaemia and social topology. *Social Studies of Science*, 24(4), 641-671. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631279402400402>
- Ross, J. (2017). Speculative method in digital education research. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 42(2), 214-229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2016.1160927>
- Sumartojo, S., & Pink, S. (2018). *Atmospheres and the experiential world: Theory and methods*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315281254>
- Whitchurch, C. (2008). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 319-436. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2008.00387.x>

About the author

Miriam Reynoldson

RMIT University Social Equity Research Centre

Miriam is a digital learning specialist, teacher and PhD candidate. Her research explores the value of learning in digital ubiquity.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6022-7739>

[LinkedIn](#)

Speculative future university 2050

Carmen Vallis and Wendy Taleo

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845430>

Speculating and imagining more hopeful learning futures can spark change (Houlden & Veletsianos, 2023). With academic–professional boundaries blurring and third space practitioner (TSP) roles such as learning designers, academic developers and education designers becoming more fluid and dynamic (Whitchurch, 2018), speculative activities offer TSPs ways to play with possible futures and anticipate and lean into how their roles might evolve.

In this activity, we invited TSPs to explore speculative future scenarios in higher education. This online, asynchronous activity invited participants to imagine how higher education institutions (HEIs) might change and/or stay the same from a TSP point of view. Through the looking glass of a shared whiteboard space, participants speculated on potential new roles for TSPs such as near-future learning designers (Costello et al., 2022), joys and frustrations, and anticipating challenges and new directions for education.

The task

Imagine you are transported to the year 2050. How would your role change? Where would you be working? What are the joys and frustrations of TSPs in this future? To capture these speculations, an online whiteboard space offered three provocations.

Provocations for the future

We seeded the online whiteboards with our own provocations.

Provocation 1: Future university?

Our first speculation about the “Future University” prompted the most conversation and reaction. AI-generated images were uploaded for comment and deconstruction.

Microsoft Copilot’s sleek, corporate-utopian campus (Figure 1) is an unsettling classroom scene featuring sensory manipulation technology and students with raised hands in what feels more like operant conditioning and Audrey Watters’ “teaching machines” than education. The image shows there is clearly more work to be done to imagine educational futures that both embrace technology and avoid its potentially dehumanising and negative environmental aspects.

Figure 1

Another AI-generated image shared (Figure 2) depicts a sleek, futuristic university campus with flowing organic architecture, extensive green spaces and gardens, holographic displays, and autonomous vehicles, representing another corporate vision of 2050 education where advanced technology is seamlessly integrated with environmental sustainability in a polished, optimised setting. Green spaces may well be essential for both environmental cooling and psychological grounding in a tech-heavy 2050 university. There was a sense that the gardens we need in 2050 need cultivating today.

Figure 2

Provocation 2: How does technology impact your work? Potential joys or frustrations?

Our second provocation for 2050 third spacers was: How does technology impact your work? AI's role in transforming instructional design? The facilitators of this speculation reflected on the

pragmatic approach of using technology to amplify rather than replace human expertise in educational design. Human skills may become more valuable as technology handles routine tasks, although we retain healthy scepticism about ensuring quality outcomes and educational purpose.

The aspects of joy and frustrations were also part of this provocation. Third spacers currently struggle with workload and professional recognition in higher education is a volatile space. Now and into the future these aspects can be seen as causing much frustration and disruption.

Provocation 3: What is the student experience in 2050?

The future student experience could become globally networked and hyper-personalised, with learners curating credentials from any institution worldwide. We are seeing a messy future despite AI's smooth promises.

Reflection

Would we do it again? We found the speculation an interesting exercise. Including synchronous sessions and real-time interaction could potentially extend the speculation. Experimenting more with the process and the duration of the workshop, to allow time for the development of personas, might help reflect more hopes and anxieties about education and student experience in 2050.

References

- Costello, E., Welsh, S., Girme, P., Concannon, F., Farrelly, T., & Thompson, C. (2023). Who cares about learning design? Near future superheroes and villains of an educational ethics of care. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 48(3), 460–475.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2022.2074452>
- Houlden, S., & Veletsianos, G. (2023). Impossible dreaming: On speculative education fiction and hopeful learning futures. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 5(3), 605–622.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-022-00348-7>
- Watters, A. (2023). *Teaching machines: The history of personalized learning*. MIT Press.
- Whitchurch, C. (2018). Being a higher education professional today: Working in a third space. In C. Bossu & N. Brown (Eds.), *Professional and support staff in higher education* (pp. 11–21). Springer Nature.

About the authors

Carmen Vallis

The University of Sydney

Carmen Vallis is a Senior Lecturer (Educational Development) who likes designing for learning, engaging with technology, and writing and thinking creatively.

Wendy Taleo

Flinders University

Wendy is a convenor of the TELedvisors network and an enthusiastic education designer, technologist and poet.

Appendices

List of Slowposium sessions

Third Space Slowposium sessions: Asynchronous

1. I am not a chicken farmer: A learning designer's reflections on co-designing with academics

Mark Parry (Western Sydney University)

2. From third space to Shared Space: A speculative renovation of university role architecture

Miriam Reynoldson (University of Melbourne)

3. Epistemology of third space Professionals

Aaron Stoller (Colorado College)

4. Empowered OER – Explore this resource

Ash Barber (University of South Australia)

5. Negotiating third space identity through the process of writing it

Carina Buckley (Solent University), Alicja Syska (University of Plymouth)

6. 2050 Speculating third spacers

Carmen Vallis (University of Sydney), Wendy Taleo (Monash University)

7. Addressing AI literacy

Chelsy Hooper (Auburn University)

8. Abstracted selfie: Creating a persona for a third space professional

Claire Bowmer (Flinders University)

9. The best HE discipline (to work with)

Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

10. Untitled Ed Tech Game

Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

11. Building a third space practitioner research library

Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

12. Make your pitch: Let's solve the question of third space titles

Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

13. Sharing the oxygen mask: Collaboration so we can all breathe more easily

Cristy Bartlett, Kate Derrington (University of Southern Queensland)

14. Learning Designers: To define, or not define?

Dan Laurence, Meredith Hinze (University of Melbourne)

15. Navigating the 'third space': Insights from education design and development professionals

Diana Turnip, Meredith Macaulay, Ellie McDougall, Morgan Harris, Nasrin Danish, Swapneel Thite, Jon Xiating Cai, Zara Khan, Agnee Amarnath, Camile Moray, Neil Lawrence (University of New South Wales)

16. Standing out in the third space

Donna Murray (University of Edinburgh)

17. Learning for learning's sake in the third space

Craig J Bellamy

18. Building effective student-staff partnerships in the third space

Naima Iftikhar, Genevieve Bryant, Jared Fraser, Dasindu Suwarapola Liyanage, Banjo Akinyemi, Mohamed Al Ramahi, Matthew Elias (Western Sydney University)

19. Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of third space professionals: Reflections on lived experience

Dustin Hosseini (University of Glasgow)

20. Third space careers visualised

Emily McIntosh (University of the West of Scotland), Diane Nutt

21. The power of partnership: Embracing collaboration in the third space

Frances O Donnell (Atlantic Technological University)

22. Leading from the third space

Gosia Drewniok (University of Bristol)

23. The (in)visibility of librarians in the third space

Heidi Butters-Stabb (La Trobe University)

24. Co-creating in the third space with friends

Jane Kiddell, Stephanie Quirk (Deakin University)

25. The contested nature of teaching in the context of Canadian university continuing education

Jennifer MacDonald, Erin Careless (Dalhousie University)

26. What can learning design do? A case for theory before technology

Jeremy Stothers (Monash University)

27. Reflecting on educational design practice

Josephine Hook, Julie Luu, Prudence Perry, Frances Broomhead, Aster Cosmos, Yogita Ahuja, Brendan Boniface, Cathy Sell, Carmen Sapsed, Andrew Junor (Monash University)

28. Proposing a third space practitioner contract

Joanne Caldwell (Salford University)

29. Enhancing wellbeing and preventing burnout in the third space

Kate Casey (Keypath Education)

30. Capturing third space skills

Kate Mitchell (University of Melbourne), Keith Heggart (University of Technology Sydney), Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

31. (De)constructing the professional identities of third space practitioners through zine making

Kate Molloy (Atlantic Technological University)

32. Redefining learning outcomes: MOSAIC model

Kay Harrison (University of Auckland)

33. What's beyond Twitter/X?

Meredith Hinze (University of Melbourne), Sharon Altena (Queensland University of Technology),
Lye Ee (Rebecca) Ng (University of Wollongong)

34. Uniting expertise

Minh Huynh, Fran Van Den Berg, Osu Lilje, Liana Pozza, Floris Van Ogtrop (University of Sydney)

35. To Trial or Not to Trial: A Space Invaders' Dilemma

Naomi Millgate, Colleen Hodgins (James Cook University)

36. The seven-year itch: Are Directors' and learning designers' perceptions of the role of learning designers a marriage made in heaven?

Ruth Greenaway (Southern Cross University), Dom McGrath, Christine Slade (The University of Queensland)

37. Hard-pressed, but not crushed: A disposition of the heart in the space in-between

Rebecca Kan, Eliza Yeo Hui (Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts, University of the Arts Singapore)

38. Weeding through data? A tool to cultivate dynamic learning environments

Roar Murphy, Muna Musarrat, Wayne Errington, Kristin Wiese, Ashley Beathe, Don Kollura
(Western Sydney University)

39. The advantages of networks and alliances for the third space

Silke Kirberg (Hochschule Niederrhein University of Applied Sciences)

40. Co-design an AI literacies framework

Stephen Abblitt, Adelle Ryall (Keypath Education)

41. Collaborative research agenda

Stephen Abblitt (Keypath Education)

42. 3S professional experiences with sense-making to drive successful partnership outcomes

Tran Nguyen, Lisa Soviero (Keypath Education)

43. What does the third space look like?

Wendy Taleo (Monash University)

44. I'm in higher education's third space, who is here with me?

Zoë Allman (De Montfort University)

45. Journeys into third space working: Personal experiences of boundary-crossing

Tara Webster-Deakin (University of Nottingham), Charlotte Verney (University of Bristol), Kelly Vere (University of Nottingham)

46. Cover to cover: A thesis radio journey

Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

Third Space Slowposium sessions: Synchronous

47. (Re)Imagining the future of Faculty professional development

Alexandra Mihai (Maastricht University), Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

48. Fireside chat – Higher Education Third Space research group (HETS)

Maeve O'Dwyer (Dublin City University), Rebecca Sanderson (University of Lincoln)

49. Explore a new framework to evolve third space relationships

Natalia Veles (James Cook University), Colin Simpson (University of Sydney)

50. Coffee with Puva

Puvaneswari P Arumugam (Deakin University)

51. How can we facilitate third space working within our organisations?

Tara Webster-Deakin (University of Nottingham), Charlotte Verney (University of Bristol), Kelly Vere (University of Nottingham)

52. #LTHE Twitter/X chat

Wendy Taleo (Monash University), Gosia Drewniok (University of Bristol), Maeve O'Dwyer (Dublin City University)

53. Empowering professional identity... through third space collaboration

Claire Toogood (Association of Graduate Careers Advisory Services), Katy Hale (Aston University)

In-person program

NAVIGATING THE THIRD SPACE

WORKING WELL IN TERTIARY EDUCATION

Sunday 1 December 2024

Arts West Building (Building 148)

University of Melbourne

Royal Parade, Parkville VIC 3052

Wurundjeri Country

SYMPOSIUM PRESENTATION	WHEN	WHERE	WHEN	WHERE
Sign in	From 9 AM			outside the Forum Theatre
Acknowledgement of Country, welcome to University of Melbourne, and housekeeping ~ Meredith Hinze Welcome to the Symposium ~ Colin Simpson	9:30 AM			Forum Theatre
Extending the Slowposium - Learning Design and TELedvisors SIGs projects ~ Colin Simpson, Kate Mitchell, Kashmira Dave, Keith Heggart	9:45 AM			Forum Theatre
Leading and working with leaders in the tertiary education Third Space - ML Huppertz, Elaine Huber, Colin Simpson	10:05 AM			Forum Theatre
Morning tea ~Third Space Skills and Competencies	10:30 AM to 11:00 AM			outside the Forum Theatre
SYMPOSIUM PRESENTATION	WHEN	WHERE	WHEN	WHERE
Learning without limits: Designing transdisciplinary courses ~ Jacqui Thornley, Anne McKay	11:00 AM to 11:20 AM	Forum Theatre		
From Third Space to shared space: a speculative renovation of university role architecture ~ Miriam Reynoldson			11:00 AM to 11:20 AM	Room 155
Partners in crime: Nexus ed developers as co-leads ~ Jon Cai, Diana Turnip, Zara Khan			11:00 AM to 11:20 AM	Room 156
Theorising the Third Space ~ Stephen Abblitt	11:25 AM to 12:05 PM	Forum Theatre		
Hubs-and-spokes for professional development? ~ James Thompson, Kate Tregloan			11:25 AM to 11:45 AM	Room 155
Reclaiming the resources we make ~ Dana Bui			11:25 AM to 11:40 AM	Room 156
Building connections: LinkedIn for women leaders ~ Kranthi Addanki, Helmy Cook, Karine Cosgrove, Leanne Ngo and Simone Tyrell			11:40 AM to 12:30 PM	Room 156
NTEU: Where to from here? ~ Ruth Jelley	12:10 PM to 12:30 PM	Forum Theatre		
Lunch	12:30 PM to 1:30 PM ~ outside the Forum Theatre			
Lunchtime meetups: ~ Shaping the ASCILITE LD SIG Research Mentorship Program ~ Kashmira Dave, Leanne Ngo ~ Designing together: co-creating a collaborative learning design guide for third space professionals ~ Kashmira Dave, Leanne Ngo, Kate Mitchell, Keith Heggart			12:50 PM to 1:30 PM	Forum Theatre

Last update: 24 Nov. 24

Third Space Symposium, 1 December 2024, page 1

NAVIGATING THE THIRD SPACE continued (afternoon program)

SYMPOSIUM PRESENTATION	WHEN	WHERE	WHEN	WHERE
Using activity theory to explore the complexities of Third Space practitioner identity ~ <i>May Kocatepe</i>	1:30 PM to 1:45 PM	Forum Theatre		
Beyond the binary: Third space allyship and equity in the academy ~ <i>Aster Cosmos, Miriam Reynoldson</i>			1:30 PM to 1:50 PM	Room 156
Collaborative autoethnography on Third Space identity ~ <i>Puvaneswari P Arumugam, Mahen Jayawardena</i>	1:50 PM to 2:05 PM	Forum Theatre		
Research for all in the future university ~ <i>Olivia Inwood</i>	2:05 PM to 2:20 PM	Forum Theatre		
Framework for academic developers ~ <i>Kate Tregloan, Naima Iftikhar</i>			2:25 PM to 3:00 PM	Room 156
Knowing, Doing and Showing: A framework for evidencing learning design practice ~ <i>Sue Sharpe, Jenny Boreland, Tanya Henry</i>	2:25 PM to 3:00 PM	Forum Theatre		
Navigating the ebbs and flows of change ~ <i>Katie Freund, Karlene Dickens, Fang Li</i>	3:05 PM to 3:55 PM	Forum Theatre		
Establishing credibility ~ <i>Sharon Altena, Meredith Hinze, Rebecca Ng</i>			3:05 PM to 3:55 PM	Room 156
Show and tell from the day Prize giving Thanks & close	4:00 PM to 4:30 PM	Forum Theatre		

THANKS!

Thanks to our generous sponsors ATEM (Association for Tertiary Education Management)

Thanks to our volunteers and special thanks to today's presenters from across the Third Space.

Thanks also to the University of Melbourne and ASCILITE for their hosting and co-operation.

Legend for the schedule:

Green	Forum Theatre (Room 153)
Pink	Room 155
Yellow	Room 156

SCAN FOR MORE INFORMATION

link: <http://bit.ly/3CEHrx>

List of contributors

Contributions to these Proceedings are listed in alphabetical order by first author. Bibliographic details are presented in APA 7 style for suggested citation format.

- Abblitt, S. (2025). Theorising the third space. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 10-11). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844932>
- Addanki, K., Cook, H., Cosgrove, K., Ngo, L., & Tyrell, S. (2025). Building connections: Enhancing LinkedIn presence for third space women. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 2-3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844331>
- Allman, Z. (2025). I'm in higher education's third space: who is here with me? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 12-13). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844946>
- Altena, S., Hinze, M., & Ng, L. E. (2025). Establishing your credibility. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 69-73). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845215>
- Arumugam, P. P., & Jayawardena, M. (2025). Collaborative autoethnography on third space identity. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 14). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844956>
- Bartlett, C., & Derrington, K. (2025). Sharing the oxygen mask. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 74). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845223>
- Bui, D. (2025). Reclaiming the resources we make. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 42-47). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845098>
- Butters-Stabb, H. (2025). On the (in)visibility of librarians in third space literature. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 15-16). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844973>
- Caldwell, J. (2025). Uncontracted: Reimagining work and identity in higher education's third space. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 120-123). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845373>

- Cosmos, A., & Reynoldson, M., (2025). Beyond the binary: Third space allyship and equity in the academy. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 82–88). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845271>
- Freund, K., Dickens, K., & Li, F. (2025). Navigating the ebbs and flows of change. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 124). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845387>
- Greenaway, R., McGrath, D., & Slade, C. (2025). The seven-year itch: Are directors' and learning designers' perceptions of the role of learning designers a marriage made in heaven? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 17–18). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844983>
- Heggart, K., Mitchell, K., & Simpson, C. (2025). Capturing third space skills and competencies. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 61–62). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845187>
- Hinze, M., Altena, S. & Ng, L. E. (2025). What's Beyond Twitter / X? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 4–6). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844894>
- Hodgins, C., & Millgate, N. (2025). To trial or not to trial? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 116–117). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845348>
- Hook, J., Luu, J., Perry, P., Broomhead, F., Cosmos, A., Ahuja, Y., Boniface, B., Sell, C., Sapsed, C., & Junor, A. (2025). Reflecting on educational design practice. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 48-60). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845108>
- Hosseini, D. (2025). Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of third space professionals. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 75). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845233>
- Huynh, M., Van Den Berg, F., Lilje, O., Pozza, L., & Van Ogtrop, F. (2025). Uniting expertise. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 118). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845357>
- Inwood, C. (2025). Research for all in the future university. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 108). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845331>
- Kan, R., & Hui, E. Y. (2025). Hard-pressed, but not crushed: A disposition of the heart in the space in-between. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 19–26). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845000>
- Kiddell, J., & Quirk, S. (2025). Co-creating in the third space with friends. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 89). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845287>

- Kirberg, S. (2025). The advantages of networks and alliances for the third space. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 7–8). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844911>
- Laurence, D., & Hinze, M. (2025). Learning Designers: To define or not to define. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 76–77). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845238>
- McIntosh, E., & Nutt, D. (2025). Third space careers visualised. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 125). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845397>
- Mihai, A., & Simpson, C. (2025). (Re)imagining the future of faculty PD. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 126–127). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845413>
- Molloy, K. (2025). (De)constructing the professional identities of third space practitioners through zine making. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 27–28). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845014>
- Murray, D. (2025). Standing out in the third space. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 29–31). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845026>
- Nguyen, T., & Soviero, L. (2025). How sense-making drives successful partnerships. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 90–91). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845298>
- Parry, M. (2025). I am not a chicken farmer. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 92–97). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845306>
- Reynoldson, M. (2025). From third space to shared space. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 128–135). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845419>
- Sharpe, S., Boreland, J., & Henry, T. (2025). Knowing, doing and showing. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 32–33). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845035>
- Simpson, C. (2025). Cover to cover: A thesis radio journey. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 109–114). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845343>
- Simpson, C. (2025). Make your pitch: let's solve the question of third space titles. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 34–35). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845053>
- Stothers, J., (2025). What can learning design do? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 63–64). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845193>

- Taleo, W. (2025). What does the third space look like? In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 36–38). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845059>
- Toogood, C., & Hale, K. (2025). Empowering professional identity ... through third space collaboration. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 39). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845065>
- Tregloan, K., & Iftikhar, N. (2025). Framework for academic developers. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 40). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845078>
- Turnip, D. S., Cai, J. X., & Khan, Z. (2025). Partners in crime. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (p. 65). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845199>
- Turnip, D. S., Macaulay, M., McDougall, E., Harris, M., Danish, N., Thite, S., Cai, J. X., Khan, Z., Amarnath, A., Moray, C., & Lawrence, N., (2025). "Inside the third space" podcast series. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 78–80). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845249>
- Vallis, C., & Taleo, W. (2025). Speculative future university 2050. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 136–138). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845430>
- Veles, N., & Simpson, C. (2025). Explore a new framework to evolve third space relationships. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 98–106). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845319>
- Verney, C., Vere, K., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2025). Journeys into third space working. In C. Simpson, S. Altena, E. Black & P. Wheeler (Eds.), *Navigating the third space: Proceedings of the 2024 Third Space Symposium* (pp. 66–67). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845209>